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D4.3 - Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption & monitoring report – final version

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
DEP	Digital Europe Programme
DMS	Document Management System
DTPC	Deputy Technical Project Coordinator
EAG	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FACL	Financial & Administrative Coordinator Leader
GA	Grant Agreement
KOM	Kick-off meeting
LCMS	Learning Content Management System
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NEB	New European Bauhaus
PMB	Project Management Board
R&I	Research and Innovation
SG	Stakeholder Group
The Consortium	All the Project Partners: TU DELFT + EAAE + ICF + IW
The Project Beneficiaries	The signatory Partners of the Grant Agreement: TU DELFT + EAAE + ICF + IW
TL	Task Leader
TWG	Thematic Working Group
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Keywords

Community, Engagement, Stakeholders, Collaboration, Inclusivity, Communication, Outreach, Participation

Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

The DigiNEB project supports the implementation of the New European Bauhaus (NEB) and accelerates the green transformation by increasing the adoption of NEB-aligned digital solutions. As a Coordination Action, DigiNEB has prioritised the identification and understanding of stakeholder needs to provide targeted knowledge support, networking opportunities, upskilling, and community participation. This document outlines the updated engagement objectives, evolving stakeholder groups, engagement channels, risks, and the roles and responsibilities of DigiNEB's partners.

The DigiNEB platform aims to deepen stakeholder understanding of the New European Bauhaus, keep stakeholders informed of key developments, contribute to the NEB digital transformation, and disseminate NEB best practices. It also fosters cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration, monitors the overall impact of NEB activities, and contributes to policy development and standardisation.

In 2023, DigiNEB played a pivotal role in rallying the NEB community around the NEB Mission, engaging Member States to support it during a key meeting at the Council of Europe on the 12th of September 2023. Following this, DigiNEB gathered eminent leaders from NEB Labs and Lighthouses to co-author a White Paper. This document, which was included as an annexe in deliverable D4.2, provides strategic direction for the NEB Mission's evolution and its eventual transition towards the NEB Facility, a future-focused funding mechanism. The White Paper captures the insights of thought leaders from across the NEB ecosystem and serves as a foundational guide for shaping the NEB's future, policy, and initiatives.

This final version of the updated Stakeholder Engagement Plan moves beyond addressing the initial catalogue of distinct target groups - architects, designers, educators, etc. Based on insights from the project's first phase and in consultation with partners, the plan has adopted a more flexible, mission-driven approach. This strategy unites multidisciplinary communities around topics of shared interest, following successful models from NEB projects such as *Bauhaus of the Seas Sails*, *Nordic Carbon-Neutral Bauhaus*, and *Bauhaus Goes South*. Aligning DigiNEB with these core themes has proven effective for onboarding large stakeholder pools, encouraging cross-sectoral collaboration, and promoting co-creation.

Since the project amendment and refocus, a major upgrade to the DigiNEB website provides a more intuitive and user-friendly interface, enhancing stakeholder access to valuable resources such as the *NEB Concepts* modular podcast. The revamped website now functions as a central hub for stakeholders, offering improved navigation, interactive learning tools, and databases that support co-creation activities.

The DigiNEB project is actively connecting with industry partners, European Digital Innovation Hubs (including Linköping Science Park), the EU Capital of Innovation (Linköping, Sweden), and a range of digital projects in alignment with the objectives set out in the Description of Action (DOA). Through the digital technical working groups/digital focus groups, a broad spectrum of stakeholders from different EU member and associated states has been engaged.

The **NEB Concepts modular podcast** was created to respond to challenges in sustaining meaningful engagement through traditional social media. It offers a modular approach, allowing users to explore themes such as sustainability, design, and innovation in a flexible format that promotes deeper

learning and engagement. This podcast represents a shift toward more substantive, long-term engagement strategies, moving away from the transient nature of social media.

This version of the deliverable includes a substantial new section (Section 5) that reports on the **final event** of the DigiNEB project in Brussels. **‘Celebrating the Lessons Learnt’** brought together 64 thought leaders from across the wider NEB community, including Lighthouses, Labs and other Coordination Actions as well as policymakers. The final event also featured dynamic discussions in a series of 'Think and Do Tanks' to reflect on lessons learnt and formulate concrete policy recommendations for the NEB roadmap. These outcomes are detailed in Section 5.13.

The final event launched the published ***Regional Innovation Model (RIM) Handbook***, based on NEB community activities with regional governments and using the Jan Åman and Adam Davies *Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook* as a foundation. The RIM Handbook is designed to be a companion to city and regional administrators. It includes practical examples of engagement and activities for local actors and changemakers in collaboration across sectors and disciplines. It suggests ways to think about grand challenges that address specific needs and characteristics of regional ecosystems while it offers support instruments and frameworks to leverage local intelligence and create a systemic shift at the global scale.

By focusing on ecosystemic approaches to regional development, the handbook ensures that the NEB community can benefit from proven methodologies and tools that drive innovation and collaboration across Europe. The handbook's launch was further supported by commitments from policymakers, including the plan for a second major launch event at the European Committee of the Regions yearly Plenary in April 2025. This strategic dissemination ensures the handbook's reach extends to policymakers across Europe, amplifying its utility as a cornerstone of regional NEB-aligned innovation.

In addition to these resources, the project has undergone significant development, including redesigning the **DigiNEB website** to provide a more intuitive and accessible hub for stakeholders. This upgraded platform offers enhanced features such as interactive learning tools, improved navigation, and the integration of **digital co-creation methodologies**.

Stakeholder engagement has evolved significantly, culminating in the joint event with CrAft and NEBula at Architect House in Brussels and the knowledge exchange at the **JUST Industry Data Week in Linköping**. The project's engagement strategy emphasises **data ethics and AI for social good**, integrating these themes into broader discussions around sustainability and digital transformation. These efforts are aligned with the project's goal of fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and supporting the NEB mission at the European level. This deliverable underscores the integration of digital and co-creation methodologies into the broader NEB mission, leveraging insights from events such as the JUST Industry Data Week and the final Brussels event.

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1. Introduction

The predecessor to this document, *D4.2 Stakeholder Engagement Plan and Adoption & Monitoring Report – Intermediate Version*, outlined the developing strategy for engaging stakeholders in the New European Bauhaus (NEB) digital ecosystem, making significant alterations after a comprehensive review and project amendment.

This final iteration of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan and Adoption Monitoring Report captures the substantial evolution of the DigiNEB project, highlighting key advancements in both methodology and impact. The most notable addition is the new, comprehensive Section 5, which documents the outcomes of the project's final event, **Celebrating the Lessons Learnt**, held in Brussels. This pivotal gathering brought together thought leaders from across the NEB ecosystem, producing invaluable policy recommendations and fostering a collective vision for the future of NEB initiatives.

Another key stakeholder engagement achievement described in this updated deliverable is the publication of the **Regional Innovation Model (RIM) Handbook**, a resource designed to support regional policymakers and communities in applying NEB principles through ecosystemic thinking, and providing a model to adapt and scale local project ideas through the concatenation of funding instruments and leveraging the affordances of digital technologies through prototyping, experimentation and community engagement.

Additionally, the project has embraced more enduring media formats, including the NEB Concepts podcast and permanent long-form video content, ensuring that the project's insights and resources continue to benefit the community beyond the lifespan of the initiative. These shifts reflect a strategic response to the limitations of ephemeral social media content, prioritising deeper engagement and sustained knowledge transfer.

This deliverable showcases DigiNEB's success in galvanising the NEB community, driving collaboration, stakeholder outreach and contributing meaningfully to the digital and cultural transformation envisioned by the New European Bauhaus.

2. Engagement Objectives

The ethos of the New European Bauhaus requires that stakeholders become more than an atomised cloud of individual users but rather active community participants, bridging digital and technological divides. This participation requires building trust within a diverse group of potential users and stakeholders, and engagement must occur transversally. Trust must be built between silos and among stakeholders from diverse knowledge domains and backgrounds – not simply between each user and the platform but amongst the many kinds of users. Key to this level of engagement is reaching out to and connecting with NEB partners, engaging with their projects, becoming well-informed of existing activities and projects, bringing them together in a space of common understanding, connecting across domains, fostering interdisciplinary understanding and monitoring the evolution of NEB in the global context.

These original engagement objectives have been central to the ongoing efforts of DigiNEB, refined and developed as part of the revision and amendment of the overall engagement plan. They were designed to foster collaboration between stakeholders in the NEB and digital communities and facilitate the adoption of NEB principles in alignment with the Green Deal. The following sections outline these objectives, with updates based on project progress and the revised priorities.

One of the main goals of DigiNEB is to interlink and unite the NEB community by providing specific mechanisms to identify and reach out to complementary stakeholder groups. To that end, DigiNEB developed a comprehensive Engagement Strategy for the project, focusing on tackling Engagement Objectives, Target Stakeholder Groups, Engagement Channels, Risks and Mitigations, and the DigiNEB Partners' Engagement Roles and Responsibilities. In doing so, assumptions about the needs and use cases of stakeholders, as well as about the nature and potential of the project, were tested, and accordingly, the ambition and focus of the DigiNEB project's stakeholder engagement were expanded and developed as demonstrated below.

2.1. Increase understanding between the New European Bauhaus and Smart Communities

The DigiNEB initiative sought to create a platform for two-way communication, with dialogue and co-creation central to the process. It is of primary importance to clarify what the New European Bauhaus is and what it represents to current and potential future stakeholders.

Understanding how NEB creates meaning for stakeholders involved reaching out to all NEB partners and engaging with the existing and developing projects active in the New European Bauhaus ecosystem. Connection with **NEB Lab projects** and **NEB lighthouse projects** provided the DigiNEB Coordination Action with an already extensive network of engaged and active stakeholders. Second, attention to innovative tools devised in both the public and private sectors at the European level was essential to enhancing the project's outreach and its platform.

Significant progress was made in this area, at first through the success of the **NEB@CERN** event, which exceeded several of our KPIs ahead of schedule. As outlined in the intermediary report d4.2, the project identified areas for improvement in digital engagement and undertook a comprehensive redesign of the DigiNEB website to create a more engaging and user-friendly experience. The revamp was part of a larger strategy to foster ongoing dialogue and improve user retention across all stakeholder groups.

In addition to increased collaboration and communication with other NEB initiatives, the DigiNEB project worked closely with every Lighthouse, Lab and NEB CSA projects to create the **Regional Innovation Model (RIM) Handbook** and the programme and content for the **Final Event 'Celebrating the Lessons Learnt'** gathering NEB thought leaders in Brussels on the 17 and 18 December 2024 (see section 5 below).

2.2. Increase capacity for all involved stakeholders and support continuous learning

A key objective of the stakeholder engagement strategy was to become and remain well-informed of existing NEB activities and projects on the ground that may have an impact on or are of direct relevance to digital platform creators. In their capacity as Early Adopters, successful NEB community projects were actively involved in DigiNEB co-creation activities with digital communities for capacity building and contributions to effective Green Deal solutions. As has been discussed elsewhere (D4.1, D4.2, D3.3., D3.4), the DigiNEB programme included a variety of methods for capacity building, including webinars, co-creation events, and a significant contribution to the establishment of the new NEB Academy (see 2.5). This has ensured that all stakeholders have access to the knowledge and skills needed to fully participate in the NEB digital ecosystem.

Capacity building has been the primary focus of the modular NEB Concepts podcast series that draws on the knowledge of the NEB champions and thought leaders. The podcast modules allow for expert knowledge to be searched using tag words for individual topics covered within the areas of sustainability, design, and innovation. This modular podcast allows users to explore a wide range of themes, such as climate adaptation, technology integration, and interdisciplinary collaboration,

through insightful conversations with leading architects, educators, and project leaders. By allowing listeners to choose their own pathway and follow either the broader themes or the detailed thoughts of individual interviewees, the podcast offers a flexible, dynamic resource for ongoing learning.

The podcast complements the project’s wider aim of providing content that extends beyond social media platforms, offering a more sustainable and direct form of engagement. With a focus on topics central to the NEB, such as sustainability, innovation, and human-centred design, the podcast highlights practical applications of NEB principles in areas like urban development, cultural heritage, and community empowerment. This positions it as a critical tool for disseminating knowledge and best practices across the NEB community and beyond, allowing stakeholders to access a diverse array of ideas and methodologies that are directly relevant to their work.

The focus on capacity building was evolved with the *Regional Innovation Model (RIM) Handbook as a key resource for local administrators and policymakers.* Drawing on best practices from JRC and DG REGIO publications and initiatives, as well as insights and extensive examples from NEB Labs and Lighthouse projects, the handbook provides guidance, activities and management approaches for implementing NEB principles on the ground and scaling them for the benefit of Europe and beyond. The RIM Handbook was first soft-launched during the DigiNEB Day ‘*JUST Living Environments: AI for Social Good*’ at the JUST Industry Data Week at the European Digital Innovation Hub (EDIH), Linköping Science Park, with participation both in person and online, further expanding the capacity of stakeholders to contribute to the NEB mission. The published and printed version was then officially launched as a major part of the DigiNEB final event, ‘Lessons Learnt’, at Architecture House in Brussels in December 2024.

The RIM Handbook, aimed at local and regional policymakers, civic leaders, and innovators, provides a comprehensive framework for addressing and scaling complex societal challenges through ecosystemic thinking. The Handbook advocates for collaborative, interdisciplinary approaches that integrate community engagement and evidence-based policymaking, thereby ensuring that regional innovation efforts are sustainable, inclusive, and adaptive to local needs.

The RIM Handbook outlines and responds to the primary framework conditions of our age: the urgent need for cross-domain collaboration and knowledge exchange, the requirement to leverage all expertise and intelligence, focusing on ground-up community engagement, and the emergence of an entirely data-driven society. Drawing on a wide range of sources from across the NEB community, the book collates and presents best practices from studies and publications by the Joint Research Centre (JRC), the European Committee of the Regions (CoR), all of the NEB lighthouses, as well as related initiatives, agencies and organisations. It highlights key tools such as the NEB Compass, strategies from the Partnerships for Regional Innovation Playbook, tools and approaches from the Innovation for Place-Based Transformation ACTIONbook, insights from the Handbook of Sustainable Urban Development Strategies, and dozens of applicable case studies, tools, methodologies, knowledge and results from successful NEB projects and labs. The book also includes insights and feedback from exclusive interviews with key figures in the NEB Community.

Inspired by documented practice, papers, publications and results from the NEB activities, the handbook emphasises the role of local and regional policymakers as change enablers - leaders capable of galvanising diverse communities and leveraging digital technologies to create innovative, context-specific solutions. As facilitators, mentors, and collaborators, public administrators are encouraged to gather diverse and interdisciplinary communities to co-create innovative, context-specific solutions, prototypes, and inventions using the best practice methodologies presented.

By acknowledging and integrating the core framework conditions - cross-domain collaboration, ground-up community engagement, and the data-driven society – the RIM Handbook provides a companion and reference for entrepreneurial public administrators to galvanise their communities to

locally address the global challenges of our time. The tested and validated tools and methodologies presented are grounded in practice and are designed to be adapted, scaled, and replicated across regions.

The Regional Innovation Model brings together businesses, academic institutions, local governments, community members, and more-than-human natural ecosystems and leverages the galvanising motivation of missions and grand challenges to inspire commitment, vision and local action. The Handbook amplifies existing research, results, methodologies, use cases and outputs piloted and validated by NEB initiatives and Lighthouse projects. The tools and actions presented enable co-creation and community participatory design in response to globally significant and locally felt grand challenges. It also discusses strategies for leveraging digital technologies and JUST (judicious, unbiased, safe and transparent) data practices to support the creation of AI for social good, as well as evidence-based approaches to crafting policies responsive to local needs, global trends, legal frameworks and the evolving technological environment.

By promoting hands-on experimentation, interdisciplinary collaboration, and citizen engagement, the handbook provides local and regional administrators with actionable tools to implement NEB principles in real-world contexts. This resource not only supports continuous community learning but also enables regions to develop resilient, future-facing ecosystems that align with the goals of the New European Bauhaus.

2.3. Contribute to the digital transformation from multiple perspectives

DigiNEB aims to continuously support both New European Bauhaus and Smart Communities breakthroughs, novel projects, and initiatives to allow all engaged stakeholders to keep learning from each other. These include learning through digital and NEB partnerships with global communities.

As the engagement strategy is not merely one of dissemination but also of providing tools and benefits for users, close collaboration between NEB and digital stakeholders has been essential. Co-creation activities addressed the challenges of digitalisation, with Early Adopter NEB communities contributing insights from sustainability, usability, and accessibility perspectives. DigiNEB leverages the best practices and knowledge from the NEB community to create opportunities for multidisciplinary collaboration towards a triple transformation in Europe: digital, green, and socially inclusive.

Members of the DigiNEB Advisory Board have been notably very active in supporting this objective, making significant contributions of knowledge and perspectives to the project. One member from outside the EU has actively supported the global community perspective: Sheela Patel is a member of the NEB High Level Round Table and is the founder and director of the Society for Promotion of Area Resource Centres (SPARC). She defines herself as an academic and activist who works "with people living in slums and informal settlements in the Global South." Much of her work focuses on education, and she has been a valuable contributor to the project by transferring lessons learned globally.

In addition to Sheela, while not being official members of the External Advisory, several other international members of the NEB HLRT contributed remotely and in person to the DigiNEB final event in Brussels, expressing their own 'lessons learnt' from the first few years of the New European Bauhaus from their own perspectives (see Section 5.X below)

2.4. Enable cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration

The NEB's emphasis on reimagining living spaces as more sustainable, inclusive, and beautiful requires input from a diverse array of disciplines, particularly those where digital tools intersect with

physical environments. DigiNEB facilitates this by enabling stakeholders to collaborate across sectors and share best practices that lead to impactful, long-lasting improvements to how we design, build, and experience our environments.

JUST Industry Data Week at Linköping Science Park in September 2024 was a key event where cross-domain collaboration was put into action to further these NEB goals. The week-long series of discussions, experiments, and workshops focused on bringing together experts from different industries—health, urban planning, AI, and data sciences—to jointly explore how judicious, unbiased, safe and transparent data practices can be used in AI applications and enhance living environments.

A core component was the *Sound for Urban Environments* track, exploring how AI, automation, and data can be used to create healthier, more responsive urban soundscapes. This directly aligns with NEB’s mission of designing spaces that are not only more sustainable but also more conducive to human well-being. Sound, as a cultural and technological element, plays a critical role in shaping how we experience cities, public spaces, and even homes. By bringing together stakeholders from the tech sector, urban planning, and cultural industries, the event fosters collaborative experimentation that can lead to the development of NEB-compliant solutions for urban living environments.

JUST Industry Data Week also served as a platform for expanding NEB’s principles of sustainability and inclusion into new domains. Participants engaged in hands-on experiments using data from the Swedish Space Data Lab 3.0, the Health Data Innovation Platform, and AI Factory data labs applications. These cross-domain activities bridged the gap between different industries and knowledge areas, promoting NEB values in a diverse range of contexts. This not only facilitated the creation of new, inclusive digital tools but also ensured that the innovations were deeply embedded in local living environments.

Additionally, the focus on data ethics and AI for social good is directly relevant to NEB’s objective of creating spaces that are not just physically sustainable but also socially equitable and inclusive. The discussions during JUST Industry Data Week explored how AI models can be trained and applied in ways that respect privacy, fairness, and inclusivity, ensuring that digital innovations benefit all citizens equally. By integrating AI and data ethics into NEB’s broader mission, the event generated solutions that are both technologically advanced and ethically grounded, thus supporting the NEB community’s ongoing efforts to build sustainable and inclusive living environments that enhance quality of experience.

The cross-domain collaborations fostered by JUST Industry Data Week provided a crucial advantage to the NEB community by expanding the application of NEB principles beyond traditional sectors. These collaborations helped develop holistic, data-driven approaches to designing and managing living environments that fully integrate sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetics—fulfilling the core objectives of the New European Bauhaus.

A full overview of the content, outcomes and impact of the JUST Industry Data Week can be found in deliverable D3.4 Early Adopter network – national and regional adoption (final version).

3. Target Stakeholder Groups

Seven stakeholder groups were selected to lead the engagement within the NEB community. Each of these groups brought their perspective, expertise, and skills to the project and were involved in different ways. The Stakeholder Groups (SGs) were identified to create a comprehensive network that facilitated interactions between digital and New European Bauhaus players. Details about the Engagement Plan for each SG are presented in Chapter 4.

A full description of the Stakeholder target groups can be found as an Annex in deliverable D4.2.

Engagement of all target stakeholder groups

The stakeholder engagement strategies outlined in *D4.1* provided a structured approach for engaging distinct target groups, such as architects, urban planners, and community organisers. However, as the project has progressed, it became evident that there is significant fluidity between these groups, driven by overlapping interests, cross-sectoral knowledge, and an increasing recognition that challenges within the New European Bauhaus (NEB) ecosystem require interdisciplinary solutions.

3.1. Evolving Stakeholder Group Dynamics

One of the most striking developments in the engagement process has been the natural overlap between stakeholder groups (SGs) originally considered distinct. For instance, architects involved in sustainable urban design often wear multiple hats, contributing not only as designers but also as educators, policy influencers, and digital innovators. This intersection of roles has blurred the boundaries between stakeholder categories, with many contributors actively engaging across several domains.

A notable development is the successful integration of stakeholder groups from outside those originally listed in the proposal, confirming the relevance of the junction between the NEB and the digital. A particularly notable example is the health sector's growing interest in the NEB framework. Health professionals, drawn by the intersection of environmental factors such as air quality and public health outcomes, are increasingly contributing to discussions around the built environment and its impact on well-being. This overlap has expanded the project's reach and demonstrated the wider applicability of NEB's principles, especially regarding how digital tools and data-driven solutions can be leveraged to improve both environmental and health outcomes.

3.2. Expanding the Target Stakeholder Groups

As a result of these cross-sectoral engagements, the original target SGs were broadened. This expansion was driven by the increasing recognition that solutions developed within the NEB ecosystem, such as AI tools for environmental monitoring or digital platforms for urban planning, have relevance beyond their initial fields of application.

While *D4.1* primarily focused on engaging architects, designers, urban planners, and construction professionals, the project saw growing participation from experts in the fields of health, digital ethics, and data science. As discussed in the intermediate deliverable D4.2, air quality monitoring, initially considered within the domain of environmental and urban design, has attracted the

attention of health professionals and researchers interested in how built environments influence public health. This broader inclusion of stakeholders from the health sector highlights the potential of NEB tools to drive innovation in unexpected but crucial areas, further expanding the project's scope and impact.

This widening of SGs has been reflected in the recruitment strategies for DigiNEB's digital focus groups and activities. Invitations to participate were extended not only to core NEB contributors, such as members of the External Advisory Board (EAB) and professional associations within the NEB ecosystem but also to professionals from sectors previously considered outside the project's original scope. This approach helped bridge the gaps between different SGs and facilitated greater cross-pollination of ideas. This intersection of a broader representation of communities and specialisms was anticipated as part of the DigiNEB day (and with involvement on other days) at the JUST Industry Data Week at Linköping Science Park.

digINEB at the JUST Data Week

Date & Time: 20 September 2024, 10:00-19:00

Venue: Online

Registration: [Register here](#)

[DigiNEB](#) is hosting a dedicated day focused on **data and AI applications for social good**, with a specific emphasis on enhancing the quality of life in living environments at [JUST Data Week](#), which aims to establish Judicious, Un-biased, Safe and Transparent (JUST) data practices as a complement to FAIR data.

The day will explore **how data-driven systems and technologies can transform urban spaces**, featuring insights from the NEB community and beyond, and reflect on JUST Data practices, emphasizing hands-on, collaborative methods for innovation across sectors like the built environment, transportation, healthcare, and earth observation.

Main highlights of the digINEB day:

✓ **10:00 Keynote on Benevolence and Invention**

Robert Cailliau, CERN Fellow and co-creator of the World Wide Web.

✓ **13:30 Launch of the Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation**

After two years of research, collaboration, and iterative development, the digINEB project is ready to launch the Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation. The handbook aims to **foster sustainable, locally-situated and inclusive regional development** across Europe and it provides innovative ideas and practical implementation, ensuring that regional innovation is rooted in the values of sustainability, inclusivity, and democratic participation.

✓ **18:00 Launch of the Susan Lesley Bland Prize for Social Good**

Presented by Robert Cailliau, the Susan Lesley Bland Prize for Social Good will be **awarded for applications and prototypes** created during a week of prototyping in urban environments using NEB methodologies.

Promotion of the DigiNEB Day at JUST Data Week through the European Commission's New European Bauhaus Community email newsletter

Insights, reflections, lessons and impacts of the Digital Focus Groups have been explored in detail in deliverable d2.5 Landscape Report and Gap Analysis.

3.3. Impact of Fluidity on Engagement and Adoption

The growing fluidity between stakeholder groups has a positive effect on both engagement and the adoption of DigiNEB's digital tools. Stakeholders from diverse backgrounds see the relevance of NEB tools in their own contexts, even if those tools were originally designed for other domains. This cross-domain interest is a significant development, as it opens the door for broader adoption of DigiNEB platforms across new industries. The fluidity between SGs not only enhances the relevance of DigiNEB's offerings but also supports a more collaborative and interdisciplinary approach to solving the complex challenges that NEB seeks to address. As more stakeholders from diverse fields engage with the project, the potential for innovative solutions that bridge the gap between disciplines continues to grow.

This dynamic interaction among stakeholders has also influenced the content of key deliverables, such as the *DigiNEB Deployment Roadmap* and the *Ethics Report*, ensuring that insights from a wider range of experts are incorporated into the project's strategic planning. The involvement of diverse sector professionals, digital ethics experts, and others from outside the initial SGs has enriched the project's understanding of the broader societal impact of NEB solutions, positioning DigiNEB as a platform that supports interdisciplinary collaboration at its core.

4. Engagement Channels: Summary of Updated Plan

Over the project lifespan, the strategic methodologies outlined in DigiNEB's engagement and adoption plan significantly evolved to reflect the changing dynamics of community interactions and the insights gained from the early phases of the project. The initial strategies, while effective in laying the foundation for stakeholder engagement, have been refined to better address the challenges and opportunities that have emerged.

- **A key development has been the recognition that in-person and hybrid gatherings of the DigiNEB community are essential for fostering deeper collaboration and co-creation.** With the easing of restrictions following the COVID-19 pandemic, these gatherings have become more feasible and are now being prioritised as central components of DigiNEB's engagement strategy. In-person events and meetings organised on behalf of DigiNEB by External Advisory Board Members and the 6-day JUST Industry Data Week in Linköping, as well as the final 'Celebrating the Lessons Learnt' event in Brussels, reflect this shift, allowing for both face-to-face and digital participation.
- **The project's updated strategy called for upgrading traditional social media channels to ones that encourage deeper learning and knowledge transfer.** It became clear that traditional social media approaches were not sufficient to sustain meaningful engagement. By shifting the focus from simple content dissemination to interactive, educational platforms, DigiNEB has been able to foster more impactful and lasting engagement within its community, creating persistent content that can be used in NEB Academy and other contexts beyond the life of the DigiNEB project.
- **A priority in this updated plan and its delivery has been engaging EU regions through the transfer of methodologies that support collaborative learning and innovation.** This updated plan incorporated revisions to the engagement channels, introducing new methodologies that prioritise collaborative learning, co-creation, and innovation. It also includes new tools,

such as the revamped DigiNEB website, the *NEB Concepts* podcast, and the *Regional Innovation Model (RIM) Handbook*, all of which are designed to facilitate both policy influence and community-driven innovation. These enhancements ensure that DigiNEB remains adaptable and responsive to the evolving needs of the NEB community.

The final version of the RIM Handbook is attached to this deliverable as an Annexe and can also be found on Zenodo at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14494301>

4.1. Project identity update

The DigiNEB project underwent a visual and conceptual identity update to better reflect the evolving nature of its role within the New European Bauhaus (NEB) ecosystem. The updated project identity drew inspiration from the traditional and digital tools used by architects and planners, positioning DigiNEB as a blueprint for future NEB interactions in the digital space.

The logo and branding incorporate design elements that evoke architectural schematics and planning blueprints, symbolising DigiNEB's commitment to creating structured yet flexible digital solutions for sustainability, innovation, and inclusion. This visual language emphasises the project's focus on bridging the physical and digital realms, aligning with the NEB's goal of reimagining spaces and environments in ways that harmonise aesthetics, function, and ecological responsibility. The identity not only reflects the project's current activities but also its vision for the future—serving as a guiding framework for digital transformation in the built environment.

The identity is a collaborative effort between project partners with multiple layers added by different stakeholders to indicate evolving collaborations.

4.2. DigiNEB Website (DigiNEB.eu)

THE DigiNEB INITIATIVE

Digital Tools

Digital Tools for

Digital Projects

Projects that develop

E-learning

E-learning and training

Open Licences

Open Licenses for

The relaunched DigiNEB website serves as the cornerstone of the updated engagement strategy, offering a more intuitive user experience, improved navigation, and new features designed to enhance knowledge transfer and collaboration.

It provides clarity on the available digital tools and learning materials, promotes notable NEB initiatives and supports open science.

THE DigiNEB INITIATIVE

Digital Tools

Digital Tools for Architects, Designers and Communities

Digital Projects

Projects that develop Digital Tools or Innovations that can support the Objectives of NEB

E-learning

E-learnings and training modules

Open Licences

Open Licences for Data and Content that can be freely used, modified, and shared

4.3. Digital Focus Groups (formerly TWGs)

The DigiNEB.eu platform embeds and disseminates the interdisciplinary Thematic Working Groups (TWGs) as Digital Focus Groups under the broad overarching themes of 1) Design & Architecture, 2) Production & Construction, 3) Verticals, and 4) Community & Sustainability and AI. These groups bring together stakeholder experts and broader community contributors into the DigiNEB.eu ecosystem.

In line with the updated Description of Action for reaching the objectives of the project, top-level experts are invited to consult with the digital technical groups. Desk research on the representative stakeholders was conducted, including both internal stakeholders, such as the members of the EAB and members affiliated with the professional associations who are project partners in the consortium, external stakeholders, such as professionals with a background in early and visible adoption of digital solutions, entities engaging in civic engagement, members in professional communities and professional associations within the broader New European Bauhaus community.

To reach the desired number of participants, we aimed for an initial sample of 3 times the number of desired participants. As such, an average of 20 invitations were sent for each group from EU member states and associated countries.

Other recruitment strategies included disseminating the TWGs / Digital Focus Groups in:

- the NEB newsletter through the European contact point for NEB;
- the NEB community platform calendar of events;
- presentation given in the European Federation for Living Social Topic Group;
- the TU Delft AI initiative

The input from the four thematic digital technical working groups has also fed into the following deliverables:

- D.1.4. Ethics report.
- D.2.5. Landscape report and gap analysis – final version.
- D5.3. DigiNEB Deployment Roadmap.

The Digital Focus Groups are open to all stakeholders and form a focal point of stakeholder engagement. They are organised around thematic areas developed with the NEB community, and add to the workshops organised in WP5, producing a series of reports on landscape and gap analysis, best practices and other relevant topics. The groups also contribute to networking events. Community co-creation helps evolve and shape the thematic areas listed in the DigiNEB proposal:

- Design & Architecture
 - Enhancing biodiversity; eco-systemic decision-making in design
 - Circular Design, design for disassembly/deconstruction
 - Morphology of human settlements: organising the relationship of urbanity and rurality
 - Architectural-data cycles for sustainable design qualities
 - Sustainable design of the rural area
 - Creative design & project environment
 - Biogenic carbon storage: designing buildings and cities as carbon banks
- Production & Construction
 - Digitising the building sector: applications throughout building and urban life cycles (online presence, VR, home automation, etc.)
 - Technologies for a sustainable construction industry
 - Engineered biomaterials and novel building products for construction
 - Additive manufacturing and CNC cutting

- Technologies for a sustainable textiles industry & other innovative materials
- Creative startups
- Verticals
 - Healthy living environment and buildings for health(care)
 - Education
 - Future-proof heritage
 - Existing housing stock and infrastructure
 - Building manufacturing
 - Building & mobility
- Community & Sustainability
 - People and their communities: user-centred criteria/participatory design processes for sustainable and smart urbanisation
 - Fair and just transitions: equity and empowerment for disenfranchised populations
 - Biogenic carbon storage: buildings and cities as carbon banks
 - Energy transition and climate adaptation in the construction industry
 - Impact assessment: gathering data and tracking our footprints
 - Ending waste: policies and practices in a circular construction economy

4.4. Upgrading Social Media Approaches

The project's approach to social media evolved to better support collaborative learning and knowledge transfer. While traditional social media channels played a role in the initial phases of the project and will continue to do so to a lesser extent, they have proven limited in fostering sustained engagement. The updated strategy moves beyond ephemeral content to dynamic and persistent content, including interactive dialogues encouraging deeper learning and stakeholder participation.

The project initially encountered limited success with static content dissemination, particularly on platforms such as Instagram, which did not foster the level of interaction needed to support the NEB community's goals. Social media have been leveraged to support events, announce publications, podcast releases and policy contributions. They are supportive rather than central to the strategy, encouraging stakeholders to engage more deeply with the substantive outputs and more enduring media dissemination and knowledge exchange initiatives of the project.

As a result of the upgraded approach, the KPIs outlined in the original plan have been revised, as they tended only to measure the quantity of output, such as the number of posts on particular platforms, rather than **more meaningful indicators or strategies for engagement by and with the NEB Community.**

4.5. Podcast: NEB Concepts

NEB Concepts

NEB Concepts features insightful conversations with leading architects, educators, and project leaders. The discussions deal with topics at the intersection of sustainability, innovation, and human-centred design. You'll hear directly from those shaping the future of urban development, cultural heritage, and community empowerment.

NEB Concepts is modular – it allows you to 'choose your own adventure': follow the links and tags to explore themes such as climate adaptation, technology integration, and interdisciplinary collaboration – or stick with the wide-ranging thoughts of a single interviewee.

Each short episode provides a collection of ideas and practices, projects and reflections, highlighting the transformative potential of the New European Bauhaus for a more inclusive and sustainable future.

Recognising the gap left by the social media disconnect described in 4.3 above, a key adaptation in the updated plan was the creation of the *NEB Concepts* podcast. Although producing a podcast was not required by the original DOA, it has been introduced as a direct response to the challenges faced in generating sustained engagement through traditional social media channels.

The podcast was developed as a dynamic and educational tool that can engage a broad audience.

The modular nature of the series allows users to explore topics based on their interests, such as sustainability, technology integration, or interdisciplinary collaboration. By offering deeper and more flexible content, the podcast provides a more robust and enduring medium for engagement, helping to overcome the limitations of more ephemeral social media interactions. This ensures that the NEB community and stakeholders can access sustained learning experiences that directly support the project's long-term objectives.

The *NEB Concepts* series features structured conversations with key figures within the wider New European Bauhaus community, including architects, educators, project leaders, and members of the DigiNEB External Advisory Board. These discussions are divided into 59 episodes, each exploring topics at the intersection of sustainability, innovation, and human-centred design, reflecting the multidisciplinary nature of the NEB initiative.

***NEB Concepts* is designed to provide insights into the evolving discourse surrounding the New European Bauhaus and, in particular, the intersection of digital technologies and tools with the NEB ecosystem.** Each episode offers a focused exploration of themes such as climate adaptation, digitalisation, interdisciplinary collaboration, and community engagement. The modular nature of the series allows listeners to engage with content in a manner that suits their interests, whether by exploring individual topics in depth or following the perspectives of specific interviewees. This initiative contributes to the broader goals of DigiNEB by offering an additional medium for disseminating knowledge and fostering dialogue among stakeholders.

NEB Concepts

NEB Concepts is a podcast that features insightful **conversations with leading architects, educators, and project leaders.**

The discussions deal with topics at the **intersection of sustainability, innovation, and human-centred design.** You'll hear directly from those shaping the future of urban development, cultural heritage, and community empowerment.

Explore the guests and collection of ideas and practices, projects and reflections discussed [here](#).

The *NEB Concepts* podcast was promoted to the NEB Community through the official New European Bauhaus Community email newsletter published by the European Commission.

The episodes also serve as a resource for various educational and professional development contexts, supporting the continuous learning objectives of the NEB initiative.

Key Participants:

The *NEB Concepts* series includes contributions from several prominent figures within the NEB ecosystem, including:

- Aase Højlund Nielsen
- Andreja Kutnar
- Davor Meersman
- Francesca Rizzo
- Frank van der Hoeven
- Jan Bunge
- Markus Reymann
- Matti Kuittinen
- Mia Roth Cerina
- Roberto Cavallo
- Selma Harrington
- Sheela Patel

These individuals are leaders of NEB Lighthouse projects, members of the NEB High-Level Round Table, and distinguished members of the DigiNEB External Advisory Board. Their participation in the podcast series ensures that the content reflects a diverse range of perspectives and expertise.

The *NEB Concepts* series complements other stakeholder engagement activities within the DigiNEB project. By providing a platform for in-depth discussions on critical topics, the series supports the project’s objective of facilitating interdisciplinary knowledge exchange and fostering a shared understanding of NEB principles. **The series is positioned as an educational tool to be integrated into the NEB Academy**, academic curricula, workshops, and professional training programs, thereby extending its impact beyond the immediate project consortium and existing stakeholder community.

4.6. Videography

In addition to the podcast, as part of the strategic update for stakeholder engagement after the amendment, persistent media in the form of longer videos has been a significant focus of the project. The enhanced approach reflects a significant shift in response to the challenges of maintaining consistent engagement through conventional social media platforms.

Rather than posting fleeting social media content, particular effort has been made to create videos that can not only be watched as they are posted, but remain in a form that can be consulted, shared, used as part of educational materials for the NEB Academy and in other contexts, and go on to have a life beyond the limits of the project. In particular, in addition to promotional highlights videos, full presentation content from knowledge exchange events such as the **JUST Industry Data Week** ([Link to Video Playlist](#)) and **NEB@CERN** ([Link to Video Playlist](#)) have been recorded and made available on YouTube.

By delivering richer, more substantive content, this method offers a more reliable and lasting form of engagement. It addresses the transient nature of traditional social media, ensuring that the NEB community and stakeholders benefit from meaningful learning opportunities aligned with the project’s overarching goals

98 videos, most of which contain long-form content, including expert presentations, interviews and panel discussions have been uploaded and shared. These have been supported by LinkedIn and the project partners’ other social media posts, and have also been disseminated through the networks of the many individuals who contributed to these knowledge events.

4.7. Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook

Authored by Jan Åman and Adam Davies for the Industry Commons Foundation, the “Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook” built on the New European Bauhaus success stories that were featured at the NEB Festival (the Duved Project was presented in a session with Commissioner Ferreira) and NEB initiatives supported by National Governments (The “Norrlands Model” and “Visions in the North”).

The prototype introduces a reimagined framework based on Walter Gropius’ 1922 Bauhaus circle diagram, adapted for modern societal challenges. It positions the local as the focal point of future development, advocating for decentralised, ecosystemic approaches that emphasise collaboration across diverse fields. The handbook suggests a holistic, inclusive model where co-creation, sustainability, and participatory processes drive innovation. It highlights the need for interconnected systems addressing climate change, democracy, and local resilience through shared knowledge, regenerative practices, and cross-disciplinary dialogue.

Excerpt from Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook showing the original and updated circles

This updated approach aims to foster local ecosystems that integrate specialised knowledge into broader contexts, ensuring that local communities take active roles in societal development. By utilising tools like the circular economy and zero-waste principles, this ecosystemic model seeks to generate synergies that support sustainable growth, resilience, and innovation across sectors such as food systems, housing, and public spaces. The handbook ultimately offers a flexible blueprint for community-driven societal transformation tailored to the specific challenges and opportunities of each unique context.

The “**Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook**” was launched at a public event at the Faculty of Architecture at Umeå University on 9th February 2024 entitled “**The Local is the Future**”. The event was introduced by Cornelia Redeker, Head Of Architecture at the University of Umeå. The panel included Helene Hellmark-Knutsson, Governor of Västerbotten County and former Swedish Minister of Education; Jan Åman, author of the Norrlands Model and Prototype of an Ecosystemic Handbook (partner ICF); Michela Magas, Member of the NEB High Level Round Table (partner ICF); Sara Thor, Lecturer in Architecture at Umeå School of Architecture; Adam Davies, Co-Founder of sustainable design agency Tÿ Syml and co-author of the “Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook”; and Magnus Myrenberg, Partner at Aalto Capital.

4.8. Regional Innovation Model (RIM) Handbook

The updated plan placed a strong emphasis on the transfer of methodologies for collaborative learning and innovation, particularly to EU regions. This strategy is encapsulated in the published *RIM Handbook*, a resource designed to engage regional authorities and community leaders in applying NEB principles to their local contexts.

The **RIM Handbook** empowers local and regional policymakers, civic leaders, and innovators to address grand societal challenges through an ecosystemic approach. It is the result of work developed in the past two years to stimulate a multiplier effect for local and regional sustainability innovation activities.

Building on the Åman and Davies handbook prototype, the early work with EU policy makers supporting the joining of regional funding instruments, and incorporating co-creation methodologies from across NEB initiatives and best practices from other projects, the handbook provides practical guidance on co-creation, participatory design, and regional innovation, helping to bridge the gap between established NEB hubs and emerging regions. The *RIM Handbook* is a practical guide for local and regional policymakers, civic leaders, and community stakeholders. The handbook is designed to facilitate the application of New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles within specific regional contexts, using collaborative learning and co-creation methodologies developed through the DigiNEB.eu project, and critically, provides a model to build upon and scale ideas from the periphery to the centre.

The DigiNEB Regional Innovation Model (RIM) Handbook builds on the work of its predecessor and incorporates co-creation methodologies from across the wider NEB community. Launched at the DigiNEB final event in Brussels with Committee of the Regions member Kieran McCarthy, the book transfers successful co-creation methodologies from established NEB projects, providing inspiration and examples for other regions, supporting broader and more inclusive engagement across Europe. By focusing on the transfer of successful methodologies,

DigiNEB – Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative has received funding from the European Union’s Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) under Grant Agreement no. 101083743.

the handbook supports DigiNEB’s goal of expanding the reach and impact of NEB principles and digital strategies across Europe.

The Handbook outlines and responds to the primary framework conditions of our age: the urgent need for cross-domain collaboration and knowledge exchange, the requirement to leverage all expertise and intelligence, focusing on ground-up community engagement, and the emergence of an entirely data-driven society. These new realities provide the foundation for the creation of solutions that harness regional strengths and adapt best practices to local needs that can then be rolled out across Europe, from the periphery to the centre.

The authors and editors of the book gathered thought leaders from the DigiNEB and wider NEB communities and collated best practices from successful NEB initiatives as well as studies and publications by the Joint Research Centre (JRC), the European Committee of the Regions (CoR), all of the NEB lighthouses, as well as related initiatives, agencies and organisations. It highlights key tools such as the NEB Compass as well as dozens of applicable and adaptable case studies, tools, methodologies, knowledge and results from successful NEB projects and labs. Inspired by documented practice, papers, publications and results from the NEB activities, the handbook emphasises the role of local and regional policymakers as change enablers - leaders capable of galvanising diverse communities and leveraging digital technologies to create innovative, context-specific solutions.

As facilitators, mentors, and collaborators, public administrators are encouraged to gather diverse and interdisciplinary communities to co-create and scale innovative, context-specific solutions, prototypes, and inventions using the best practice methodologies presented and leveraging a concatenation of funding instruments at different levels across the local, national and European levels.

The RIM Handbook provides a companion and reference for entrepreneurial public administrators to galvanise their communities to address locally the global challenges of our time. The tested and

validated tools and methodologies presented are grounded in practice and are designed to be adapted, scaled, and replicated across regions.

The Regional Innovation Mode explains an approach that concatenates funding instruments at different scales, while bringing together businesses, academic institutions, local governments, community members, and more-than-human natural ecosystems to address grand challenges and inspire commitment, vision and local action. In addition to the ‘on the ground’ case studies and tools provided by the partnering NEB initiatives, the handbook contextualises NEB within the fully data-driven society with a focus on Digital Life and an exploration of the critical importance of JUST Data principles.

The RIM Handbook amplifies existing research, results, methodologies, use cases and outputs piloted and validated by NEB initiatives and Lighthouse projects. These tools and actions enable co-creation and community participatory design in response to globally significant and locally felt grand challenges. It leverages not only potential funding avenues as a scaling mechanism but also digital technologies and JUST data practices to support the creation of AI for social good, as well as evidence-based approaches to crafting policies responsive to local needs, global trends, legal frameworks and the evolving technological environment.

At the project’s final event in Brussels, where the book was officially launched (see section 5 below), Kieran McCarthy, Cork City Councillor and member of the Committee of the Regions, praised the book and expressed a desire to reprint it for a significant launch at a major CoR summit in April 2025, to ensure it finds its way into the hands of regional and city policymakers all across Europe.

The RIM Handbook is attached to this deliverable as an Annexe and can also be found on Zenodo at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14494301>

4.9. Engaging Communities in Policymaking

Strategic development of the engagement plan involved collaborating directly with the NEB Community of experts in policymaking through collaborative authorship. By encouraging stakeholders to contribute to joint White Papers, policy recommendations, and other publications, DigiNEB aims to empower community members to influence policy development at regional, national, and EU levels.

A key milestone in this process was the engagement by DigiNEB of the NEB community around the NEB Mission by engaging Member States to support the NEB Mission at the Council of Europe on

the 12th of September 2023. This activity was crucial as it led to the establishment of the NEB Facility, the key cross-cutting funding vehicle for the future of the NEB.

DigiNEB EAB members organised policy meetings, such as a workshop held in Zagreb by the Croatian Society of Architects.

The DigiNEB Regional Innovation Model (RIM) Handbook directly engages policymakers and regional administrators in co-creation methodologies to apply best practices from the New European Bauhaus ecosystem to engage local communities in fostering improved living environments through digital and social technologies and innovations.

DigiNEB engaged leaders of NEB Labs and NEB Lighthouses in regular meetings to co-author a White Paper intended to guide the NEB Mission's future direction and evolution towards the NEB Facility. The community agreed at the NEB@CERN event to co-author a white paper to guide the NEB towards future funding. This continued at dedicated workshops and meetings organised by the members of the DigiNEB External Advisory Board, NEB Lab, and NEB Lighthouse thought leaders.

The White Paper, written by thought leaders from across the NEB community, presents a comprehensive vision for the future of NEB. It serves as a foundational document that will continue to drive policy discussions and shape the future of NEB-related initiatives.

The White Paper highlights the wide-ranging perspectives of DigiNEB thought leaders and also emphasises the practical steps needed to build a sustainable and inclusive digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus. One of the key themes across several contributions is the integration of **co-creation methodologies** that foster collaboration between regional authorities, communities, and digital innovators. The White Paper also underlines the importance of **data ethics and governance**, advocating for transparency in digital innovation to ensure that NEB principles—sustainability, inclusiveness, and aesthetics—are reflected in both technological development and policy frameworks. Additionally, there is a strong focus on leveraging existing NEB Lighthouse projects as scalable models for other regions, ensuring that the NEB digital ecosystem can be tailored to different local contexts while maintaining core European values. The paper stresses the need for interdisciplinary collaboration, calling for enhanced dialogue between the public, private, and research sectors to create an ecosystem that is not only innovative but also aligned with the mission of the New European Bauhaus.

Excerpt from the White Paper

Editor's Note

This White Paper is written in response to the European Commission working paper 'First Reflections on Building Blocks for the Design of a Possible EU Mission on the New European Bauhaus'. The contributing authors are thought leaders from the DigiNEB community – the digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus. They include members of the DigiNEB External Advisory Board and leaders of NEB Lighthouse projects. Representatives of this community first came together during the DigiNEB event NEB@CERN 27 February – 1 March 2023 and, in a series of workshops, started to develop a comprehensive vision for the development of the New European Bauhaus digital ecosystem. A productive meeting about the NEB Mission was organised by DigiNEB with representatives from the NEB unit at the JRC in Zagreb on the 20th and 21st of September, 2023. This

White Paper starts by referring to the original vision by President von der Leyen and the Concept Paper by the NEB High Level Round Table (HLRT) and proceeds to the contributions of the listed authors.

We adopted a pluralistic approach to capturing the voices of the community, representing sometimes differing views, and most importantly, not cancelling each other out. Each EAB member or lighthouse leader who was asked to contribute was tasked with creating a 1-2 pager on their positioning with respect to the NEB Mission. Each positioning was added as a separate chapter. Contributors could work together or amplify each other's vision by agreement with the authors. Aside from small edits, contributions are left intact, demonstrating a multiplicity of views and diversity of approaches. All are valid and seldom contradictory. We have, at times, suggested more effective wording to convey the message, but we have allowed for a democratic representation of all the core voices from the community.

<p>digiNEB White Paper on the future of NEB in Horizon Programmes</p> <p>Editor Michela Magas</p> <p>Authors Amanda Brandellero Annette Hafner Selma Harrington Aase Højlund Nielsen Michela Magas Orla Murphy Kirsi Mustalahti Nuno Nunes Sheela Patel Ignasi Perez Arnal Mia Roth-Cerina Annmie Wickmans</p>	<p>Editor's note</p> <p>This White Paper is written in response to the European Commission working paper 'First Reflections on Building Blocks for the Design of a Possible EU Mission on the New European Bauhaus'. The contributing authors are thought leaders from the digiNEB community – the digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus. They include members of the digiNEB External Advisory Board and leaders of NEB Lighthouse projects. Representatives of this community first came together during the digiNEB event NEB@CERN 27 February – 1 March 2023 and, in a series of workshops, started to develop a comprehensive vision for the development of the New European Bauhaus digital ecosystem. A productive meeting about the NEB Mission was organised by digiNEB with representatives from the NEB unit at the JRC in Zagreb on the 20th and 21st of September, 2023. This White Paper starts by referring to the original vision by President von der Leyen and the Concept Paper by the NEB High Level Round Table (HLRT) and proceeds to the contributions of the listed authors.</p> <p>We adopted a pluralistic approach to capturing the voices of the community, representing sometimes differing views, and most importantly, not cancelling each other out. Each EAB member or lighthouse leader who was asked to contribute was tasked with creating a 1-2 pager on their positioning in respect of the NEB Mission. Each positioning was added as a separate chapter. Contributors could work together or amplify each other's vision, by agreement with the authors. Aside from small edits, contributions are left intact demonstrating a multiplicity of views and diversity of approaches. All are valid, and seldom contradictory. We have at times suggested more effective wording to convey the message, but we have allowed for a democratic representation of all the core voices from the community.</p> <p>Framing the NEB vision</p> <p>When President von der Leyen launched the New European Bauhaus in her inaugural State of the Union speech on the 16th of September 2020, it was the first time that she called for a "co-creation space where architects, artists, students, engineers, designers work together". This call to create a multidisciplinary movement for co-creation is significant because, for the first time, she called for translation of thought into practice through the prototyping of tangible solutions that could turn into evidence-based policy.</p> <p>A group of practitioners were invited as the President's High Level Round Table to translate their practice into a Concept for the New European Bauhaus. The first HLRT activity identified a strong "line of justice" that cut through all foundational values. Mapping desired outcomes was united by a strong concept of "learning by doing". Social justice and</p> <p>1</p>
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In addition to the White Paper, a repository was created using Notion as a community resource as an outcome of the CERN event. This platform has enabled ongoing collaboration, with the community continuing to interact regularly, hosted by sister projects such as CrAft and the NEB Academy. This approach aligns with the NEB's commitment to participatory innovation and builds on the NEB method by combining scientific rigour with grassroots-driven insights. Community-driven policy input is gathered through events, the website, and social media channels, ensuring broad and diverse participation in shaping the future of NEB-related policies.

The DigiNEB White Paper is attached to deliverable d4.2 as an Annexe and can also be found on Zenodo at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14497677>

4.10. Educational Strategy

One of DigiNEB's objectives is capacity-building across the European Union. Using the networks of the EAAE, the project engaged educational channels to promote innovation and collaboration within the New European Bauhaus (NEB) community. During the activities and engagements, significant progress was made in aligning educational efforts with the needs of the NEB community. The educational strategy emanates from work package 3 and its tasks: Training programme, Transferring innovation best practices and Early Adopters network. These tasks support each other to create a digital and physical ecosystem of exchange. **DigiNEB relied on activities and events where the project connected with the NEB Community and Stakeholders to create collaborative spaces to learn from each other's experiences and practices. A comprehensive list of these activities can be found in deliverable 3.3.**

A combination of webinars, Digital Working Groups, and workshops in collaboration with the partners' networks ensured that DigiNEB could collect and spread innovation best practices while engaging with the NEB Community and other networks. Furthermore, DigiNEB developed a training programme that showcases existing learning resources that are aligned with the NEB.

Training Programme and NEB Academy

The first pillar of the education strategy is the training programme: a compilation of learning resources supporting the upskilling of the NEB Community related to the NEB Values. We monitored the existing learning resources and finally made an inventory showing the gaps and overlaps. Parallel to the project, the NEB Academy initiative was launched to strengthen the relevance of this task. The DigiNEB project supported the NEB Academy through its ideation through workshops at the CERN IdeaSquare Event. Later, partners actively participated in the NEB Academy launch in Slovenia, leveraging and sharpening our educational strategy. Furthermore, TU Delft oversaw the initiation of the NEB Academy digital platform demo, engaging various NEB partners in its co-creation and testing, including Nordic Bauhaus members. DigiNEB will have a strong impact on the future of the NEB Academy.

Workshops and webinars

Workshops are physical or online events to facilitate discussions and co-creation between Smart Communities and the New European Bauhaus stakeholders. The DigiNEB team exceeded its intended delivery of six hands-on co-creation workshops as part of the CERN event. The format delivered was based on best practices from NEB co-creation processes and has been shown to produce greater value for the community.

The DigiNEB project initially planned to primarily deliver webinars. However, as the project progressed, numerous webinars and in-person workshops were delivered, fostering collaboration and engagement with stakeholders across various fields.

A full list of over 40 workshops, seminars, community events, keynotes and other engagements is listed in D3.3. These include sessions on 'How can timber construction and digitalisation boost the New European Bauhaus?', 'How can we register ideas in the Creative Industries?' and keynote speeches at the launch of the Swedish Presidency of the Council of the EU.

DigiNEB has facilitated clustering and convergence on common themes and challenges, fostered the exchange of good practices, and identified how digital transformation can contribute to implementing digital solutions for the New European Bauhaus community projects. The workshops have been recorded, and the knowledge gathered is distributed through dissemination.

Part of the strategy for greater community engagement is the leveraging of larger-scale events and notable project partnerships to attract participation. The multi-day dedicated physical workshop,

which was organised in partnership with CERN and hosted at CERN IdeaSquare, gathered over 50 DigiNEB community stakeholders. The Wood4Bauhaus event gathered more than 200 stakeholders from the wood sector. The JUST Industry Data Week involved hands-on participation by over 100 stakeholders from across industrial domains including health, space, automotive and primary industries.

4.11. DigiNEB Early Adopters

DigiNEB leverages the interest and engagement of Early Adopters of the DigiNEB platform for further outreach. The DigiNEB Early Adopters are champions who use digital solutions and act as ambassadors or enthusiastic mediators between the creators of the tools and their own wider communities. Such champions help community-building processes by facilitating community interaction and onboarding broader communities.

The strategy for onboarding Early Adopters has been to focus on NEB thought leaders. This has proven successful already in the early stages of the project. All have continued to be active contributors to the direction, content and organisation of in-person workshops and meetings. A selection of thought leaders have contributed to the *NEB Concepts* podcast series. This content is also made available (under granted & referenced permission), promoted and highlighted on the DigiNEB platform as a reference for the DigiNEB community.

4.12. External Advisory Board

The DigiNEB EAB has been notably very active and has offered expert guidance, as well as hands-on contributions and organisation of events and activities. The EAB covers accessibility, architecture, design and construction materials. It comprises 16 renowned and esteemed EAB members (eight women and eight men) who have agreed to bring their expertise to the DigiNEB community.

The EAB has connected DigiNEB with proactive, eminent stakeholders with thought leadership and influence. It provided competent and independent guidance to the project while at the same time supporting both the working groups and the NEB evolution through roadmap recommendations. Members of the EAB have been notably active and many have hosted events or provided crucial text for the project's recommendations. Their capacity was to support content and outputs (i.e., roadmap, policy briefs, Digital Focus Group reports) and impact policy, industry and research.

Below is a complete list of the External Advisory Board members, led by **Michela Magas** (Chair), from DigiNEB partner Industry Commons Foundation:

- **Christina Claesson-Jonsson**, Director of Research and Development at NCC AB, construction industry
- **Annette Hafner**, Professor at Ruhr-Universität Bochum
- **Selma Harrington**, Executive Board Member at The Architects' Council of Europe (ACE)
- **Dimitris Kiritsis**, Professor of ICT and Sustainable Manufacturing at EPFL (École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne)
- **Matti Kuittinen**, Professor at Aalto University and former Senior Ministerial Advisor at the Ministry of the Environment of Finland
- **Andreja Kutnar**, Director at InnoRenew CoE
- **Martin Luce**, Director at TUM School of Engineering and Design
- **Tom Minderhoud**, Sensor Architect at UNStudio
- **Kirsi Mustalahti**, Founder & Chairwoman at ACCAC Global

- **Fredrik Nilsson**, Professor, Vice President of Campus and Sustainable Development at Chalmers University of Technology
- **Alan Organschi**, Director at Bauhaus Earth
- **Sheela Patel**, Grassroots Global Activist at International Institute for Environment and Development
- **Ignasi Pérez Arnal**, Director at REBUILD Congress
- **Francesca Rizzo**, Full Professor at Politecnico di Milano
- **Mia Roth-Čerina**, Vice-Dean for International Relations and Art at the University of Zagreb
- **Ruth Schagemann**, President of the Architects' Council of Europe (ACE-CAE)
- **Jose Pedro Sousa**, Associate Professor at the University of Porto and Member of the NEB HLRT.

As shown in the list above, each individual has been selected from diverse organisations and research institutions to cater for a broad domain range and balanced geographical distribution. Experts were chosen for their experience and roles as advisors or experts in sectoral innovation, market needs, government policies and societal impact. They reflect the different NEB stakeholders and include experts in architecture, accessibility, construction, design, engineering, and national and regional policy. EAB members have affiliations with prestigious institutions, and have been selected to ensure a comprehensive representation of the Stakeholder Groups and create fundamental synergistic relationships with external institutions and organisations to facilitate the learning & transfer process.

DigiNEB External Advisory Board comprises multidisciplinary experts from Sweden, Germany, Switzerland, Finland, Slovenia, Croatia, Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Portugal and India.

4.13. Communication with the NEB community

The DigiNEB team has established a good working relationship and continuous dialogue with the NEB communication team at the JRC to ensure that the DigiNEB communication strategy is aligned with that of the New European Bauhaus. The DigiNEB and NEB teams communicate via emails or video calls and present the main topics to be carried out in the next month, summarised in a collaborative online document. The cooperation between DigiNEB and the NEB team helps each other multiply the impacts of their work and reach a wider audience.

NEB partners came together at the final DigiNEB event ‘Celebrating the Lessons Learnt’ together with representatives from the JRC and the European Committee of the Regions (see section 5 below). The event was a collaboration of DigiNEB with CrAft, NEBULA, NEB Lighthouses and NEB Labs.

More information on the communication flow between DigiNEB and NEB is described in the deliverable *D5.1 Plan for dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities (DECP)* in month 6.

5. DigiNEB Final Event: Celebrating the Lessons Learnt

The two-day final event ‘Celebrating the Lessons Learnt’ gathered 70 NEB thought leaders at Architecture House in Brussels over the 17th and 18th December 2024. The structure and content of the event were designed to reflect the successful implementation of the community engagement and adoption strategy, and focus particularly on the impacts of this implementation. **The final event yielded a high level of engagement, discovery of particularly valuable roles and functions for the NEB community in both innovation and policy making, and established concrete future plans, strategies and directions.**

All sessions were captured in audio format for transcription and summarisation, as well as photography and videography for dissemination. While it represented the final event for the DigiNEB project, it was also the first in a relay of engagement events that created a long-term legacy for DigiNEB in partnership with the CrAft and NEBula projects, and further NEB initiatives, including those funded by the ERDF and EIT Community.

NEB | CELEBRATING THE LESSONS LEARNT

**A collaboration of DigiNEB with CrAft, NEBULA,
NEB Lighthouses and NEB Labs**

**17-18 December 2024, Brussels
Architects House**

We are wrapping up the first generation of NEB projects, and after the first 3 years we'd like to take stock of what has been achieved. What did we learn? How did the context around us change? And how do we bring all of this now into an even bigger, better, more mature, more structured New European Bauhaus: a more impactful New European Bauhaus for the next generation.

The December and March events are the first in a series of engagement activities, both online and on site, that we hope will contribute to shaping not just the NEB of the future, but also the Europe of the future.

17 December 2024 | ACHIEVEMENTS

09:00	<p>Welcome addresses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Frank Van Der Hoeven, TU Delft, digiNEB project coordinator - Annemie Wyckmans, NTNU, CrAFt project coordinator - Jacques Timmerman, Belgian Society of AH, Chair of the ACE New European Bauhaus Work Group - Solene Gautron, Joint Research Center, policy officer at New European Bauhaus Coordination Unit
09:20	<p>digiNEB: fostering digital solutions and synergies that boost the New European Bauhaus (NEB) movement Frank Van der Hoeven</p>
09:40	<p>digiNEB results Galvanising the NEB community</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The New European Bauhaus Academy: Up- and re-skilling the sector workforce with innovative trainings Oliver Jancke, InnovaWood - NEB Concepts: Podcast education modules featuring NEB experts on Sustainability, Innovation, and Human-Centred Design in Urban Development Andrew Dubber, Industry Commons Foundation.
10:15	<p>Break</p>
10:45	<p>Implementing the NEB in R&D: Challenges faced by EU projects Clémentine Coujard, NEBULA, Dowel.</p> <p>Think & Do Tank 1 – What have we learned from “learning by doing”? Moderated by: Mia Roth and José Pedro Participation: ALL The power of NEB for effective knowledge transfer and learning</p>
12:30	<p>Lunch</p>
13:15	<p>digiNEB results NEB and the Regions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opening Statement by Kieran McCarthy, Cork City Councillor and Member, EU Committee of the Regions - Statement by Orla Murphy, member of the NEB HLRT <p>The Regional Innovation Model Handbook showcasing best practices from NEB projects Moderator: Andrew Dubber, Industry Commons Foundation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Kieran McCarthy, Cork City Councillor and Member, EU Committee of the Regions - Eszter Davida, member of the NEB HLRT - Jan Áman, Author of the Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook - Michela Magas, member of the NEB HLRT <p>Statement by Shigeru Ban, member of the NEB HLRT Statement by Sheela Patel, member of the NEB HLRT Statement by Hubert Trammer, member of the NEB HLRT</p>
14:15	<p>Break</p>
14:30	<p>Think & Do Tank 2 – What have we learnt from EU neighbourhoods? Moderated by: Aase Højlund Nielsen and Annemie Wyckmans with all lighthouses and labs Participation: ALL</p>
16:00	<p>End or networking break</p>

5.1. Introductions

The final event began with introductions by Frank Van der Hoeven (DigiNEB), Annemie Wyckmans (CrAFt), Jacques Timmerman (ACE NEB Work Group), and Solène Gautron (NEB Coordination Unit at the JRC). The welcome speeches emphasised the achievements of the first generation of NEB projects while reflecting on challenges and opportunities for the future.

DigiNEB coordinator **Frank van der Hoeven** highlighted how the NEB initiative has embraced design as a crucial element in creating more inclusive, sustainable, and beautiful built environments. He acknowledged the challenges of integrating new partners unfamiliar with European programming and stressed the importance of adhering to the structured commitments of NEB projects. **van der Hoeven expressed optimism about continuing efforts, such as through the NEB Academy and Alliance, to sustain and expand the initiative's impact.**

CrAft coordinator **Annemie Wyckmans** reflected on the longstanding alignment of NEB principles with existing practices, pointing out how the programme has allowed these approaches to be brought to the forefront. She noted the richness of NEB’s impacts, including its ability to bring people together, foster joy, and connect culture and mobility. She also cautioned that the initiative must better document and translate its qualitative impacts into terms understandable to investors and policymakers. **Wyckmans advocated for a united effort to amplify NEB’s effects and ensure continued support beyond individual projects.**

Jacques Timmerman of the Architects' Council of Europe (ACE) and Chair of the New European Bauhaus WG described NEB as an inspiring framework for envisioning urban futures and achieving sustainability goals such as carbon neutrality by 2050. He emphasised the need to embed NEB values in key policies, including public procurement and the revised European Performance of Buildings Directive, to ensure systemic change. **Timmerman advocated for innovative business models and cross-sector collaboration to regenerate urban areas and make NEB principles actionable at all levels.**

Solène Gautron, NEB Policy Officer at the Joint Research Centre, commended the exceptional collaboration among NEB projects, particularly their success in fostering shared knowledge and trust. She introduced the NEB Facility, a new funding instrument designed to support future initiatives and sustain the relationships and knowledge generated by the first generation of projects. **Gautron underlined the economic and social value of NEB’s long-term investments in well-being and happiness and expressed enthusiasm for learning from the event’s workshops and discussions.**

5.2. Fostering Digital Solutions and Synergies that Boost the NEB movement

Frank van der Hoeven reflected on the evolution of European initiatives from energy-efficient building programmes to the New European Bauhaus. Drawing from his academic experience at TU Delft, he underscored the importance of fostering a cultural shift in research and design, especially through open science and collaboration. He critiqued earlier European programming for its narrow focus on materials and installations, neglecting the broader potential of architectural design and urban planning to optimise sustainability, and praised NEB for addressing this gap by merging technology and artistic perspectives in a unified approach.

He emphasised the role of digital tools in transforming design processes, showcasing examples such as open-source plugins for architectural software, which empower small architectural practices to adopt parametric design. He compared this with the closed, inaccessible nature of AI-driven tools and lack of long-term maintenance of the results from large-scale European projects, which cannot be accessed by broader communities. He quoted an example from a project about Building Information Modelling (BIM) for energy-efficient buildings, which had received €7 million in EU funding. He pointed out that the project's website became non-functional shortly after the project concluded, with key functionalities such as accessibility and registration being disabled. This, he argued, represented a missed opportunity for wider dissemination and continued use of the knowledge and tools developed through the project. The point was to showcase the problem of

large, well-funded initiatives failing to create lasting, open resources for the broader community. Instead of fostering ongoing benefits, the project's outcomes were effectively "fenced off," limiting their impact to a small, closed group of beneficiaries, undermining the goal of ensuring that publicly funded projects contribute to accessible and sustainable solutions. He particularly focused on the importance of community-driven approaches in design and digital solutions, highlighting that community-focused initiatives often use open-source tools, allowing greater accessibility and participation. These tools enable local democracy and active citizen involvement, fostering collaboration at the grassroots level.

Recommendation: prioritise open, community-oriented digital tools in future agendas, ensuring that design processes are inclusive and accessible to broader audiences. Empowering communities through open design and participatory tools is essential for achieving the social and environmental goals of the New European Bauhaus. The approach not only strengthens local engagement but also supports the transfer of knowledge and skills across diverse groups. He proposed a roadmap to prioritise open, community-driven digital tools and highlighted initiatives like the NEB Academy, which focuses on lifelong learning to keep pace with rapid technological advancements.

5.3. DigiNEB results: Galvanising the NEB community

InnovaWood Business Manager Oliver Jancke introduced the NEB Academy, a project that has been facilitated by the DigiNEB partners to reskill and upskill the construction ecosystem to align with NEB principles. As an engineer specialising in wood science and technology, he emphasised the Academy's role in fostering bio-based construction and urban transformation. Oliver detailed the Academy's structure as a decentralised network of regional and topical hubs across Europe, with training tailored to local needs. The Academy targets diverse groups, including construction professionals, policymakers, local communities, and civil society, aiming to provide accessible, high-quality, certified training through digital platforms and in-person sessions.

He highlighted the Academy's ambitions to establish a robust training ecosystem over the next two years, develop transferable training formats within five years, influence EU skills policies and ensure long-term integration of NEB values into the construction sector. He also stressed the importance of involving a younger generation to bring fresh perspectives and maintain momentum within the NEB ecosystem. The Academy plans to launch an open call for new hubs and courses, ensuring continuous growth and adaptability while maintaining quality standards. **The Academy's mission is to connect communities and professionals through open collaboration, ensuring NEB principles are deeply embedded in construction practices across Europe.**

Andrew Dubber of Industry Commons Foundation presented the **NEB Concepts Podcast**, a series created as part of the DigiNEB project to foster wider understanding and engagement with the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles. He emphasised that the podcast serves as an educational resource for the NEB Academy and beyond, showcasing diverse perspectives from architects, designers, scientists, and other experts, while being accessible to a broad audience.

Dubber outlined the unique modular format of the podcast, which allows listeners to explore complete individual interviews with each expert - or topic-specific discussions, tagged by themes such as interdisciplinarity, local solutions, and sustainability. The series includes **12 interviews divided into 59 episodes**, offering flexible and focused insights for various educational and professional contexts. The podcast's mission is to capture expertise and galvanise the NEB community by documenting conversations and insights from its members. It is designed to be used within the NEB Academy and other training environments to inspire and inform learners. It also seeks to reflect a wide range of approaches to addressing NEB principles, fostering a richer dialogue on the challenges and opportunities in sustainable design.

To give examples of this diversity of perspectives, Dubber shared notable ideas from the podcast's contributors, touching on topics such as the potential of digital tools like digital twins to enhance participatory urban planning, the importance of reconnecting design practices with local contexts and traditions, and one interviewee's call to view the built environment not just through a carbon-neutral lens but as an opportunity to define a distinctive European cultural expression.

- “Typically, an architect or an urban planner goes to a site once or twice, spends an hour there and returns to the office to do the work. I tend to believe that someone who lives for 10 years in a neighbourhood is pretty much an expert in that area. That person may not be skilled in urban planning or architectural design or is not a great designer for public space. But at the same time, things are changing due to AI, where the skill of visualising spatial ideas was once a specific quality that architects or urban designers possessed. Now, it is

much easier for non-experts to generate images of what they would like to see in their environment, and I think that in the coming years, we will see a much richer dialogue between the two.” - **Frank van der Hoeven**

- “What is the New European Bauhaus? To me, first and foremost, it's a golden opportunity for the design sector, architects and designers, artists, planners and so forth to get actively involved in the solving of these planetary environmental crises starting from the European context. So far, these problems have been mostly addressed through eco-technical or eco-social means. It's about the time that the latent potential of arts, design and architecture and culture are brought into the toolbox - not only of policymakers our city planners and regional decision-makers, but also everybody involved in the value chain of the built environment.” - **Matti Kuittinen**
- “If we talk about public space, what do we mean by “the public”? All of these notions become expanded: what it means to act within the earth, what it means to act towards the air and disrupting migratory routes, and establishing opportunities for other species to coexist with humans and so on. So this is really putting it very simply, but it implies a new direction in design - and in the basic question that comes with design: who is the user? Who are you designing for? And this notion of interconnectedness is something that is being brought into the discourse more and more, though probably not at the pace that is necessary.” - **Mia Roth-Cerina**
- “Digital twins are data-driven tools, but the way you can visualise it impacts the possibility for the people to understand, especially those who are not experts. This is one of the important powers that digital twins can give policymakers at the local level - to use these kinds of tools to really visualise important changes.” - **Francesca Rizzo**
- “One of the aspects that really interested me is in which way these digital tools and solutions are operating. I would talk in terms of the accessibility and affordability of these tools - and solutions for whom? What are the things that are out there that are freely accessible for people, whether they are professionals or just people who are there to learn? How can they get access to that? I think this is a more important issue than interoperability, because interoperability is a step further. First is to provide proper access and affordability for these tools.” - **Roberto Cavallo**
- “In our training as architects, too often we are trained to think “new”. You have some information through the history of architecture, but even at the level of building regulations, as they have been developed for a very long period of time, they were looking at only building new. So that means new materials, new structures, including infrastructure, roads, etc. So the knowledge kind of stayed parked on historic materials, methods of building, and so on. The New European Bauhaus and its sustainability component is calling on us, I believe, or giving us an opportunity, to link the two.” - **Selma Harrington**
- “We can now build cities on top of a game engine with an immersive environment that allows you to draft based on real-world data. And anybody can do it. Look at Barcelona, for example, where they created extremely valuable neighbourhood changes for healthier outcomes just by involving women and children in the urban design process. They're just better because they took into consideration many more perspectives. And it's a digital superpower we have.” - **Davor Meersman**
- “I believe policy needs to give us the models society can learn from. And oftentimes there are public buildings that are being constructed that people can experience. I think that the policymakers should be aware that these acts of requesting a certain specific material in the buildings they're constructing can have an enormous impact on society because if you've never been in a wooden building, obviously you will not decide to build one, because you have no clue.” - **Andreja Kutnar**

- “I think we’ve missed focusing on understanding the places where we work. In a sense, we have become so globalised that we think there's one size fits all, even though I don't think people necessarily believe in it. The specifics, or the essence of a place that makes a place special, is also an opening towards acknowledging that other places are also special. You need this outside perspective to understand yourself. That goes for both organisations and human beings. And if you're not open to this, you get stuck in your own closed world, and then the prototypes, or whatever you develop, lose their relevance in a broader context.” - **Aase Højlund Nielsen**
- “I think it's important to remember that 50 to 100 years ago, most banks were family businesses and and inherently, their mission was to create intergenerational wealth. When they invested in the railway in the US, they didn't think they were going to make a lot of money in the next quarter. But they really knew that they're going to make a lot of money in the next 100 years. And it’s these kinds of transformations that we need now.” - **Jan Bunge**
- “There are so many things that are banned in Europe you can't produce. You know, perfumes are a very dirty business. So all the perfume bases are made outside. All the dirty stuff: paints, perfumes, all this chemical stuff which can leach into the ground and is dangerous - it’s banned in Europe. What does that mean for the rest of the world? Because you need paint and you need perfume and all the other stuff that you require. It's produced in the Global South.” - **Sheela Patel**
- “We'd like to think of ourselves as individuals, but then, on the one hand, we are so completely neglecting that our life is augmented by technology, and on the other, our bodies are inhabited by colonies of bacteria, viruses and fungi. And I mean, this idea of the individual is so Vienna last century.” - **Markus Reymann**
- “I think the great thing that the president did is to understand, if we only look at trying to make the built environment carbon neutral, it might become a very dull place. So she took this at the same time as an opportunity to drive towards a new European cultural expression. What does Europe stand for?” - **Frank van der Hoeven**

Dubber highlighted the podcast’s role as a bridge between expert knowledge and public understanding, contributing to the NEB’s overarching goals.

5.4. Implementing the NEB in R&D: Challenges faced by EU projects

Clémentine Coujard presented insights from the NEBula project, a CSA focused on connecting the European Union's **Built4People** programme with the NEB. Her talk summarised findings from a September workshop at the Sustainable Places conference, the first session dedicated to the NEB at this annual gathering of European built-environment projects. The session aimed to raise awareness of NEB principles, explore how these were being implemented, and identify challenges encountered by participating projects.

The workshop involved 40 participants from 25 European projects, primarily engineers with fewer representatives from social sciences. Participants explored how NEB values were being integrated into projects. For sustainability, common implementations included energy efficiency, bio-based materials, circularity, and community-building. Challenges included the lack of standards, difficulties with citizen engagement, and a slow shift in mindset within the construction industry.

On inclusiveness, the workshop examined co-creation processes, the role of intermediaries between professionals and residents, and digital and physical participation methods. Challenges arose in ensuring digital inclusion, managing information flow, and building trust. For beauty, discussions focused on cultural identity, emotional connections to places, and using built environments to foster social and cultural activities. However, this value was harder to define, particularly for participants from technical fields, and balancing beauty with sustainability and economic considerations remained difficult.

The NEB working principles also posed challenges. While interdisciplinary collaboration has improved, issues such as differing terminology across cultures and professions, over-solicitation in participatory processes, and skill gaps were noted. Multi-level engagement revealed difficulties in replicating participatory approaches across diverse contexts and ensuring coherence with project objectives. Clémentine explained that sustainability was the most easily understood and implemented value, while inclusiveness and working principles showed progress but required further integration, particularly in stakeholder engagement and co-design. Beauty, with its multifaceted and subjective nature, proved the hardest to operationalise. **She emphasised that while a shift in mindset has begun, full deployment of NEB principles remains a work in progress.**

5.5. Think & Do Tank 1 – What have we learned from “learning by doing”?

The first of four ‘Think and Do Tank’ sessions focused on learning by doing. It was led by Professors José Pedro Sousa and Mia Roth-Čerina, who explored the practical applications, challenges, and transformative potential of a hands-on learning-by-doing approach within NEB initiatives. José Pedro began by sharing examples from the NEB Goes South initiative, describing how it brought together schools of architecture across Europe to engage students, professionals, and local communities in participatory design processes. He highlighted a project in Manteigas, Portugal, where citizens collaborated to reimagine a municipal building, starting not with architectural designs but with discussions to determine its purpose: “We realised the value in not just designing for the community, but designing *with* them.”

Mia Roth-Čerina built on these ideas by discussing the emotional and qualitative dimensions of learning by doing. She talked about a workshop in Croatia where mapping personal and collective memories became a way to reimagine public spaces. “This is about connecting lived experiences to spatial design—not just creating spaces, but embedding meaning and collective identity within them.” Drawing on vernacular traditions, she emphasised the importance of designing spaces that

invite collective behaviours: "What are the conditions that allow a space to become more than just its physical form - something that is truly shared?"

What have we learned from "learning by doing"?
What is the task? The power of MEB for effective knowledge transfer and learning.

Frame 3

What have we learned from 'learning by doing'?

- how do we 'make' neighborhoods?
- what conditions enable collectivity?
- what needs to change in education, including 'life-wide' and life-long learning?

Frame 4

Frame 5

What was done?

What can we learn?

What are the key principles or practices of "learning by doing" more effective than traditional approaches?

What challenges or barriers have you faced when implementing "learning by doing" methods? How have you addressed them?

How can we assess the success of "learning by doing" initiatives in terms of knowledge transfer and long-term impact?

What policy changes or institutional supports are needed to scale "learning by doing" practice and embed them in education, industry and community projects?

After the initial presentations, the conversation was opened up under Chatham House rules (with exceptions granted for cases where participants wished to be identified), and participants contributed a wide range of insights and experiences both verbally and via a Miro board.

A contributor noted the iterative nature of learning by doing, remarking that "the first time a process happens, people experiment; the second time, they truly learn." Another participant shared a story of a workshop where schoolchildren collaborated with architects to design a green space. The key lesson was the importance of engaging participants in all process stages, including understanding why certain ideas might not be feasible. "It's not just about empowering people to dream but helping them navigate the realities of implementation."

A recurring theme was the challenge of measuring the impact of learning by doing. Many participants advocated for moving beyond quantitative metrics, with one remarking, "We are obsessed with numbers, but how do you measure when someone's life has changed?" Instead, they argued for capturing stories of transformation and change, using narrative approaches to convey outcomes. Another contributor expanded on this idea: "Take photographs now, take them later, and capture the evolution. It's a simple but powerful way to show long-term impact."

The discussion also highlighted systemic barriers, including the rigidity of regulatory frameworks and funding mechanisms. One speaker observed, "Public procurement and funding criteria often favour predefined outcomes, but learning by doing thrives on iteration and experimentation. We need policies that reflect this reality." Others pointed to the need for experienced facilitators to guide participatory processes and for clear frameworks to align bottom-up initiatives with institutional requirements.

A key observation was that some things can only be learned by doing. "You can't learn to surf without surfing" was how this was epitomised. Still, the emphasis on hands-on learning does not replace the value of learning in more traditional methods. Knowledge in books and articles is still foundational for many, if not

most intellectual domains. For instance, with architecture, key physical principles of structural engineering do not need to be rediscovered every time by trial and error.

The session concluded with reflections on the long-term potential of learning by doing, particularly its ability to create a sense of ownership among participants. One speaker recounted a project where, despite political setbacks, a community felt empowered to continue advocating for their priorities. "The process itself becomes a foundation—a way for communities to build resilience and keep pushing forward." Through its exploration of successes, challenges, and future possibilities, the session underscored the unique power of learning by doing to foster inclusive, sustainable, and meaningful change.

The following ideas were highlighted in post-it notes contributed on the Miro board by participants.

What are the key principles or practices of "learning by doing" more effective than traditional approaches?

- "Learning by doing"
- "Learning by interaction"
- "Learning by reflection"
- "You can't learn to surf without surfing"
- "Learning by doing changes the process. It is no longer a one-way street"
- "Learning by doing changes the subject of the learning process"
- "Bottom-up processes"
- "It is key to transfer balance between external inputs and local capabilities in iterative ways"
- "What is the subject of the learning-by-doing process?"

What challenges or barriers have you faced when implementing "learning by doing" methods? How were they addressed?

- "Communities have their own rhythms and timeframes"
- "First challenge is to establish a common vocabulary and understanding of NEB" - (Eszter Davida)
- "Have a common understanding on what NEB values can mean in the local environment"

How can we assess the success of "learning by doing" initiatives in terms of knowledge transfer and long-term impact?

- "Qualitative rather than only quantitative measurements"
- "Narrative"
- "Do every pilot activity twice"
- "Find alternatives to quantitative methods"
- "Build local ownership of process/knowledge"
- "Learn to recognise and capture intangible impact"
- "Labeling is important, needs to mean something to the people using it"
- "Finding new ways to discover and monitor democracy" - (Roberto Cavallo)
- "Start thinking about long-term impacts now. How do you compare pilots when you can't measure success until years later?"

What policy changes or institutional supports are needed to scale "learning by doing" practices and embed them in education, industry and community projects?

- "New roles in institutions and municipalities"
- "Further focus on NEB as a value-driven framework with clear incentives for those leading learning-by-doing practices"
- "Try definition: policies are tools for experimentation, for finding out, for taking a risk, for learning"
- "Stop asking 1000 partners to apply for a tiny pot of funding"
- "Local government capacity building as part of the NEB Academy"
- "Non-tension between professionalisation and skills of facilitators and learning outcomes"
- "When are the gaps? When they are already testing with enough early adopters with active participation"
- "At least there's a budget already..."
- "Use a framework that has experimentation embedded in its process"

5.6. NEB and the Regions: Launch of the RIM Handbook

The *Regional Innovation Model (RIM) Handbook* was launched in a session celebrating its potential as a tool for disseminating best practices and NEB principles. It was opened by Kieran McCarthy, Cork City Councillor and Member of the EU Committee of the Regions, who reflected on NEB’s journey and its transformative impact on local and regional development. A self-described passionate advocate for integrating NEB values into policymaking, McCarthy called the initiative “a paradigm shift that has brought together actors, organisations, and networks in ways we’ve never seen before.” He stressed the importance of ensuring NEB’s ideas reach the local level: “The real battle now is at the grassroots, with local authorities and citizens.” He also suggested a second launch for the handbook at the Committee of the Regions Plenary, inviting further engagement to bring its ideas to a wider audience.

Following McCarthy’s introduction, video messages from international members of the NEB HLRT, Orla Murphy, Shigeru Ban, Hubert Trammer and Sheela Patel, reflected on their experiences with the New European Bauhaus and their hopes and concerns for the initiatives going forward (see section 2.3 above). The panel discussion, moderated by Andrew Dubber, focused on the handbook’s themes and the broader implications of its approach.

Orla Murphy

Orla Murphy discussed the achievements of the New European Bauhaus in Ireland, highlighting its integration into national policy and its influence on local projects and education. She described initiatives such as the creation of a climate-resilient garden in a disadvantaged town and the transformation of architectural education to address the dual challenges of housing and climate emergencies. Orla underscored the unique approach of the NEB, which balances local, inclusive actions with transdisciplinary collaboration. She emphasised the rigorous, evidence-based nature of the initiative, its commitment to pluralism and co-creation, and its capacity to foster resilience and trust in a challenging global context. She also warned of the fragility of the New European Bauhaus principles, highlighting the threats of political resistance, misinformation, and global instability. **She noted that building trust with vulnerable communities is delicate and can be easily undermined by external shocks. She also cautioned against oversimplification, stressing the importance of pluralism, accommodation of dissent, and resisting one-size-fits-all solutions to pursue a more inclusive and regenerative world.**

Shigeru Ban

Shigeru Ban reflected on his work with the New European Bauhaus, particularly his collaboration on privacy partitions for Ukrainian refugees following the Russian invasion. He described how the NEB network enabled swift action to provide support in Poland, Slovakia, and other countries, showcasing the effectiveness of international cooperation. **He praised the Bauhaus initiative for fostering deep connections among its members and creating opportunities to share knowledge and educate younger generations. He emphasised the organisation’s success in bringing people together to address urgent challenges through collaborative, innovative approaches.**

Hubert Trammer

Hubert Trammer reflected on his experiences as a member of the NEB HLRT from 2021 to 2024. He highlighted collaborative efforts, including his work on implementing Shigeru Ban's privacy partition system for Ukrainian refugees in Poland and Slovakia. Trammer described Ukraine as a "laboratory" for rebuilding efforts aligned with the principles of sustainability, inclusivity, and innovative design. He praised the evolution of Bauhaus concepts, particularly the shift from a narrow focus on aesthetics to a broader emphasis on multisensory experiences, belonging, and quality of life. He also stressed the importance of balancing sustainability efforts across diverse sectors and global contexts. **Trammer expressed concern that groups, such as farmers and others outside the creative industries, were not sufficiently included in sustainability efforts. He highlighted the risk of overlooking these stakeholders in a framework that aims to be holistic and equitable. Additionally, he highlighted a narrow understanding of aesthetics within the European Bauhaus, advocating for a broader, multisensory approach that values local contexts and experiences.**

Sheela Patel

Sheela Patel expressed gratitude for her involvement in the New European Bauhaus but voiced concerns about its current trajectory. She criticised the apparent loss of the initiative's initial global perspective, noting that it now seems more inwardly focused and less ambitious in its scope. Sheela argued that NEB's potential to address interconnected global challenges, such as climate and development, is not being fully realised. **She stressed the urgency of addressing energy efficiency in public housing within the EU as a critical issue that NEB should prioritise. She highlighted the inaccessibility of science and technology for vulnerable populations and the lack of emphasis on equity in carbon reduction efforts across northern and southern cities. She also pointed to the NEB's shift towards funding small, competitive projects rather than maintaining its broader, systemic ambitions. She emphasised her respect for NEB professionals and commitment to the initiative's ideals, urging it to reclaim its ambitious and inclusive vision.**

Eszter Davida (left) discussed her work in Hungary, where NEB-inspired funding structures have enabled deeper participatory processes. She described a project that transformed an unused school building into a community hub, noting that 30% of the budget was allocated to engaging the neighbourhood. "Without NEB, this kind of funding and community focus simply wouldn't have been possible." **She emphasised the need for similar models in smaller municipalities across Europe and stressed the importance of personal engagement: "Toolkits are essential, but someone has to be there to walk communities through the process. Change happens when people meet, connect, and act together."**

Michela Magas contextualised the *Regional Innovation Model (RIM) Handbook* within the broader framework of the New European Bauhaus and reflected on its origins and goals. She explained the groundbreaking collaboration that led to the

handbook's central idea, emphasising the unprecedented level of coordination between EU institutions and stakeholders. **“For the first time, we brought together the Committee of the Regions, Interreg Europe, DG Grow, and the Commissioner’s Cabinet in a single meeting,” she explained. This convergence of efforts was critical in aligning instruments and funding mechanisms to support local initiatives and scale their impact.**

Magas highlighted the pandemic and the early stages of the war in Ukraine as key moments that demonstrated the power of cooperation and knowledge-sharing. These crises underscored the urgency of building resilient, adaptable systems that can respond to challenges while fostering solidarity. She shared the example of the collaboration between Shigeru Ban and Hubert Trammer to implement privacy partitions for Ukrainian refugees, describing it as a powerful demonstration of NEB’s principles in action. “This was about rolling up our sleeves and showing that NEB isn’t just theory—it’s practical and transformative.” She also outlined specific mechanisms that have been introduced to support NEB-inspired initiatives, such as the voucher scheme to provide funding and support to small municipalities. She described the handbook as a critical tool for scaling these efforts. “It captures the methods, stories, and learnings that can help ignite recovery sparks across regions.”

“We now have a wealth of people with hands-on experience in NEB coordination. These are the individuals who can bring the ideas in this book to life.” - Michela Magas

Lead author of the earlier DigiNEB prototype handbook, Jan Åman, shared insights from prototyping initiatives in northern Sweden, emphasising that small, experimental projects can generate scalable solutions. He expanded on the importance of integrating expertise with community-driven approaches, sharing how inviting world-renowned experts like Shigeru Ban can inspire local efforts. **“Prototyping creates the momentum needed to challenge entrenched systems”. “When you combine global expertise with grassroots energy, you create something extraordinary”.** The panel agreed that this ecosystemic approach, which balances top-down and bottom-up efforts, is crucial for achieving NEB’s ambitious goals.

Kieran McCarthy concluded the discussion by urging participants to ensure the handbook reaches communities across Europe. He emphasised the need for localised launches and outreach and highlighted the growing interest in NEB principles at the municipal level. **“In my own city, we’re seeing departments like architecture and community culture genuinely embrace this work - and enjoy it.” “This book is a starting point, but it’s up to all of us to bring it to life.”**

5.7. Think & Do Tank 2 – What have we learnt from EU neighbourhoods?

The second Think and Do Tank, moderated by Aase Højlund Nielsen and Annemie Wyckmans, explored lessons from EU neighbourhoods, focusing on the challenges and opportunities of scaling, replicating, and adapting NEB-inspired initiatives in diverse local contexts. The session featured narratives, examples, and reflections from participants, weaving together insights on the power of community-driven approaches, the complexities of replication, and the role of NEB principles in fostering sustainable and inclusive neighbourhoods.

A recurring theme was the tension between the deeply local nature of NEB projects and the desire to replicate their successes. One participant asked, “How do you scale and replicate something that is truly place-based and deeply rooted in local contexts?” The conversation reflected on how scaling often risks losing the richness and nuance of the original project, with one speaker suggesting that “scaling” might better be reframed as “spreading inspiration” or “scaling relationships” rather than directly duplicating outcomes.

Several examples illustrated these dynamics. One participant described a co-design project in a disadvantaged community that addressed climate resilience by creating a public space to manage floodwaters. They noted the importance of embedding NEB principles in national policy and procurement to ensure that all public projects integrate the NEB principles.

Another example highlighted a project in Denmark where artists worked with local communities at construction sites, creating a deeper sense of place and revealing hidden beauty in ordinary spaces. The participant observed that such activities not only transformed perceptions but also inspired broader changes in how spaces were understood and valued.

The discussion also touched on the risks of unintended consequences, such as gentrification, when NEB projects attract investment but displace the very communities they aim to support. “We’ve seen it too many times,” one participant warned, “where the creativity and community engagement used to revitalise an area are later erased when prices rise, and original residents can no longer afford to stay.” This raised questions about how to safeguard NEB values in the long term, ensuring that community-driven initiatives remain inclusive and accessible.

A critical point of reflection was the importance of relationships in enabling knowledge transfer. One speaker shared an anecdote of a Danish agricultural school adapting an Irish approach to working with vulnerable young people. The key to the project’s success was not merely the method itself but the personal trust and understanding between collaborators. “He didn’t just copy and paste the idea,” the participant explained. “He adopted it, adapted it, and applied it in his own context.”

The role of funding and industry engagement was also explored. Participants acknowledged that private developers often drive regeneration projects, but they emphasised the need for public bodies to retain a guiding role in applying NEB frameworks to ensure that projects align with sustainability and inclusivity goals. One contributor remarked, “If the NEB principles are to have a real impact, they need to be seen not as just another framework, but as a tool for assessing and managing complex urban challenges.”

The session closed with a reflection on the challenge of making NEB’s tacit knowledge explicit and accessible to municipalities and practitioners. Participants emphasised the need for intermediaries who can translate lessons into practical tools while recognising that the true value of NEB lies in its approach. As one speaker put it, “NEB isn’t just about methods or tools—it’s an ethos, a way of rethinking how we live, work, and create together.”

The following ideas were highlighted in post-it notes contributed on the Miro board by participants.

Question: How might we create interest from stakeholders and policy makers in the learning and outcomes from NEB activities in neighbourhoods?

- "Adopt, adapt, apply."
- "How to align the different initiatives across? First step is to align within the projects and create trust through relationship, next step is to expand this alignment."
- "What are the core that connects this diverse group?"
- "NEB is a playground where you can be creative and invent. You need a structure around that to make sure it doesn’t disappear. We should all be working together to make sure that the guidelines and models are structure, and not regulations." - **Annemie Wyckmans**
- "NEB: a new triple bottom value line – support local governance, transport and green values. Help the industry to assess what they are doing!"
- "Holistic view, capability to manage complex issues."
- "We can only be strong if we align first."
- "Broadcasters need receivers."

- "Not everything needs to be scalable."
- "The model of an open invitation to artists, rather than specific artists doing specific things, is what is scalable."
- "Not just scaling up, but out and deeper."
- "Structures before regulations."
- "Building trust in new approaches takes time: housing quality needs to be sufficient to allow for future flexible uses, e.g., beds in and beds out is not lost."
- "What are we scaling in this process? Scaling the values, not necessarily the specifics."
- "Keep telling stories, keep connected, keep going!"
- "The value of a narrative is that you don't need to explain it further."

18 December 2024 | WHAT IS NEXT?

09:00	<p>NEB and Digital impacts for industry</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Key digitalisation trends and AI in the NEB – Diana Popa - JUST Data / AI for social good – results from the JUST Data Week, Michela Magas - DigiPedia – Michela Turrin - Wood construction, digitalisation and NEB: the Wood4Bauhaus alliance, Oliver Jancke, InnovaWood
10:30	<p>Think & Do Tank 3 – What is NEB in the digital? Moderated by: Indy Johar and Michela Magas Participation: ALL NEB and digital principles, values, JUST Data, AI, ethical dimension, the line of justice in the digital, AI applications for industry</p>
12:10	<p>The NEB Pocket Guide on Climate-Positive Cities and Communities (CrAFT Cookbook vol.2) Katherine Weir</p>
12:30	Lunch
13:30	<p>Think & Do Tank 4 – NEB legacy: Impacts & Skills Moderated by Annemie Wyckmans and Roberto Cavallo Participation: ALL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NEB Relay & NEB Alliance - Future pathways for learning and learners (EAAE, Roberto Cavallo)
15:00	<p>Taking results from the NEB legacy into the NEB roadmap: Policy recommendations – ALL projects</p>
15:30	<p>Wrap up – Looking forward: a glimpse into the future Moderated by Frank van der Hoeven, Annemie Wyckmans</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introducing “Shaping Sustainable Futures: Innovating for People-Centric Cities and Communities - NEB Alliance goes forward
16:00	End of Day 2

5.8. NEB and Digital Impacts for Industry

Key digitalisation trends and AI in the NEB - Diana Popa

DigiNEB researcher Diana Popa presented the findings from the Digital Focus Groups and research activities conducted over the past year, aimed at understanding digitalisation trends, gaps, and challenges across the New European Bauhaus (NEB) community. Her presentation reflects the work presented in deliverable D2.5 and offers a landscape overview of the NEB’s approach to digital tools and their integration across sectors and member states, alongside an additional focus on the emerging role of artificial intelligence (AI).

The study initially planned four focus groups but expanded to include a fifth session on AI due to its growing relevance within NEB projects. Diana described how the research employed a funnel methodology, narrowing broad investigations into specific thematic findings. Desk research, interviews with key experts, and community participation in multiplier events underpinned the study, capturing diverse perspectives beyond those found in formal research outputs.

One key finding was the overwhelming volume of available digital tools, which practitioners found challenging to navigate efficiently. She explained, “Most respondents said it is difficult to find the right tool that offers an extra edge for a specific problem without spending significant time evaluating countless options.” Another prominent theme was resistance to being forced into digitalisation. Many participants expressed concerns that digitalisation was treated as a goal in itself, contrary to democratic principles. They emphasised that retaining analogue options was critical for resilience, with one participant observing, “If we rely too heavily on digital solutions, can we function when they are unavailable?”

Diana Popa highlighted systemic challenges, such as digital poverty in education, which perpetuates professional inequities for students. While controlled environments in educational settings allow for testing novel solutions, scaling these tools in real-world scenarios often exposes unforeseen complexities. Educators cautioned against over-reliance on digital tools, warning that critical thinking skills could be eroded. One example discussed was the uncritical interpretation of AI outputs, which could lead to dangerous or misguided decisions.

She also discussed the implications of the EU AI Act, which mandates AI literacy for employees using these technologies. She described activities held during the JUST Industry Data Week in Sweden, including her workshop on AI literacy, where participants mapped the risks posed by low literacy levels across different roles—developers, deployers, and affected individuals. The European approach to AI, focused on user-centric, trustworthy, and ethical frameworks, was contrasted with market-driven models in the United States and state-centric approaches in China.

The presentation also addressed the fragmentation of digital initiatives within the EU, noting a “high volume of low-scale initiatives” that often remain invisible at the European level. Participants in her study expressed a desire for better coordination and visibility, with one remarking, “We need a helicopter view of the digital landscape to understand what tools and solutions are available.”

Interoperability and siloed innovation were identified as major challenges. Popa stressed the need for system-level thinking, stating, “Digitalisation is not consumed amorphously; it must be experienced holistically.” The research also explored how cultural traditions influence the adoption of bio-based materials, revealing that aesthetics often play a decisive role in convincing clients to choose sustainable options despite higher costs.

Popa emphasised the importance of aligning technological development with democratic and ethical principles, ensuring inclusivity and resilience within NEB’s digitalisation efforts. She encouraged attendees to explore the report (D2.5) for further details.

JUST Data / AI for social good – results from the JUST Data Week - Michela Magas

Michela Magas delivered a presentation that connected her extensive work in innovation labs and digital systems with the values and principles of the New European Bauhaus (NEB). She emphasised the critical role of interdisciplinary collaboration and systemic thinking in embedding NEB principles into practical applications, particularly for data, digital systems, and industry.

Magas discussed the fostering of community-driven innovation and bridging gaps between policy, industry, and creative communities. She described NEB-inspired projects as deeply rooted in real-world action: “The tangible examples we take into policy discussions aren’t abstract statistics or theories - they’re real things that happen on the ground.” She credited the NEB community for its ability to create “evidence for policymakers that is unquestionable,” showcasing the practical impact of initiatives in areas like sustainable urban living and health innovation.

The key focus of her presentation was JUST Data practices which integrate fairness, ethics, and accountability into digital systems. She highlighted the shortcomings of FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), which focus on technological interoperability but neglect the responsibilities of data users and collectors: “FAIR data is not fair to people - it’s F.A.I.R. to machines. We need to think about justice and meaning in how we design systems.” She proposed embedding societal and cultural values into data systems to ensure their relevance and fairness across diverse communities.

Magas also addressed the challenges posed by the limits of data within AI systems, citing an example from NEB-inspired workshops that revealed how such systems often amplify biases. She recounted a test in which AI systems were simply unable to produce unbiased representations with the simplest of prompts (e.g. “Show me a woman who is taller than a man”). She used this example to underline the importance of critical interrogation of AI outputs and the integration of NEB principles in AI literacy and governance.

Magas stressed the importance of systemic and ecosystemic thinking, describing ecosystems as dynamic, self-balancing networks that require constant action and collaboration. She argued that NEB principles must transition from static codes of conduct to actionable incentives, enabling stakeholders to co-create solutions that address societal challenges. “It’s about moving from regulation to enablers - from static systems to dynamic, interactive ecosystems.”

Magas’s presentation celebrated the diplomatic and collaborative skills within the NEB community, which she described as essential for fostering democratic and peaceful futures. **She noted that the NEB ethos has trained a new generation of leaders skilled in “social negotiation of meaning,” a capability she linked to resilience, cohesion, and innovative governance. She also underscored the importance of integrating creative and technological disciplines to address complex challenges and shared examples of cross-sector collaborations, including partnerships with artists and engineers that led to safer mining practices and enhanced urban environments. These initiatives exemplify NEB’s potential to inspire transformative change across industries and communities.**

INCLUSION

DATA BASED ON SOCIETAL AND CULTURAL VALUES

ECOSYSTEMIC APPROACHES TO DATA-DRIVEN SYSTEMS

JUST DATA

MITIGATION OF BIASES, TRANSPARENCY OF PROVENANCE, PROTECTION OF SENSITIVE DATA, JUDICIOUS DATA PRACTICES

DigiPedia – Michela Turrin

Michela Turrin presented *DigiPedia*, a project aimed at advancing digital literacy and fostering open education within the architecture and built environment sectors. She explained DigiPedia as a platform designed to address the evolving challenges of digitalisation in education and industry, connecting to broader NEB values by emphasising inclusivity, collaboration, and sustainability.

Her presentation discussed the importance of digital literacy, which she described as a skillset that goes beyond basic software knowledge to include a deep understanding of digital transformation and its implications. “It’s not just about learning tools; it’s about mastering how to think critically and embrace transformation.”

DigiPedia offers open-access educational materials that integrate practical and theoretical knowledge. The platform aligns with the principles of open science and education, making resources publicly available and encouraging collaboration among educators, students, and professionals. Turrin emphasised the project’s commitment to scalability and adaptability. While DigiPedia is currently being tested within her faculty at TU Delft, plans are underway to expand its reach through collaboration with industry and other universities. She pointed out that the platform also addresses the needs of professionals under pressure to adapt to AI and digital innovation. **“Digital literacy isn’t just for students; it’s a lifelong requirement in a rapidly changing industry.”**

Wood construction, digitalisation and NEB: the Wood4Bauhaus alliance - Oliver Jancke

Oliver Jancke presented the work of the Wood4Bauhaus Alliance, illustrating the role of wood construction in advancing the NEB principles. He provided an overview of the sector, its digitalisation, and its alignment with NEB goals, while also highlighting the challenges and opportunities in adopting wood as a sustainable building material.

He noted its contribution to Europe’s economy and environment, employing 17.5 million people and covering over a third of the continent’s landscape. While wood construction is a small part of this broader sector, he highlighted its rapid growth over the past 30 years, driven by innovation and digitalisation. “Wood construction today is highly digitised, based on off-site production and engineered wood products.” He showcased examples such as prefabricated modules and cross-laminated timber (CLT) used in high-rise and modular buildings.

One of the key advantages of wood construction is storing carbon and contributing to climate goals. “It’s not just about taking CO2 out of the air and storing it in forests, but also transferring it to long-term storage in buildings.” Recent developments in design for deconstruction are further enhancing sustainability, allowing materials to be reused rather than discarded.

Oliver traced the sector’s success to strong partnerships between companies, research institutions, and educational organisations: “This interconnected ecosystem has allowed us to solve major technical issues like fire resistance, thermal insulation, and structural soundness.” He also stressed the importance of initiating projects with wood in mind from the outset, warning that treating it as a late-stage alternative often limits its potential.

The Wood4Bauhaus Alliance has facilitated knowledge sharing, policy recommendations, and co-creation workshops that bring technical and business professionals into dialogue with creative and community-driven stakeholders, challenging siloed approaches and fostering a broader vision for the future of sustainable construction. **“NEB has given us tools to step out of our silos and engage with new perspectives.”**

5.9. Think and Do Tank 3: What is NEB in the Digital?

Indy Johar opened Think and Do Tank 3 with a provocative reflection on the systemic forces shaping Europe’s future and their implications for the New European Bauhaus. He framed his remarks around three critical dynamics—growth, security, and regulation—and challenged participants to rethink the scale and methods of transformation required to address the challenges ahead.

He began by highlighting the centrality of economic growth to maintaining Europe’s welfare infrastructure and social contract, arguing that growth is no longer just an ideological debate but a pragmatic necessity: “Without growth, the welfare infrastructure crumbles, and the social contract begins to break.” He noted the increasing global volatility driving nations to prioritise resilience in foundational economies, particularly in securing resources such as energy, food, and critical minerals. **He described this as part of a broader shift towards a "new production economy" that Europe must navigate.**

A major focus of his introduction was the diminishing effectiveness of Europe’s traditional reliance on regulatory mechanisms to drive change. He said that “a regulatory-driven approach to change is dead,” and pointed to Europe’s declining share of global GDP and its reduced geopolitical leverage. **He argued that Europe’s influence must now shift towards enabling frameworks for industrial transformation rather than enforcing policy-driven change. This requires a fundamental rethinking of how NEB and other initiatives engage with economic and political realities.**

Indy Johar also addressed the digital infrastructure landscape, describing Europe as a "digital vassal state" of the United States. He critiqued Europe’s failure to establish its own robust digital ecosystem, noting that “the greatest digital boom the world has seen left Europe with Spotify.” **The digital**

dependency on the US presents both a challenge and an opportunity for Europe to lead in building new digital infrastructures that go beyond traditional notions of sovereignty and enable democratic and inclusive innovation.

With respect to NEB, Indy called for a scale of transformation akin to the Industrial Revolution, emphasising the need to transition to a biomaterial and intangible economy while radically reducing resource consumption. He criticised NEB’s tendency towards small, localised projects, urging participants to think in terms of systemic, large-scale change. **“What is the new Bauhaus Berlin or Hamburg? We have to start talking about scales of transformation we’re uncomfortable with—hundreds of millions of euros in capital, not small projects.”**

A recurring theme was the need to rethink economic models and the valuation of NEB-aligned projects. While such projects are often seen as expensive in traditional economic terms, they generate unaccounted-for value: **“We have to shift how we price future value in our economy.”**

Finally, he addressed the need to rethink not just the “what” but the “how” of transformation. He critiqued traditional public-private partnership models and startup-driven approaches as insufficient for the scale of change required. Instead, he called for the development of new institutional and organisational models that can operate at the necessary speed and scale. **“The real shortage isn’t a description of the problem—it’s the means of organising the solution.”**

Following Indy Johar's introductory speech, Michela Magas responded by building on his call for systemic transformation, emphasising the importance of designing new economic models and collaborative frameworks. She addressed the need for Europe to leverage its unique strengths - values-driven governance, interdisciplinarity, and inclusivity - to create scalable solutions that align with NEB principles. She highlighted the necessity of moving beyond traditional regulatory frameworks, advocating instead for enablers that foster dynamic ecosystems. **“We need to stop thinking of regulations as static barriers and start thinking of them as tools to incentivise action.”**

Magas reflected on the NEB’s ability to bring together unlikely collaborators across disciplines and sectors, citing her experience with the Industry Commons Foundation. She emphasised the importance of integrating digital tools and data systems into this process, highlighting JUST Data as a framework for creating accountability and fairness in AI and digital infrastructure: **“Data systems need to serve communities and align with human values.”**

She also stressed the urgency of scaling up NEB initiatives and advocated for embedding NEB principles into the foundational economies of energy, food, and mobility. She emphasised that true transformation requires aligning industrial processes with long-term societal goals. **“This is about building infrastructures for future generations, not just patching existing ones.”**

Participants in the room expanded on these points, contributing to the Miro board and focusing on the interplay of values, governance, and economic frameworks. One speaker emphasised the role of experimental governance in creating adaptive systems that can respond to rapid societal changes. **“We’ve entered an era where flexibility is more valuable than certainty. Our governance models need to reflect this reality.”**

Another participant highlighted the role of private-public partnerships in fostering systemic change, noting that traditional boundaries between sectors often impede progress. They shared an example of an initiative that brought insurance companies and city planners together to develop flood-resistant infrastructure. **“By aligning incentives across industries, we were able to solve problems that no single sector could address alone.”**

The discussion also touched on the challenge of creating cascading impacts from NEB initiatives. One speaker questioned how small-scale projects could effectively contribute to systemic change, proposing that NEB projects be designed with replication and scalability in mind. **“Every project should be a prototype for a larger system and every system should be designed to evolve.”**

A recurring theme was the need for new economic models that value long-term societal benefits over short-term profits. One participant pointed out the limitations of current financial frameworks, noting that **“We price risk in ways that discourage innovation, yet we fail to price in the cost of inaction.”** They called for NEB-aligned financial tools that reward sustainability and resilience.

Finally, the role of community engagement was highlighted as a critical element of systemic change. Several speakers noted that NEB’s strength lies in its ability to involve citizens in shaping their environments, but they cautioned against tokenistic approaches to participation: **“Communities need to feel ownership, not just consultation.”**

This session reinforced the urgency of aligning NEB principles with bold, systemic action, emphasizing the need for interdisciplinary collaboration, adaptive governance, and innovative economic models. The following key themes were highlighted in the post-it notes contributed by participants.

Growth & Security:

- "We need to build digital infrastructures that allow multi-national collaboration. EU can play a role in transnational democratic systems."
- "Regulatory-driven approach to change is dead."
- "Move from a regulatory economy to a production economy."
- "If we understand why the politicians are growing the way they are (growth, security), we can create the space for them to operate in new ways by recognising the deeper questions."
- "Default is a mission to ‘not do something’—massively reduce our material economy."
- "The state as a partial representation of the public."
- "Growing delta between return on labour and return on capital. Political gap that needs to be addressed as a new economy."

Theories of Regulation and Structural Change:

- "Theories of regulation need to be dynamic."
- "Serious systemic change can only happen by perpetuating existing capital structures."
- "We need to digitise our core registries—they give us a pathway to look at new horizons of regulation."

Vision and Ambition:

- "What do we plan and what do we not plan?"
- "Not design vs plan. Experiment and test. Iterate. Learn by doing."
- "Ambition transforms everything."
- "We have to fix the engine while the train is running."

Innovation and New Models:

- "Banks 50-80 years ago were structured for regional wealth—not a quarterly rate."
- "Human-machine relationship is evolutionary rather than input/output."
- "\$200B for AI R&D in the US to generate AI-products—this energy and market cascade from there."
- "Create new affordances, which open up new market possibilities."
- "We need an innovation insurance agency."

Values and Foundations:

- "NEB compares values as drivers of our action, e.g. AI—why are we using these tools? For what values?"
- "NEB as a means of developing policies, not just another funding channel."
- "NEB as a soft tool to influence policies in countries that are slow to come on board."
- "Play the ball in front of us: civil security."

Systemic Change:

- "Systemic change in silos makes no sense."
- "Create a shopping list of demands for regulatory change. This is why we need a NEB Alliance."
- "Movements are organically evolving and can't be controlled top-down."

Practical Examples and Challenges:

- "London Olympics 2012 was originally an ambitious infrastructure project. Preliminary designs were abandoned due to liability fears."
- "In design, you need confidence that something real will come out of a value. You do not know what the outcome will be."
- "Projectification is a big problem. Projects need to be activities—use continuous projects to keep that dimension."

5.11. Think & Do Tank 4 – NEB Legacy: Impacts & Skills

The final Think and Do Tank of the event, moderated by Annemie Wyckmans and Roberto Cavallo, addressed the future of education and collaboration within the NEB framework. This session focused on exploring pathways to embed NEB principles into learning systems, professional practices, and interdisciplinary collaborations, with a particular emphasis on the role of the NEB Alliance as a mechanism for continuity and expansion.

DigiNEB team member Roberto Cavallo, representing the European Association for Architectural Education (EAAE), began with a reflection on the diverse landscape of architectural education across Europe. He highlighted the spectrum of institutions, from technical universities to art academies, and the unique contributions each brings to fostering NEB-aligned practices. He underscored the necessity of integrating lifelong and **life-wide learning** into curricula to better prepare learners for a rapidly changing world. **“It’s not just about what you learn but how you learn to adapt and contribute meaningfully in contexts beyond traditional boundaries.”**

Cavallo emphasised that architectural education must shift from being primarily object-focused to subject-focused, prioritising the development of dynamic skills and attitudes. He pointed out that many architecture graduates end up working in adjacent fields, such as urban planning, digital design, and environmental consultancy. These shifts highlight the value of transferable skills, including adaptability, resilience, and interdisciplinary collaboration, which are at the core of the NEB ethos. **“Architectural education is not confined to making buildings; it’s about making connections—between people, disciplines, and systems.”**

Annemie Wyckmans facilitated interactive exercises designed to explore the intersections between NEB-aligned projects and emerging skill sets. Participants mapped their work onto NEB’s principles, identifying overlaps, co-benefits, and “win-win solutions.” These exercises encouraged attendees to consider the systemic impact of their projects and how they could foster new ways of learning and working. One participant remarked, **“It’s clear that NEB isn’t just a framework for designing cities—it’s a framework for designing systems of collaboration.”**

A key theme of the discussion was the importance of the NEB Alliance in ensuring the continuity of NEB values across sectors and scales. **Wyckmans highlighted the Alliance’s potential to support skill-sharing, capacity-building, and mentorship, particularly among smaller institutions and communities that might otherwise lack access to NEB resources.** It was positioned as a vehicle for fostering cross-sector collaboration and scaling the impact of NEB initiatives. Participants reflected on the need for distributed networks and governance models that can adapt to local contexts while maintaining a shared vision. One participant observed that **“the strength of the NEB Alliance is in its ability to connect diverse actors and create a shared sense of purpose.”**

The discussion also addressed challenges in translating NEB principles into actionable educational practices. Participants noted the risk of “projectification,” where initiatives become constrained by rigid institutional structures or short-term goals. Instead, they called for an adaptive, experimental approach that allows for ongoing innovation and learning. Wyckmans emphasised the importance of documenting impacts and creating narratives to demonstrate NEB’s transformative potential. **“We need to show not just what we’ve done, but how it’s changed the way we think, work, and collaborate.”**

In addition to the Miro board, as part of the fourth Think and Do Tank, participants also contributed to a Menti questionnaire asking for follow-up NEB-related events that NEB stakeholders could potentially coordinate to participate in. These included:

- Final Conference, Ocean Space (TBA21), Venice, 14/15 November 2025
- Opening of C&CP building, Putselaan, Rotterdam, end of June 2025
- 17-18 December 2024 Brussels DigiNEB + CrAFt + NEBULA with everyone
- Irresistible Cities Lab online webinars, co-creation session, talks, app once a month. Topics to be decided.
- Mapping our joint impacts (what do we measure and how) for integration in the NEB Pocket Guide vol.3 (March 2025) and Brussels event 6-7 March 2025
- Architecture Biennale Venice June 2025
- Smart City Expo World Congress Barcelona 4-6 Nov 2025
- NEB-STAR final event May

- NEBourhoods 2 Day Final Conference: Creating NEBourhoods for Tomorrow March 27-28 Exhibition / Workshops / Site Visit
- October 2025: NEB Lighthouse impact event as part of the Danish EU Chairmanship
- 6-7 March 2025 Brussels 7 March showcasing the joint impacts of the NEB Lighthouses & Alliance
- 21-25 May Oeiras Valley Science Festival (?) September - Tagus Regatta
- Interreg PlaceCraft NEB project kick-off May
- ETOM NEB Lab conference September 2025?
- NEB approaches in Spain REBUILD Expo April 23rd, 2025 Madrid All afternoon session 30,000 attendees
- Launch of the RIM Handbook at the Plenary of the European Committee of the Regions April 2025
- BoS Co-design methodology Date TBC, Brussels
- 1st meeting for the creation of a Community of Cities 13th December 2024 EHHUR's Next GA in Maia - April 2025 Final event of EHHUR project in Denmark between end of August-September 2025
- CAM Bauhaus of the Seas show at Gulbenkian Foundation
- 10-12 June 2025 URBIS Brno integrating NEB in the expo structure
- NetZeroCities 6-8 May 2025 Vilnius: what if we integrate NEB there?
- March: Open Call NEB Academy hubs
- EUSEW eu sustainable energy week
- COP in Belem, Brazil
- Smart City Expo & EIT Community NEB

Participants were also simply asked, “What if we...?”. Responses included:

- NEBify the Parliament
- Work together in finding a social and business impact model to boost the NEB initiative from bottom up, while exploring EU calls opportunities to support that
- Achieved that many more people know how to answer the question "what is the NEB?" in simple and convincing words.
- Have more entities from eastern Europe involved - more discussion on inequities within and beyond Europe
- Work on Weerbare Wijken mission: NEBifying it!
- Connect projects owners that have successfully implemented NEB to other opportunities to keep deploying NEB across Europe
- We create some "open rules" to include NEB objectives in new projects and works procurement
- Push the DigiPedia platform
- Identify / make explicit synergies across projects - joining forces for actions on steps forward / impact.
- Develop a NEB app
- Combine all our good practices?
- prepare really well the NEB academy and put all our energy into it
- Launch a call for micro lump sum grants to develop tools and narratives
- collaboratively write a manifesto for the NEB Alliance.
- Focus on energy transition and affordable housing

5.12. Taking results from the NEB legacy into the NEB roadmap

Participants reflected on the lessons learned from NEB initiatives and how these can inform systemic change at a broader policy level.

A key takeaway was the importance of fostering adaptive, flexible governance models that can respond to the dynamic nature of NEB-aligned projects. Participants agreed that while NEB principles are aspirational, they must be supported by practical frameworks that incentivise their adoption. One contributor noted, **“We need policy that doesn’t just define goals but creates pathways for experimentation and iteration.”** This perspective underpinned calls for policies that embed NEB principles into funding mechanisms, public procurement, and urban planning processes.

Another recurring theme was the need for continuity in NEB’s impact beyond individual projects. Participants discussed the challenge of moving from “projectification” to systemic transformation, emphasising the importance of long-term investment in NEB-aligned networks and infrastructures. **“The legacy of NEB is not just in its projects but in the connections it has fostered.”**

Policy recommendations centred on embedding NEB principles into key European frameworks, such as the European Green Deal and Horizon Europe. Participants highlighted the potential for NEB to act as a bridge between creative and technical sectors, advocating for interdisciplinary collaboration to address complex challenges. They also called for increased support for capacity-building at the local level, ensuring that smaller communities and municipalities have access to NEB resources and expertise.

“Why doesn’t the EU taxonomy, for all of its merits, include the New European Bauhaus and why don’t they pull in the same direction? The investment guidelines, EIB, investment guidelines for NEB and the taxonomy? Could the next step be just one and the same? So if you go to a climate

neutrality Net Zero Cities, of course, also cities missions - it's net zero. It's not really climate neutral. And then you see that all of these big frameworks for climate neutrality, including IPCC, there's hardly any new European Bauhaus values or principles in them. Of course you could imagine it's just that they don't mention the New European Bauhaus, but if you just look at the content, the directionality is really towards technical measures, big infrastructure projects, expensive ones that require a lot of political acceptance in order to get done. So why not get these bottom-up, community-driven, artistic, cultural, social, and local jobs measures in there as well? Because that could create a lot more hope and a lot more leeway. This imagination space that we heard of this morning could happen then, but it's not there now."

The discussion concluded with reflections on the NEB roadmap and its role in scaling the initiative's impact. **Participants emphasised the importance of prioritising cascading effects and the potential for using the scaling methodology outlined in the RIM Handbook, ensuring that the lessons from NEB projects inspire broader systemic change. "The NEB roadmap must not be a fixed destination; it must be a living document that evolves with the needs and ambitions of its stakeholders".**

Takeaways from these two days

Closing remarks highlighted the need to celebrate NEB’s successes while maintaining a forward-looking approach. **Participants agreed that the initiative’s greatest strength lies in its ability to connect people, disciplines, and ideas, creating a shared vision for a more inclusive, sustainable, and beautiful future. These final reflections underscored NEB’s potential to act as a catalyst for transformative change, rooted in its legacy but focused on its future.**

5.13. Conclusions and Policy Recommendations

Over the course of the two-day “Celebrating the Lessons Learnt” event in Brussels, participants contributed many observations, conclusions, and recommendations that can inform policy at the local, regional, and European levels. These are drawn from the four Think and Do Tanks above, as well as the keynotes and discussions at the event, and are summarised below.

Learning by Doing / Education

- Focus more on “life-wide learning” (complementing life-long learning). It should form the basis of a funding call.
- Leverage the RIM Handbook, which contains many on-the-ground examples and case studies of NEB projects that have been implemented. These can serve as inspiration and models for other communities to replicate.
- We need an integrated NEB platform to collect and document all of these great projects and to document the knowledge that we can share further, especially with younger generations - a way to capture the learning and pass it on.
- Learning by doing is not an isolated initiative but a critical component of inclusive, sustainable urban development that should be embedded into policies and standard practices. Ongoing engagement and support for local governments will be crucial to achieving this integration.
- Collaborate with local government representatives, such as through the Committee of the Regions, to codevelop guidelines, toolkits, and other resources that make it easier for municipalities to adopt these practices.

- Revise public procurement policies for more flexible, experimental, and participatory processes. This could include creating dedicated funding streams or innovation vouchers for learning by doing projects.
- Provide training and capacity building for financial institutions, investors, and project developers to understand and apply these new economic and financial theories.
- Provide capacity building and training programs for local government staff to equip them with the skills and mindsets needed to facilitate learning by doing. This could be done through the NEB Academy or other initiatives.
- Establish knowledge-sharing platforms and peer-to-peer learning networks to enable cities to learn from each other's experiences with learning by doing. Facilitate the exchange of tools, case studies, and best practices.
- Adjust evaluation criteria for urban development projects to place greater emphasis on qualitative, community-driven outcomes rather than just quantitative outputs. Recognise the value of the learning process, not just the final product.
- Mandate the inclusion of learning by doing methodologies in urban development plans and strategies. Require municipalities to demonstrate how they are engaging communities and testing new approaches.
- Ensure that learning-by-doing approaches are embedded throughout the entire lifecycle of urban projects, from initial visioning to long-term monitoring and adaptation.
- Create an enabling policy environment that recognises learning by doing as a core component of sustainable, inclusive urban development rather than treating it as a nice-to-have add-on. Systemic change at the policy level is crucial to scaling these practices.
- Documentation is important but not enough. We have to think about the formats for delivering this knowledge to the people who have to use it in their daily work.
- Capture and disseminate, distil and organise the knowledge created at these sorts of events and in NEB initiatives. The knowledge should go beyond those who read EU project reports. Having a designated person or group to collect, distil and share the knowledge would be ideal.
- Engage local governments directly and demonstrate the value of these approaches. Share concrete examples and evidence of how learning by doing has led to more inclusive, sustainable, and community-driven outcomes in urban projects.
- Ensure NEB continues to evolve and reach beyond the "converted" to engage a broader range of stakeholders, including citizens and local/regional authorities.

NEB and the Regions

- Value the inclusive, community-driven approaches that bring together a wide range of stakeholders, including activists, artists, and local residents. This helps ensure the NEB movement remains grounded in local contexts.
- Disseminate and support the RIM Handbook more widely across the EU regions to engage more local and regional authorities at events such as the book launch suggested by Kieran McCarthy.
- Use local champions with strong personal connections (many more "Michelas and Jans") on the ground to help facilitate and curate NEB activities locally. The RIM Handbook can serve as a tool to empower and equip these local champions.

- Find ways to make the tacit knowledge and approach of the New European Bauhaus more explicit and accessible for municipalities and other local actors, potentially through intermediaries or "oven-ready" examples they can adapt.
- Consider the importance of time, immediacy, and deep community engagement when translating and replicating place-based project learning across different contexts rather than just focusing on scaling.
- Policymakers should acknowledge the different layers of existential risks facing various populations and tailor responses accordingly rather than generalising to issues like climate change.
- Encourage the integration of NEB principles into national and local policy frameworks, urban planning, and public procurement processes to drive systemic change.
- Utilise intermediaries and knowledge brokers. Municipalities, NGOs, and other organisations can be key in translating NEB and spreading good practices to the private sector in accessible, actionable ways.
- Advocate for policy changes that create space and incentives for learning by doing. This could include revising procurement processes, development plans, and funding schemes to prioritise participatory and experimental approaches.
- Facilitate knowledge sharing and capacity building for local government staff. Offer training, workshops, and peer-to-peer learning opportunities to help them understand and implement learning by doing methodologies.
- Highlight successful case studies and support local leaders who have championed learning by doing. Use these examples to inspire and motivate other cities to follow suit.
- Prioritise an ecosystemic, collaborative approach, bringing together diverse stakeholders - local authorities, citizens, experts, corporations, etc. This collaborative model can help scale initiatives by mobilising broader support and resources.
- Facilitate better cross-sectoral collaboration and knowledge exchange between NEB initiatives, industry, academia, and policymakers to align priorities and leverage synergies.
- Ensure the inclusion of a diverse range of stakeholders, including marginalised communities, in the development and implementation of NEB-related policies and programs.
- Explore ways to provide capacity-building support and resources for smaller organisations, one-person architecture offices, and entities from underrepresented regions to participate actively in the NEB movement.
- Activists and practitioners should seek to build alliances across sectors and industries to drive systemic change, rather than operating in silos.
- Develop strategies to prevent gentrification and displacement when implementing place-based projects, such as aligning incentives across diverse stakeholders and building trust from the start.

NEB and the Digital

- Implement JUST Data practices and principles as a central digital pillar for all NEB initiatives.
- Adopt a public service approach to digital media in Europe that draws from the public service broadcasting and public access media models - free from commercial and political pressure, publicly funded, connecting, supporting and amplifying communities, and addressing market failure.

- We need to digitise our core registries, they give us a pathway to look at new horizons of regulation
- Europe should leverage its strategic advantages in areas like the human-machine economy, digital infrastructure, and public goods to chart a distinct path from the US and China. This could involve developing new forms of computational consensus-building and public engagement.
- Encode the political economy of the Bauhaus movement as an alternative to surveillance corporatism.
- Outline principles for maintaining an "open playground" for experimentation, innovation, and new ideas while also working to consolidate and stabilise successful NEB approaches.
- Safeguard responsible uses of data when applying NEB to the digital space.
- Maintain an open, distributed network and collective intelligence rather than a centralised structure. This allows for more flexibility and grassroots engagement.
- Foundational economy of Europe can be built on the affordances of the digital environment.
- Use the NEB compass to assess values as drivers of our action. eg: Questioning AI - why are we using these tools? For what values?
- We should be building the new capabilities that give us the resilience and capabilities.
- Establish a centralised platform or repository to document and share the diverse impacts, processes, and learnings from NEB projects and initiatives. This can help inform policymakers and funders on the value and potential of NEB approaches.
- There are so many good tools we need to connect them. NEB can be "digital mycelium". We need to make the tools more user-friendly.
- Backcast from a vision for the future. Some problems that we have to address, like it or not, but we need a values-based vision to move towards.

The future of NEB and NEB Legacy

- Emphasise the role that the NEB thought leaders play - people who have trained as cohesion enablers and other essential skills. They can act as NEB Diplomats - the people here can work as that.
- Link the NEB initiatives so that when one project finishes, we can offer opportunities to continue elsewhere.
- Advocate for better integration and alignment between NEB and other EU initiatives, programs, and funding streams to maximise synergies and impact.
- NEB should urgently address the need for energy-efficient public housing in the EU to combat extreme weather.
- Leverage NEB as a new "triple bottom line" framework. Position NEB as a way for companies to demonstrate sustainability, inclusion, and cultural value in their work, beyond just traditional metrics. This can help integrate the principles into their decision-making.
- Consider establishing an "innovation insurance agency" to price the systemic risks associated with new technologies and business models. This could help create the conditions to support more ambitious, values-driven innovations.
- Integrate NEB principles and values more closely into existing EU policy frameworks, funding programs, and investment guidelines. This includes aligning the EU Taxonomy, IPCC

guidelines, and mission-oriented initiatives like the Climate Neutral Cities to better reflect NEB's focus on community-driven, inclusive, and culturally sensitive approaches.

- Provide dedicated funding and support mechanisms for the NEB Alliance and its member organisations to continue their work, expand their reach, and maintain the playground for experimentation.
- There is a need to be more ambitious and systemic in the vision for transformation, going beyond small-scale projects to address the scale of change required across the economy and society.
- Incentivise cross-sector collaboration and the involvement of diverse stakeholders, including community members, in the planning and implementation of urban initiatives. Make this a requirement for accessing funding or other support.
- Support research and development of new economic models that go beyond traditional GDP and financial metrics to capture the broader value generated by Bauhaus approaches.
- Implement policies and incentives that encourage the adoption of these new valuation frameworks, such as tax credits, procurement rules, or investment funds targeted at Bauhaus-aligned initiatives.
- Establish public-private mechanisms to finance large-scale Bauhaus-inspired projects, moving beyond the limitations of traditional public-private partnerships.
- Engage industry and private sector stakeholders more effectively to demonstrate the value of New European Bauhaus principles and align incentives.
- Document and share the diverse experiences, impacts, and unexpected outcomes from NEB projects and initiatives to help inform policy and funding programs.
- Commit to expanding the NEB community to include more entities, especially from Eastern Europe, and re-establish the wider, outward-looking international focus of NEB to ensure broader geographic representation and diversity of perspectives.
- Involve decision-makers from all sectors in these gatherings and discussions because the conversations are so fruitful. Why do this all over again just to include another group?
- Focus on creating synergies across all NEB initiatives - emphasise and build upon coordination between projects.
- Rethink regulation to incentivise new forms of value creation.
- There is a need to move beyond a purely regulatory approach to change and instead focus on enabling functions for a new industrial future. This requires rethinking the political economy and developing new theories of value, pricing, and financing.
- Communicate more with others outside the immediate NEB community. Most people don't know what it is.
- It would be ideal for NEB actors not to need the European Commission to work on the NEB. It is something to work towards in 2025 for all involved - further collaboration outside the boundaries of funded projects and an Innovation Commons investment mindset rather than a project funding mindset to create sustainable initiatives.

6. Stakeholder Engagement Plan

The Stakeholder Engagement Plan included all activities that the DigiNEB consortium aimed to implement during the project lifetime. Each partners has contributed to upskilling, upscaling and leveraging existing communities. Linking with partners’ existing networks and connections has been an essential aspect of this outreach, as well as ensuring that the digital divide and data literacy issues are addressed within stakeholder-specific domains. In addition, each partner had a specific focal area, in part to share the workload and leverage key strengths but also to avoid duplication.

The role played by each partner is summarised in the table below:

Partner name	Engagement role and responsibility
Delft University of Technology (TU Delft)	The partner is the primary contact for creating the DigiNEB Thematic Working Groups. TU Delft provides, as the main outcome, the development of landscape and gap reports and contribution to the strategic DigiNEB Deployment Roadmap. In the amended and updated DigiNEB plan, TU Delft has taken over the design and management of the website platform. Furthermore, TU Delft is engaged in three NEB Lighthouse projects (CULTUURCAMPUS, NEB-STAR, and DESIRE), ensuring a smooth dialogue with them.
Industry Commons Foundation (ICF)	ICF brings together an extensive network of over 8500 cross-domain stakeholders and experts in cross-domain collaboration. The ICF work in digital solutions for large industry players enables a strong connection between NEB and digital transformation. ICF Director of Research, Michela Magas, is a member of President von der Leyen’s High Level Round Table for NEB and is closely connected to the thought leaders of the NEB Labs and Lighthouse projects, as well as NEB Partners and Friends of NEB. As Member of the CERN Advisory Board, she is able to leverage the connection between NEB and CERN.
European Association for Architectural Education (EAAE)	EAAE is one of the main contributors to scout and recruit Early Adopters of the NEB Digital Ecosystem. The team also contributes to adding relevant content for the eLearning courses included in the NEB Academy.
InnovaWood (IW)	The partner has a strong experience in NEB-related initiatives connected to sustainable wood and forestry construction and bio-based materials and acts as one of the leading players in creating engagement towards the stakeholders involved in this field. Moreover, InnovaWood is instrumental in seeking training and digital solutions related to the forestry industry.

Table 4 - Engagement roles and responsibilities played by the DigiNEB consortium

6.1. Plan and Timeline

The DigiNEB consortium performs dedicated campaigns to support the building of an engaged community through four distinct phases, as described during the proposal phase.

Campaigns and channels to engage with the stakeholders

The above graphic shows the original plan. This plan has been updated with a new version of the website. The site has been relaunched by TU Delft to address the challenges that led to the project amendment and refocus of the initiative.

The project timeline has been updated to reflect the phased approach:

- **Phase 1 (M1-14):** Establish core engagement strategies, launch the website, and build the foundation of the DigiNEB community.
- **Phase 2 (M15-27):** Expanding the strategic methodologies, launching new tools like the podcast and handbook, and prioritising in-person and hybrid events for deeper engagement.

This two-phase approach allows for the continuous evolution of the engagement plan, ensuring that it remains responsive to the needs of the NEB community and adaptable to emerging trends in digital innovation and interdisciplinary collaboration.

6.2. Stakeholder Group engagement

To ensure each Stakeholder Group (SG) were both engaged with and could contribute to shaping the NEB digital ecosystem, the consortium updated its plan to maximise involvement across all groups. This engagement strategy emphasised interdisciplinary collaboration and alignment with the NEB initiative, inviting participants from all SGs to engage in shared activities such as the JUST Industry Data Week in Linköping and other interdisciplinary events. Below is the revised engagement plan for each group:

Stakeholder Group	Categories	Engagement Plan
SG#1	Architects, Designers, Engineers, and other professionals belonging to the NEB community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Engaged through participation in the Early Adopters Programme, showcasing NEB-aligned digital solutions that have been adopted and successfully implemented. ● Encouraged to become active users of the Digital Toolkit and Observatory, which provide essential resources for NEB-aligned digital transformation. ● Upskilling opportunities provided via access to the NEB Academy, including eLearning courses aimed at enhancing their professional expertise. ● Participation in Digital Focus Group discussions, contributing to Landscape and Gap Reports that help define the scope of NEB innovation.

Stakeholder Group	Categories	Engagement Plan
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invited to interdisciplinary events and workshops, where they can collaborate with other SGs to shape the NEB digital ecosystem.
SG#2	Construction industry suppliers & other relevant industry players, including start-ups, SMEs, associations in the building, mobility & health sectors, and SDOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exposure opportunities by contributing digital solutions to the Digital Toolkit, allowing their innovations to become potential success stories within the NEB ecosystem. Gaining insights into the NEB digital landscape by interacting with other suppliers and learning about existing market solutions. Offered skills development through access to the NEB Academy's eLearning resources. Participating in interdisciplinary events and workshops, allowing cross-sector collaboration to better understand market needs and opportunities.
SG#3	Research and academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Addressing the knowledge gap by both providing and accessing learning resources, particularly through the NEB eLearning platform. Contributing to discussion groups and engaging with Landscape and Gap Reports to ensure that research outputs are aligned with the NEB ecosystem's needs. Offering access to digital solutions developed in the context of R&I initiatives and EU-funded projects, fostering a bridge between research and real-world applications. Actively participating in interdisciplinary workshops aimed at identifying future needs and gaps within the NEB digital ecosystem, collaborating with professionals from other SGs.
SG#4	Digital technology companies & associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provided exposure opportunities through contributions to the Digital Toolkit, with their digital solutions serving as case studies and success stories. Given access to the NEB digital ecosystem, enabling them to assess and benchmark their offerings against other market solutions. Skills development opportunities through participation in the NEB Academy's eLearning programmes, helping them stay ahead in digital innovation. Engaging in interdisciplinary workshops and events, fostering collaboration with other sectors to shape future needs within the NEB digital ecosystem.
SG#5	Policy Makers, including Green Deal-related	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accessing the Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation, which serves as a foundation for shaping

Stakeholder Group	Categories	Engagement Plan
		<p>future policies that promote NEB-aligned digital environments at both European and local levels.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participating in interdisciplinary webinars and workshops, where they can collaborate with experts from various SGs to gain insights on policy perspectives and NEB-aligned digital transformation.
SG#6	National & regional authorities, mayors (including urban planners) and cities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contributing digital solutions and success stories that showcase NEB-aligned innovations successfully implemented in cities, villages, and regional communities. • Accessing the Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation, helping local authorities align with broader NEB policies while addressing specific regional needs. • Engaging in interdisciplinary workshops, collaborating with other SGs to share local policy insights and practical approaches for applying NEB principles at the regional and local levels.
SG#7	Civil society organisations and citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invited to interdisciplinary webinars that focus on explaining the goals of DigiNEB and the broader NEB initiative, helping citizens understand how they can contribute to and benefit from these innovations. • Accessing the resources made available via the NEB eLearning Catalogue, helping to reduce knowledge gaps and empowering citizens to engage with the NEB digital ecosystem.

Table 6 - Engagement Plan per Stakeholder Group

7. Synergies

Sharing the benefits of developing the NEB Digital Ecosystem is a collaborative activity. Since the beginning of DigiNEB, the project team has established strong synergies with the following NEB initiatives and in industrial domains.

7.1. NEB Lighthouse projects

The NEB [Lighthouse projects](#) are demonstrators that can showcase the benefits and practicalities of applying the NEB's main goals locally. To date, the following 6 Lighthouse projects have been selected¹:

CULTUURCAMPUS: A sustainable hub of arts, research, learning and community as a catalyst. By blending education, research, policy, and culture and considering the lived experiences of its residents, Cultuurcampus aims to transform the disadvantaged urban area of Rotterdam

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_2780

South (NL). The Cultuurcampus is in a historic building and acts as a hub for different groups and activities. (<https://www.cultuurencampusrotterdam.nl/en/>)

NEB-STAR (New European Bauhaus STAvangeR): NEB-STAR showcases how territorial transformation plans can incorporate the principles and values of the NEB in Stavanger (NO), Prague (CZ) and Utrecht (NL). The project tackles four emblematic challenges linked to climate-neutral cities, all considering local needs and concerns through co-creation with residents and stakeholders. (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079952>)

NEBourhoods: NEBourhoods prepares Munich-Neuperlach (DE) for the future as mapped out by the European Green Deal regarding the built environment, circularity, mobility, energy, food, and health. The project builds on the area's strengths – a strong sense of community, vast green areas, and large-scale housing, even if in need of renovation – and addresses its weaknesses – higher than average unemployment and lower than average education levels. (<https://www.nebourhoods.de/>)

DESIRE (Designing the Irresistible Circular Society): The project aims to tackle the major challenges faced by societies and cities: climate change, biodiversity loss, and resource challenges. Based on three main themes of inclusivity, circularity and reconciling cities with nature, the project uses art, architecture, and design to explore alternative ways of transforming territories across different European cities in Denmark, the Netherlands, Italy, Latvia and Slovenia. (<https://www.irresistiblecircularsociety.eu/>)

EHHUR (EYES HEARTS HANDS Urban Revolution): the project supports cities and vulnerable residents in transforming their built environment. Spread across seven different locations in the EU and Associated Countries (Denmark, Belgium, Portugal, Italy, Greece, Turkey, and Croatia), it seeks to tackle socioeconomic and cultural challenges such as social segregation, energy poverty, and degradation of depopulated historical centres. (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079948>)

Bauhaus of the Seas: the project aims to promote renewed ethical and aesthetic regenerative development from a diverse range of dimensions of our continued relationship with the sea. Conceived as a journey with Portugal as a starting point, the Bauhaus of the Seas generates a design movement extending to all European coastal and maritime regions.

The NEB Lighthouse projects have been engaged through dedicated workshops where the experts brought their own experiences in cities, regions and nations to help implement the NEB principles thanks to digitalisation. All Lighthouse projects have been onboarded in the first part of the project, primarily through their involvement at the CERN event.

7.2. DigiNEB and sister CSA projects

DigiNEB started to engage with projects that share similarities in terms of communities and objectives in October 2022.

The two sister projects, which are CSAs, are DS4SSCC and Living in EU:

- [DS4SSCC](#) (Data Space for Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities) is an EU-funded initiative that prepares for the creation of a data space for smart communities as an enabler of the EU Green Deal goals and Sustainable Development Goals.
- [Living in EU](#): through co-creation with citizens, the project aims to bring the economic and social benefits of this transformation to all local communities and implement an inclusive digital Europe with powerful digital services, technologies, infrastructures and skills).

7.3. NEB-oriented and sustainable living space projects

In addition to the abovementioned synergies, the DigiNEB consortium established synergies with stakeholders involved in NEB-oriented initiatives, such as [NEB Goes South](#), the [New European Bauhaus of the Mountains](#), [Nordic Carbon Neutral Bauhaus](#), the [Friends of NEB](#), the [NEB High Level Round Table](#), and NEB Labs across all of the EU cities and regions, leveraging the already extensive networks within those frameworks. Cooperation with these initiatives includes the organisation of co-creation events that lead to high-level recommendations for developing the Deployment Roadmap. All of these projects have been engaged and onboarded during the NEB@CERN event during the first part of the project.

DigiNEB included on its External Advisory Board (EAG) Matti Kuittinen, Chair of the Nordic Bauhaus, and Professors Mia Roth-Čerina and José Pedro Sousa of *Bauhaus Goes South*, all of whom have extensive networks of their own.

Synergies with the Nordic Bauhaus was already envisaged in November 2022: Nordic Bauhaus ran an event called *Bauhaus Goes To The Woods*² on 24 November 2022 that drew in wood producers, forestry and primary industry, environmental scientists, open data specialists, ministers and policymakers in countries for whom wood production is extremely important, as well as architects and construction firms with a particular interest in wood construction. By organising around topics of interest rather than industry specialism, the event was able to be much more inclusive.

Synergies with Bauhaus Goes South have been leveraged through active engagement of Mia Roth-Čerina and José Pedro Sousa in running DigiNEB Think and Do sessions both at NEB@CERN and the DigiNEB final event, as well as organising DigiNEB workshops and policy meetings.

In addition, the DigiNEB consortium established synergies with the following projects that operate in the local living spaces and digital environments through 3rd-party events Barcelona Smart City Expo and OASC Connected Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities Conference:

- [AURORAL](#): Architecture for Unified Regional and Open digital ecosystems for Smart Communities and Rural Areas Large scale applications.
- [DUET](#): Virtual city replicas that make it easy to understand the complex interrelation between traffic, air quality, noise and other urban factors. Powerful analytics model the expected impacts of potential change to aid evidence-based operational decisions and longer-term policy choices.
- [CommunityCity](#): A transformative citizen-centred project that is launching 100 tech pilots addressing the needs of cities and communities through co-creation and co-learning processes.
- [CrAft](#): Part of the New European Bauhaus initiative that places the transition to climate neutrality at the heart of urban stakeholders. The project supports the Mission Board on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities and the NetZeroCities platform in designing and deploying Climate City Contracts based on knowledge from CrAft's 3 Sandbox Cities (Bologna, Prague, and Amsterdam) and 60 CrAft Reference Cities.

7.4. Multipliers

During the second project period the consortium focused on creating synergies with industry and DIH engaged in the digital transformation. Strong synergies were achieved across multiple industrial domains at the JUST Industry Data Week and with the wood industry stakeholders at the Wood4Bauhaus event. Both events are described in greater detail in D3.4.

² <https://www.nordicbauhaus.eu/into-the-woods#/page=1>

Over the first 18 months of the project, it became clear that the intersection between ICT and NEB communities must prioritise ethical considerations in data management and the application of AI technologies for societal benefit. This shift in focus represented a renewed opportunity for establishing synergies around data ethics and AI for social good at the heart of DigiNEB’s overarching plan. The DigiNEB multiplier activities have increasingly centred around these themes, driving collaboration with a wide range of projects that explore ethical data management, AI-driven solutions for public good, and prototyping NEB concepts with ICT innovations. These efforts underscore DigiNEB’s commitment to advancing responsible, inclusive technological solutions in line with NEB principles.

Through the JUST Industry Data Week, the project identified synergies with industry, European Digital Innovation Hubs (Linköping Science Park), the EU Capitals of Innovation, and related digitalisation projects at national level. In alignment with the JUST Industry Data Week engagement with data ethics and AI for social good has emerged as a significant area for caring synergies with the DigiNEB project. Synergies have been identified with multiple stakeholders spanning industrial domains in health, space, automotive, primary and wood industries.

8. Monitoring

The impact of all strategically important DigiNEB activities performed is measured through a core set of key performance indicators (KPIs) wherever they are quantifiable. Continuous monitoring activity is carried out by the T4.3 task leader and shared with all partners.

8.1. KPIs

Qualitative metrics come into play whenever there is a need for a deeper analysis of the relevance of outcomes achieved. The table below shows the end-of-project KPI targets and their status at M27.

KPI Number	Description	Status at M27	KPI objective at M27
1	F2F General Meetings	5	5
2	EAB members engaged	17	10
3	EAB strategic meetings	8	2
4	Digital solutions mapped and part of the DigiNEB Toolkit	408	250
5	Open licenses (e.g. MIT) with existing projects	50	25
6	DWGs (TWGs)	4	4
7	Projects/initiatives in the Observatory	509	500
8	Policy briefs by TWGs	4	4
9	Unique visitors to DigiNEB (monthly)	7K (monthly)	50K (cumulative two years)
10	Website Iteration	3	3
11	Early Adopters	149	100
12	Synergies created	Over 300 (in cross-domain multipliers)	100
13	Newsletters including info from DigiNEB	23	21
14	Users engaged in events	2000+	2000
15	Videos	98	24

16	Social media content items published on socials (Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram)	260	192
17	Social media followers (total all channels)	28174 (includes dissemination across partners and via main NEB channels)	7000
18	Webinars organised (100 attendees each)	40 (including 6 traditional webinars and 34 live-streamed seminars, workshops and global brainstorming sessions)	8
19	Workshops organised (50 attendees each)	30	16
20	Yearly events organised (150 attendees each)	3 (2024: 100+ at JUST Data Week and 70 in Brussels)	2
21	Marketing Campaigns	6	6
22	Attended external events	60	not set

Table 7 - DigiNEB KPIs

8.2. Website monitoring

All website analytical data is gathered continuously using **Cloudflare Analytics** to derive detailed statistics about online engagement. Monitoring will be in place to track the project KPIs related to website performance, proactively detect possible problems, and implement corrective actions. The Google Analytics profile was set up in M1, and the first data about traffic sources, visitors, navigation paths and conversions are being tracked. The primary data will be disclosed in the upcoming dissemination deliverables. Dynamic engagement strategies will respond to real-time online metrics. Project update reports will be collected as a more statistically significant data source as traffic grows due to upcoming communication and engagement activities.

A traffic KPI has been set for the activities in WP4 that will be measured with Cloudflare Analytics:

- Traffic: # sessions per month >1.5k at M12, >5k at M27;

The traffic KPI (# of sessions) will be pursued with close cooperation with the communication activities in WP5. As an example of such collaboration, a set of different copy templates for social media posts can be tested to assess which format is more attractive, thus resulting in more traffic.

Other relevant metrics, even if not set as KPIs, will be monitored to assess the success of the operation: individual logins, session duration, number and frequency of new vs returning users, conversion actions (e.g., submitting a web form or downloading a pdf), etc. These, in turn, will help achieve the communication target KPI by helping the communication teams focus on activities that are not only designed to increase traffic but also ensure social media visits.

Similarly, traffic sources, visitor geographies, most viewed pages, etc., are breakdown dimensions that will help us understand which parts of the NEB digital hub are being actively visited and which are not in terms of traffic acquisition and content generation.

A customised dashboard depicting our Cloudflare Analytics results has been set up to monitor these breakdown dimensions and will be updated monthly until M27 (December 2024). In the snapshot below, examples of such metrics and dimensions are shown:

Fig.9 Snapshot of DigiNEB Cloudflare Analytics

Future versions of the dashboard include and monitor variables such as the adoption of digital tools and all other relevant KPIs identified by all WPs. The adoption growth will be marked in a benchmarking activity assessing hands-on engagement and adoption of digital tools in a blended environment that will include technology providers.

User feedback will be collected, and all input will be processed and reverted to the various WPs for iteration and channelling towards further deployment and benchmarking activities. Finally, the successful deployment of technologies will be assessed in a series of feedback loops.

8.3. Other impact monitoring

Throughout the DigiNEB lifecycle, the project team is going to evaluate the impact of all the engagement activities performed:

Engagement Activity	Description	Impact by M03
Organisation of webinars, workshops, yearly events and participation in 3rd-party events	The organisation and participation in events help DigiNEB give visibility to the NEB Digital Ecosystem to all identified SG categories.	The project has reached 149 stakeholders through the webinar and 10,000+ people through third-party events
Development of the Community Database	The Community Database collects all stakeholders DigiNEB has engaged with through social media channels, newsletters or online and physical events.	594 people (362 are coming from social media)
Establishment of Digital Focus Groups	The Digital Focus Groups bring together top-class experts of the NEB digital ecosystem to stimulate discussions and share best practices that are collected to provide strategic policy recommendations.	The identification of the TWGs experts is in progress, and their work will generate four landscape reports and contributions to the two iterations of the DigiNEB Roadmap
Establishment of synergies	Establishment of strong synergies with initiatives in the NEB and local living spaces area to foster the adoption of digitalisation to build more inclusive, sustainable and beautiful living spaces.	The dialogue to clarify the scope of collaboration has started with nine synergies
Development of the Digital Toolkit	The NEB Digital Toolkit comprises digital tools developed by technology providers and EC-funded projects.	27 Digital Solutions added.
Development of the Observatory	The Observatory maps and disseminates the projects and activities in the NEB landscape with a particular focus on R&I projects. It comprises success stories, TWG discussions, and Early Adopters' stories and events.	15 items added, of which: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 success stories - 4 TWG discussion groups - 8 events
Development of the eLearning catalogue	Collaborative online catalogue of initiatives and digital solutions that include best practices and training materials. The eLearning courses stimulate knowledge sharing and are freely accessible on the DigiNEB platform.	The impact by M03 cannot be evaluated as the activity will start in M06. The eLearning catalogue aims to reach 1000+ trainees

Table 8 - Impact monitoring

9. Risks and Mitigations

The following table identifies risks identified during the first months of WP4 implementation and the corresponding risk-mitigation measures implemented so far. Risks with high severity have been mitigated a-priori. All risks - both those already identified and potential new ones - are being continuously monitored at project runtime. New risks/mitigation measures arising from engagement activities are managed as part of **Subtask 1.1.3 Risk management, ethics and IPR management**.

Risk Number	Risk Description	Proposed mitigation measure
R1	<p>Lack of liaisons with pan-European & National initiatives</p> <p>Likelihood: Low Impact: High</p>	<p>Consortium members are exploiting established links with all major EC-recognised initiatives in Europe and globally: NEB, NEBC16, EIT, EIC, EOOSC, ECTP (the European Construction and Technology Platform), CoR, Interreg, Covenant of the Mayors, EU Capitals of Culture, EU Green Capitals, EU Capitals of Innovation, EU Women Innovators, and more.</p> <p>Also, familiarity with and ease of access to the EC's DG CONNECT actors and projects (including close involvement with several "booster" initiatives: Horizon Results Booster, HSbooster.eu) is currently being leveraged to find relevant synergies for DigiNEB's community (e.g. early adopters, the External Advisory Board, thematic working-group members). Participation in key events such as the Barcelona Smart Cities World Expo Congress and the OASC Connected Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities Conference has strengthened pan-European liaisons. Should difficulties arise in the project's next stages, activation of "Task Forces" will be sought, with win-win value propositions. Finally, concertation efforts will be initiated involving key stakeholders.</p>
R2	<p>Lack of engagement from relevant stakeholders</p> <p>Probability: Medium Impact: Medium</p>	<p>With their influential network and pan-European standing, all partners are committed to inherently mitigating the risk of lack of interest from target audiences. During the first months, DigiNEB has created meaningful relations to integrate with the NEB movement, creating a shared communication strategy. Moreover, it has also adopted and implemented a stakeholder management framework designed according to agile principles. Such an approach implies periodically assessing whether its approach is sufficiently inclusive and if the adequate target audience or candidates have shifted (also based on the feedback gathered from interacting with them. In the following months, DigiNEB will reinforce its efforts to attract the most challenging regional stakeholders, including the use of powerful networks and resources of partnering organisations such as strong alliances with the Committee of the Regions and Interreg Europe, all EU communication channels, and those that DigiNEB is synergising within the digital and industrial domains. Proactive use of communication channels by all partner networks will be engaged to inform about the breakthrough uses of technologies and stimulate widespread adoption.</p>
R3	<p>Capacity building and tech transfer difficulties</p> <p>Probability: Low Impact: High</p>	<p>To mitigate risks of insufficient technological knowhow, capacity building effectiveness, and tech transfer bottlenecks, DigiNEB is engaging experienced facilitators (e.g. External Advisory Board, Early Adopters) and using well-established tested methodologies for rapid upskilling with novel technologies, such as those developed by partners TU Delft and ICF.³</p>

³ <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00207543.2021.1989514>

Risk Number	Risk Description	Proposed mitigation measure
		Through its open innovation platform, DigiNEB is fostering inclusive co-creation and exploitation of all NEB results in the wider business community (e.g. architects, designers, construction, creative sector, social actors), dedicated outputs for higher education and VET (see the success stories published so far in the observatory and the digital solutions included in the NEB Digital Toolkit).
R4	Lack of interoperability Probability: Low Impact: Low	Risks associated with the engagement of stakeholders include the establishment or replication of non-interoperable systems. This is not simply a technical problem of data, but a cultural and engagement problem often encountered when working with multidisciplinary communities with digital assets and data sets built within different systems to meet sector-specific standards. This may lead to the exclusion of large sections of potential stakeholders. As a mitigation strategy, the DigiNEB consortium ensures interoperability and ontology harmonisation across domains by sharing know-how from projects such as OntoCommons, a CSA dedicated to the standardisation of data documentation through harmonisation, standardisation and coordination, particularly in the realm of materials and manufacturing. Lessons and strategies from OntoCommons will inform DigiNEB approaches to stakeholder data.
R5	Being perceived as a fringe initiative Probability: Low Impact: Medium	Another risk identified by consortium partners is being seen as fringe or alternative and, therefore, not core to missions. As this is primarily an issue of communication and dissemination, DigiNEB is currently the key digital vehicle for engagement, learning, funding information and mapping overview across all programmes connected with NEB. An example is the promotion of the NEB academy, which will be carried out during the project's duration.
R6	Separation into silos Probability: Low Impact: Medium	The creation or reinforcement of existing silos within the wider digital and NEB communities provides a potential risk where different specialisms or groups within that community do not speak to each other, thereby preventing potential synergies and multidisciplinary possibilities and excluding those who may be made to feel they do not belong. Adopting thematic and mission-oriented approaches (e.g. thematic working groups, local workshops) provides an effective mitigation strategy, allowing for inclusion through interest rather than membership in a particular silo or specialism.
R7	Exclusion due to low digital skills Probability: Low Impact: High	Those with fewer digital skills or lower levels of digital access are at risk of exclusion. Providing introductory training in free, open-source tools that allow full participation will address this significant barrier for some valued community members. Examples include eLearning courses and other sector-specific training initiatives that will be organised according to specific needs. Additionally, using Thematic Working Groups instead of only Technical WGs can help reduce the risk of exclusion.
R8	Lack of evidence of co-creation Probability: Low Impact: Low	As it is vital for the DigiNEB project to align with NEB principles, the website and digital platform format allow effective contributions based on co-creation and not simply the delivery of results. Rather than act as a broadcast platform where the project announces its successes, the DigiNEB website constitutes a dynamic environment, with spaces dedicated to discussions and a user-friendly platform allowing individual contributions through a cost-free subscription. While live moderation can be resource-intensive, it acts as an effective form of online engagement when implemented in conjunction with the activity of Thematic and Technical Working Groups.

Risk Number	Risk Description	Proposed mitigation measure
R9	Lack of incentive for participation Probability: Low Impact: High	In the co-creation of this engagement strategy plan, consortium partners identified a potential lack of incentive for participation. Risk mitigation strategies include using analytics and setting KPIs (either established in advance or developing live as a series of dynamic goals and indicators), developing new feedback mechanisms, and creating and disseminating tangible success stories (see DigiNEB observatory). The use of these measures allows for the demonstration of the effect of co-creation on engagement.

Table 9 – Risks and mitigations

Future risk scenarios that might arise during the execution will be notified to the Technical Project Coordinator (see Grant Agreement Section 2.3.4.1) in order to co-devise a mitigation plan to review the project objectives and detail a contingency plan to minimise the impact of the risk.

10. Conclusion

The DigiNEB project concludes with a legacy of stakeholder engagement, underscored by the successful implementation of a revised strategy that included closer collaboration with all lighthouses, NEB Labs and CSAs through collaborative events and Think and Do Tanks, and an emphasis on persistent rather than ephemeral digital media. The community cohesion evidenced in the final Brussels event, which not only engaged stakeholders but provided rich policy recommendations and community-driven insights, demonstrated the power of collective thinking and action within the NEB ecosystem.

The redesigned DigiNEB website played a enhanced the project’s impact, serving as a central hub for stakeholder engagement and knowledge dissemination. With a more intuitive user interface, improved navigation and features including access to co-creation tools, the updated website provides stakeholders with accessible and enduring resources that extend far beyond the project’s immediate timeline. Crucially, the website was designed with a light touch on personal data, adhering to best practices in data privacy and ensuring ethical standards. This approach not only positions the site as a reliable reference for stakeholders but also reinforces trust and demonstrates a commitment to transparency, inclusivity, and responsible digital innovation.

The publication of the *Regional Innovation Model (RIM) Handbook* further cements DigiNEB’s contribution to shaping regional innovation practice, providing a practical framework for addressing societal challenges through co-creation and interdisciplinary collaboration. The shift to persistent media formats, including the *NEB Concepts* podcast and comprehensive knowledge-sharing video documentation, ensures that the NEB community’s knowledge and methodologies remain accessible to stakeholders.

DigiNEB’s engagement strategy succeeded in expanding, empowering and mobilising a diverse and multidisciplinary community and produced tangible outcomes that support the New European Bauhaus mission at both policy and implementation levels.

Annexe 1: Regional Innovation Model (RIM) Handbook

The RIM Handbook is attached below.

REGIONAL
INNOVATION
MODEL
HANDBOOK

How to use this handbook

This handbook is designed to be used as a companion to city and regional administrators. It includes practical examples of engagement and activities for local actors and changemakers, in collaboration across sectors and disciplines.

It suggests ways to think about grand challenges that address specific needs and characteristics of regional ecosystems, while it offers support instruments and frameworks to leverage local intelligence and create a systemic shift at the global scale.

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TOM MINDERHOUD
TORBEN KLITGAARD
TUULI UTRIAINEN
UWE KIES
AND MANY MORE

REGIONAL INNOVATION MODEL HANDBOOK

"I believe that the New European Bauhaus must become a real movement which involves local and regional authorities and is not just another top-down project. It must be a project for everyone, not just the few. To be successful, this exercise must be socially, culturally and territorially inclusive"*

– Cork City Councillor **Kieran McCarthy**

.....
* i) [CoR-members-adopt-McCarthy's-opinion-on-the-New-European-Bauhaus.aspx](#)
ii) [Kieran McCarthy at the European Week of Regions 2023 and Cities](#)

THE RIM HANDBOOK IS A COLLABORATIVE WORK. THE COMPONENTS OF THIS HANDBOOK – THE FRAMEWORKS, CONCEPTS, GUIDELINES, METHODS, TOOLS AND PRACTICES – ARE THE RESULT OF WORK BY BRILLIANT RESEARCHERS, PRACTITIONERS AND THOUGHT LEADERS FROM THE NEB COMMUNITY. IT HAS NOT BEEN POSSIBLE TO DO JUSTICE TO THE DEPTH OF THAT WORK IN THE SCOPE OF THIS VOLUME, BUT IT IS RECOGNISED, ACKNOWLEDGED AND APPRECIATED.

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There is a 20 year-old Japanese Playstation 2 video game called Katamari Damacy in which the player pushes a ball within a 3D environment. As the ball rolls around and encounters objects, those objects stick to it, and the ball grows in size. Over the course of the game, the ball becomes planetary in scale.

There are parallels between that game and the evolution of this handbook.

1

In the beginning of 2022, the world was still emerging from lockdown and a war had started on European soil. The Omicron variant caused a spike in the number of cases, and in just the first week of 2022, 43,000 people died of Covid-19.¹ The following month Russia's invasion of Ukraine displaced two million people in just a matter of days, leading to what would become the single largest mass movement of human beings in Europe since World War Two.²

These simultaneous crises came with paradigm shifts in society's attitudes to problem-solving. The Covid vaccine was developed faster than any other vaccine against a new disease in history, thanks to unprecedented global collaboration and knowledge sharing between hundreds

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1 Stefanelli et al, 2022. Tracking the progressive spread of the SARS-CoV-2 Omicron variant in Italy, December 2021 to January 2022. [\[Link\]](#)
2 European Central bank: The impact of the influx of Ukrainian refugees on the euro area labour force. [\[Link\]](#)

of governments and organisations³. Shortage of supplies during the pandemic highlighted the need for information alignment across supply networks and collaboration across domains.

The displacement of the Ukrainian population called for dispensing with old narratives that created barriers to integration. In an unprecedented move, the European Commission announced that Ukrainians could apply for jobs where regions had skills shortages. Rather than treat this as a 'refugee crisis', it was recognised as an influx of talent and intelligence.

In regions of Poland that received a high influx of incoming Ukrainian people, urgent action was needed on the ground. To empower incoming skilled workers and their families, their new living conditions had to be more than just a blanket on a factory floor.

Two 'think and do' architects were on the ground immediately during the first days of the war, galvanising volunteers to provide privacy shelters and create dignified living conditions for the incoming populations. Formidable Japanese architect Shigeru Ban aided by Polish architect Hubert Trammer, in collaboration with local governments, engaged armies of volunteer students to construct agile and economical privacy shelters using lightweight and readily available materials, based on the design for a Paper Partition System (PPS)⁴. The architects met as members of "the New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table" (NEB HLRT).

Construction of privacy shelters spread very fast through VAN – the Voluntary Architects' Network – an international initiative created by Shigeru Ban Architects to engage student volunteers with disaster relief projects – and rolled into Slovakia facilitated by Slovakian design expert Mária Beňáčková Rišková, another member of the NEB HLRT.

.....
³ Gavi The Vaccine Alliance, 2020. How did scientists manage to develop safe COVID-19 vaccines in just ten months? [\[Link\]](#)

⁴ Shigeru Ban Architects: Ukraine Refugee Assistance Project, 2022. [\[Link\]](#)

The initiative required all hands on deck with every bit of available intelligence, breaking down of traditional silos, mobilising communities, collaborating, experimenting and sharing knowledge. Schools of architecture at local universities provided student volunteers for the Voluntary Architects' Network. Corex, a Belgian company with a production plant in Poland, stopped their own production to produce the paper tubes free of charge. Ikea donated the materials in Slovakia. A variety of private companies donated the carton.

Photo by Jerzy Latka, Shigeru Ban Architects

The resulting design of the structures treated basic privacy and dignity as human rights, enabling people to continue to contribute to society in their new context rather than reducing them to the disempowering status of 'refugees'. The meaningful and purposeful application of design motivated communities of volunteers to roll privacy shelters fast across the regions.

The key (as will become a recurring theme throughout this handbook) was *learning by doing*. Empowered by a systemic approach to design solutions, the knowledge, skills and competences of the volunteer students expanded and spread as they learned collaboratively, by building together. Within two months, privacy shelters were implemented along the Polish and Slovak borders providing families shelter and human dignity.

The New European Bauhaus, launched just 18 months earlier by the President of the European Commission Ursula von der Leyen, anticipated and laid out the necessary structure and approach for these kinds of interventions. Referred to fondly as 'NEB' by its members, it provided the intellectual, cultural and strategic advantage necessary to address grand challenges at this scale.

"People tend to meet, come together and discuss solutions quickly – this is what also happened with the New European Bauhaus: without this organisation, this would not happen as fast as it should." – **Shigeru Ban**⁵

.....
⁵ Shigeru Ban – Building temporary shelters for Ukrainian refugees with Paper tubes, fabric and safety pins, 2022. Lampoon Magazine. [\[Link\]](#)

2

Collaboration across domains and regional implementations of meaningful solutions on the ground were proving vital for survival. While emergency high-level meetings were taking place about the Ukraine crisis, NEB HLRT member Michela Magas coordinated a meeting uniting for the first time 13 representatives from the European Committee of the Regions (CoR), Cohesion Funds, INTERREG Europe, the Directorate General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (DG GROW), and the NEB HLRT.

The proposal was to engage 100 regions in prototyping meaningful solutions, then scaling the best results by concatenating multiple European funding instruments.

A circular expanding schema showed the NEB regional recovery ignition spark leveraging regional intelligence for the creation of innovative ideas and prototypes, which could be scaled by connecting them with regional and cohesion instruments, and the results channelled further to EU cooperation programmes to create a multiplier effect.

A proposal to scale regional ideas by concatenating European funding instruments by Michela Magas and Thomas Wobben, Director for Legislative Works (Regional Policy, Economic Affairs, Employment and Innovation) at the European Committee of the Regions

A collaboration of this kind was unprecedented. The benefit of joining forces across funding mechanisms was recognised by all present. Complementary actions were being launched by Cohesion Funds in terms of technical assistance to municipalities to incubate NEB projects. Interest from Interreg came at the “resulting ideas and prototypes” stage, since Interreg works very much by reacting to something that is happening on the ground. The CoR noted an enormous amount of energy for NEB uptake that they wished to capture.

It was highlighted that this approach could bring a lot of good ideas into the system. It could provide evidence-based policy that draws on multidisciplinary communities of experts that join forces to generate ideas and inform regional governments with tangible results to base their policies on. It could also build a culture of collaboration, aesthetics, businesses, higher education, research and innovation. The agile initial spark could make everything else perform so much better as a result. In this sense NEB was seen to be not just a programme, but a movement.

Innovative regional solutions, sparked by local responses to grand challenges, could access funding mechanisms to scale their impact. Solutions could emerge from regional ecosystems, combining local knowledge with global expertise and shared best practices. These agile designs and methods could then be rapidly adapted and deployed across regions facing similar challenges. As regional innovations gained momentum through cross-domain collaboration and multiple funding mechanisms, they could grow from local solutions into initiatives with national, cross-European and global impact.

In this vision, regional politicians and communities were positioned to see their ideas gather momentum, grow rapidly in scale and roll out across Europe. The peripheries became the centres of innovation and positive change that scale up to become the methodologies and solutions that address grand challenges at the European and global scale.

As with the necessary shift from specialist and siloed responses to an all-hands, cross-domain approach, regional support moved to support ground-up initiatives that can demonstrate tangible results. Cohesion funds have been designed as instruments to build competence within smaller cities, preparing them for this new approach to regional development. The NEB Lighthouse programme was conceived to demonstrate and implement the power of cross-disciplinary engagement at the neighbourhood level, providing practical examples of how communities can be galvanised into relevant action at a local scale, in a way that can be adopted and amplified across Europe.

Link: [Contribution to the European Week of the Regions 2023: Stimulating Local and Regional New European Bauhaus Grassroots Projects](#)

3

The NEB movement provided a new lens for understanding the place of regions as central engines of urgent and necessary societal, technological, industrial, ecological and cultural innovation.

The regional innovation model of concatenating and aligning funding instruments provides the environment for NEB to scale by adding more elements, people, tools and competencies to its kit of parts, as it continues to grow and become more intertwined, creating greater robustness and resilience.

What follows are experiments, tools, frameworks and guidelines, that have grown as part of this momentum. They offer ways to think about regional ecosystems, methods to integrate fresh perspectives, and the means to develop ideas and approaches that build both local and global value.

Take these examples. Try them. Adapt them. Learn from them. Engage communities and bring together people with diverse experiences, expertise and ideas to learn by doing and *keep the ball rolling*.

Andrew Dubber and Michela Magas

"I don't know why people are frightened of new ideas. I'm frightened of the old ones." — **John Cage**

THE LOCAL
IS THE
FUTURE

Walter Gropius Bauhaus Circle diagram from 1922
 Translation from the original in the Bauhaus Archiv [\[Link\]](#)

Remake/upcycle version of Walter Gropius Bauhaus Circle diagram from 1922 for New European Bauhaus 2023 by Jan Åman and Adam Davies (13.03.2023)

THE LOCAL IS THE FUTURE

This handbook began life within the Horizon Europe-funded digiNEB project with an update of the Walter Gropius Bauhaus Circle diagram from 1922. The update, by Jan Åman and Adam Davies, introduced the Ecosystemic Principle – addressing food systems, infrastructure and mobility, affordable housing, integration of digital and knowledge systems, innovation and new business, habitat and public space, culture, governance and democracy.

That prototype had an organising principle at its heart: **The Local Is The Future.**

Of course, knowledge and the development of strategies do not emerge or grow in a vacuum, even given the very fertile ground of the initial NEB movement. The prototype had its roots in other initiatives, including the Swedish **Duved project**, which experimented with deeply rooted organisational systems such as legal frameworks and norms that hinder societal development.

Duved is a small town of around 1000 inhabitants on the Western side of central Sweden, close to the ski resort of Åre. It's just 45 minutes from the border with Norway and just over an hour to the nearest airport. It has a hotel, a church, a school, some shops, a small ski slope of its own – and a couple of very good restaurants, a legacy from the town's close proximity to the site of the legendary Fäviken, a unique restaurant concept that was built by leveraging the local ecosystem in an unusually remote setting. It was listed among the top 10 restaurants globally in 2013 and received two Michelin stars in 2016⁶.

In 2018, a diverse group including Jan Åman, top chefs, regional government representatives, architects and citizens began an experiment to develop Duved based on self-sufficiency and circularity⁷. The aim was to establish an innovation engine that reflects communities as role models for sustainability at the local scale.

In 2022, as part of the NEB Sweden "Visions in the North" initiative, the Duved model was supported to scale into the **Norrlands Model**⁸ for city neighbourhoods, thanks to the first-ever collaboration between five governmental agencies. These included Formas, the Swedish government research council for sustainable development; the Swedish Innovation Agency Vinnova; Energimyndigheten, the Swedish Energy Agency responsible for supporting sustainable energy use and transition to a fossil-free economy; Boverket, the national board of housing, building and planning; and ArkDes, the Swedish Centre for Architecture and Design.

The model developed for the Duved project, and the scaled model for city neighbourhoods developed as part of a national NEB initiative, suggested that collaboratively-developed and locally-situated innovation models could be scaled and adapted for a variety of different regional ecosystems. With that in mind, Åman and Davies set to embed the updated Gropius diagram into a broader framework.

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⁶ Magic out of mould: inside the world's wildest restaurant, 2016. The Guardian. [\[Link\]](#)

⁷ The Duved Model [\[Link\]](#)

⁸ The Norrlands Model [\[Link\]](#)

Michela Magas and Jan Åman in Duved, February 2023

The **Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook**⁹ (PFAEH) provides a framework for thinking about ways to engage in creating locally-situated innovation that can be scaled and adapted across other regional ecosystems. It is intended for anyone interested in societal development and sustainability, including policymakers, urban planners, architects, thinkers, designers, and community members who want to make a tangible and meaningful difference to the place where they live and for their communities. It represents more than just a documentation of success stories – it extrapolates key lessons, and offers a fresh interpretation of original Bauhaus principles, recontextualised for contemporary challenges through the lens of recent experiences.

9 Åman and Davies, 2023. Prototype of an Ecosystemic Handbook

"It is not a set of instructions to be followed step by step. On the contrary."

With contributions and feedback by regional government officials involved in the related projects, PFAEH formulates and presents strategies for regional ecosystems that allow for each location's unique characteristics to be considered. While it acknowledges a high-level commonality of ambition and purpose (zero waste, affordable housing, accessible transport and so on), it assumes and accommodates differences at the ground level. It provides a shared starting point for place-based learning and community engagement and empowers local public servants, policy officers and community organisers to facilitate bottom-up action towards smarter societies and more sustainable local environments.

"A shift from silos to connectivity"

Focusing on the wider application of the core lessons learned, PFAEH is both a conceptual and practical guide to innovating in the context of regional societal development. It emphasises the need for interconnected local systems to tackle climate change, democratic processes, and local resilience through shared knowledge, regenerative practices, and cross-disciplinary dialogue. Within regional and city government structures it highlights the importance of connecting different departments that are more accustomed to functioning separately.

The updated approach to the Gropius circle provides a flexible framework for navigating the interconnected layers as a starting point for creating prototypes, supporting action and inspiring a systemic shift towards more sustainable, resilient, and participatory local and global practices. By leveraging circular economy and zero-waste principles, the model seeks to generate synergies supporting sustainable growth, resilience, and innovation across food systems, housing, and public spaces.

"A campus without a university"

"The whole knowledge system is in a sort of convergence where everything is changing rapidly. And working with Duved, we've created something that we call "Campus Without University." It's interdisciplinary, transgenerational, and it takes the rural possibilities of lower costs, the possibility of prototyping, the possibility of actually testing things in a new way, and of having different teams to work with. And actually, that attracted the universities to come"¹⁰.

PFAEH can be deployed as a blueprint for community-driven societal transformation tailored to the specific challenges and opportunities of each unique context.

Link: <https://bit.ly/prototype-handbook>

The Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook was launched at a public event entitled "The Local is the Future" hosted by the Faculty of Architecture at Umeå University on 9th February 2024. The event was introduced by Cornelia Redeker, Head Of Architecture, University of Umeå, and included Helene Hellmark-Knutsson, Governor of Västerbotten County and former Swedish Minister of Education; Jan Åman, author of the Norrlands Model and PFAEH; Adam Davies, Co-Founder of sustainable design agency Tÿ Syml and co-author of PFAEH; Sara Thor, Lecturer at Umeå School of Architecture; Michela Magas, Member of the NEB HLRT; and Magnus Myrenberg, Partner at Aalto Capital.

"Some may think the handbook is simplifying things. Some may think it is too abstract. So then, go ahead and make another version. That is the whole point. This is only a starting point. Not the end."

– **Åman and Davies**

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10 Jan Åman, Ecosystem Living panel, NEB Day, Aveiro Tech Week, 13 October 2022

ECOSYSTEM LIVING

The process of developing frameworks for regional innovation ecosystems requires a change to our mental models: a shift towards ecosystemic perspectives.

Ecosystem Living moves beyond the concept of urban planning and its focus on the management of infrastructures and complexities of urban environments, to consider broader alignment with the conditions that affect cohabitation.

The concept of Ecosystem Living inspired a week of experimentation with 50 participants from 23 countries in the Ria de Aveiro, one of the most biodiverse areas of wetland in Europe¹¹. During the week, a day dedicated to NEB gathered thinkers to discuss ecosystemic approaches. Using the device of a manifesto, several shifts towards ecosystemic perspectives were identified. These shifts reveal the need to redefine roles, re-evaluate how we converge around topics, re-consider how we build knowledge, and rethink the design of our environments.

MANIFESTO FOR ECOSYSTEM LIVING

LINEAR TO MULTIDIMENSIONAL

A shift from linear thinking to a multidimensional, pluralistic approach, that aggregates many domains and perspectives, and rapidly builds new knowledge.

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 11 MTF Labs Aveiro 2022: Ecosystem Living. [\[Link\]](#)

Experimentation in situ at the Ria de Aveiro. ©MTF Labs 2022.

TOP-DOWN TO INTERPLAY

By shifting from top-down directives to an interplay between bottom-up and top-down actions, the evidence from the ground can be gathered at high level, where the design of new instruments can help stimulate further positive action on the ground.

SMALL-SCALE TO MISSION-DRIVEN

Shifting from small-scale experiments to a view high above ground captures the impact of the small interventions on the whole ecosystem and stimulates mission-driven approaches.

CENTRE TO PERIPHERY

Most regions may be geographically peripheral, but they are at the forefront of climate change facing challenges such as sea level rise and biodiversity losses. These threats are experienced in an immediate, lived and local way by communities who are central to addressing our most pressing environmental concerns. The periphery becomes the centre – where real solutions emerge and transformation begins.

ECOSYSTEMIC DEMOCRACY

The active role of the civil servant

Dan Hill encourages local policymakers to “think like gardeners”¹². Gardeners create fertile conditions for growth but allow the plants to evolve organically. He recommends that policymakers focus on setting the stage for innovation by establishing clear goals and providing resources, but not try to predetermine the specific outcomes. Instead, they should nurture, support and tend them – enabling them to grow and take root. Gardeners understand the importance of biodiversity for a healthy and resilient ecosystem. Hill advocates for a similar approach to innovation, encouraging policymakers to engage with a diverse range of stakeholders, ideas, and solutions.

At the time the Duved model was being scaled for implementation in a neighbourhood in the city of Umeå to become the Norrlands Model, the Governor of Västerbotten County, Helene Hellmark-Knutsson wrote:

I believe that this will become the new, sustainable way of planning both villages and cities. Everyone wants to invent their own model and many are uncomfortable learning and being inspired by others. That is the biggest obstacle. And also that we in Sweden think we are so good at collaborating and having a dialogue with the citizens. But we never let this really affect us. In other words, when decisions are made and money is managed, it is always from an expert and top-down perspective. Especially in the cities. We find it difficult to define and identify which residents should have influence in a city or district, for example. And cities are much more complex with stronger economic and political interests that do not

.....
12 Dan Hill, Designing Missions, Vinnova – Swedish Innovation Agency 2022.

want to give up power. Therefore, today, the village is a better innovation platform than the city. But I think we must dare to do this in the cities as well. And Umeå could be first! But it makes demands on civil servants and politicians.

This demands a rethink of the role of the civil servant:

I think this means that many municipal and state officials have to relearn and learn new things. And get a new role. See themselves as enabling instead of controlling. And see your expertise as a piece of the puzzle that should contribute to the whole, not act as a culvert or stopping block¹³.

ECOSYSTEMIC CONVERGENCE

Working across domains / radical inclusion

The new approach to knowledge creation is an “ecosystemic convergence” based on the principle of radical inclusion. Instead of defining contributors by categories or areas of expertise, the starting question is “Where do we converge?”

The main issue we encounter when we work with municipalities is that there's a limited amount of money in the budget and an atmosphere of competition in those organisations, where suddenly the Transportation Department has to prove that they are more important than the Housing Department, more important than the Energy Department... because they feel they're competing for finite resources. The reality is that all these things are inherently interconnected

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13 Helene Hellmark-Knutsson, in *The future is born in a village*, Arkitektur, nr.7, 2022.

– someone's waste is someone else's energy, which then has to do with mobility and housing. Logically, all these things have to be considered as one organism – one ecosystem. The key to success is for us to align incentives and create a setting where we all start to work towards the same goal¹⁴.

Bringing domains together into a space of convergence reveals overlaps and synergies. The diversity of perspectives can be channeled into hands-on low-level prototyping of potential solutions:

Get to the prototypes as quickly as possible. This is where the real learning happens, even via the 'half-step' forward. Prototypes flip the focus from abstract analysis towards real world synthesis, putting 'the room in the system'¹⁵.

Translating thought into practice creates a new kind of evidence for policy makers:

To me, what that does is creates the sort of evidence for policy makers that's not based on statistics anymore. It's about tangible results on the ground¹⁶.

ECOSYSTEMIC KNOWLEDGE

Collaborative methods for knowledge creation

Duved's "campus without university" relied on the convergence of different domains but also on intergenerational learning: collaboration and dialogue between generations to retrieve endangered ecosystemic understanding.

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¹⁴ Jan Bunge, Ecosystem Living panel, NEB Day, Aveiro Tech Week, 13 October 2022

¹⁵ Dan Hill, Designing Missions, Vinnova – Swedish Innovation Agency 2022.

¹⁶ Michela Magas, Ecosystem Living panel, NEB Day, Aveiro Tech Week, 13 October 2022

In Venice, knowledge about the lagoon – vital for the city's sustainability and cultural preservation – was at risk of being lost between one generation and another. TBA21 implemented educational programmes that engaged young people in rediscovering local species, collaborating with chefs on traditional recipes, reinforcing intergenerational exchange and cultural resilience.

One thing we realised when we arrived in Venice, is that that knowledge of the lagoon was slowly going to be wasted because people in Venice, they're not passing this on. This knowledge through intergenerational exchanges, and this is why we started the massive educational programme with kids. The food programme, rediscovering the food, the indigenous species from the lagoon, and working with chefs to cook this food and working with kids to study the lagoon, and we were also doing a programme of walks in the lagoon with Venetians. Because to tackle these problems that we've been mentioning, you need to have that knowledge¹⁷.

Aside from passing knowledge on, bringing together different disciplines opens up new ways of generating new knowledge:

Ocean literacy is so important that when we got to Venice and we opened Ocean Space, we realised that there weren't sign languages about the oceans. So together with artists and deaf communities, we created new sign languages, because we realised that a big chunk of population was excluded by a massive problem or opportunity, which is knowledge about the seas. And we got there because of convergence, because of inclusion, and because of the willingness to bring together different disciplines and different communities around the specific focus or a specific mission¹⁸.

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¹⁷ Marco Zappalorto, Ecosystem Living panel, NEB Day, Aveiro Tech Week, 13 October 2022

¹⁸ ibid

ECOSYSTEMIC ENVIRONMENTS

Beyond-human quality of living

Our understanding of the ecosystem is expanding beyond the traditional confines of human-centric planning and habitation. The focus shifts to the interconnectedness of living systems, encompassing both human and non-human actors. This offers us a broader, more integrated view of cohabitation that values the complex interplay between species, habitats and ecological cycles. It challenges our assumptions about resource use, sustainability, and what we mean when we say "we":

We consider human beings and their activities to be part of nature and not separate from it, and so true ecosystem living is about harmony, alignment and balance, and finding an entire value network within a holistic cohabitation. This balance must synthesise and integrate artistic practice, scientific research, traditional craft professions and local cultural practices¹⁹.

MANIFESTO FOR ECOSYSTEM LIVING was developed by Jan Åman, Jan Bunge, Marco Zappalorto and Michela Magas during MTF Labs Aveiro 2022.

Link: [NEB Day @Aveiro Tech Week: Manifesto for Ecosystem Living](#)

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 19 Michela Magas, Concept of Ecosystem Living, MTF Labs Aveiro 2022. [Link]

DESIRE

AN IRRESISTIBLE

CIRCULAR SOCIETY

Garden Caretaker, Herlev (DK). Photo: Hanne Kokkegaard, DTU Compute

From October 2022 to November 2024, **Desire** worked with communities across Europe, making European citizens central to their work. The insights they gathered are not just research outcomes but are a rallying call for a renewed urban policy agenda.

Cities are more than just collections of buildings; they are ecosystems where humans and non-humans cohabit, creating spaces crucial for thriving communities. The built environment is a powerful leverage point to reimagine our collective future. To envision a sustainable transition amidst today's overlapping crises, it is necessary to go beyond established norms. We need creative, interdisciplinary approaches that invite everyone to participate. This means integrating the social, economic, and ecological dimensions that form the backbone of a circular and regenerative urban future. It means making the circular and regenerative choices the irresistible choices.

Real, lasting transformation comes from place-based change, where collaboration among designers, artists, architects, municipalities, and local communities can play an important role.

Desire is about three things:

Creating Sustainable Futures Through Deep Engagement

Designing Urban Spaces for Trust and Ownership

Innovation Through Art, Design, and Participation

The Desire project created and collected a wide range of invaluable tools for ecosystemic regional innovation, local development and community engagement. These range from simple prompts for workshops, templates and canvases, workshop formats, future visioning exercises and engaging pen-and-paper interventions to digital mobile tools and interactive datascares to map local community sentiment and concerns.

Garden Careta Wildemanbuurt, Amsterdam (NL). Photo: The Beach and Samenwonen–Samenleven (SW–SL)

The Transformation Guide

Desire has developed a series of six transformation themes with guidance on implementing them. These are core principles and guidance for people and organisations that want to lead in pushing for circularity in transforming spaces and places in their region in an irresistible manner. It focuses on creating ambitious approaches to transformation in order to influence and inspire radical change.

The transformation themes are:

Build and Maintain Trust

Establish and Nurture Ownership

Prioritise Empathy and Deep Care with the Place

Raise and Sustain Ambitions

Embrace and Enable Inclusion

Monitor and Learn Continuously

Each theme is explored and explained with practical steps, considerations, and examples that allow you to provide a context for ecosystemic innovation with a diverse community of stakeholders. These themes and their respective guides offer a practical starting point for regional policymakers wishing to engage with and work with local communities, laying the foundations for the long-term relationship-building necessary to create valuable long-term associations.

Link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularsociety.eu/learn>

Monitoring Assessment and Learning Tools

Photo: Hanne Kokkegaard, DTU Compute

The Monitoring Assessment and Learning Tools include logbooks for activity planning and reflection, outcome mapping workshops for capturing, tracking and supporting project progress, and peer-to-peer learning templates to foster knowledge exchange. These tools are designed to establish a structured, collaborative learning environment. The practical tools include PowerPoint templates for the peer-to-peer sessions and an Excel spreadsheet for the activity record. These tools are particularly helpful in supporting new regional innovation projects to get underway, collecting empirical data and reflecting upon the learning with a series of simple tools already prepared to help manage the process.

Link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/the-monitoring-assessment-and-learning-tools>

Beauty for All

Beauty for All model, MIND, Milan (IT). Credit: PlusValue and Politicnico di Milano, Design Department.

Beauty for All is a tool designed to help you guide and evaluate the transformation of public spaces, with a focus on quality of lived experience, inclusiveness, and sustainability. Through co-creation, defining context-specific indicators, and tracking progress using both qualitative and quantitative metrics, it supports decision-makers, funders, and urban planners in shaping and monitoring meaningful changes in urban spaces, either in permanent builds or temporary contexts. It can be used broadly or to direct attention towards more specific goals and outputs – e.g. supporting stakeholders and decision-makers in where to put their focus.

Link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/the-beauty-for-all-model>

Think it, Sketch it, Show it!

Gadehavegaard, Høje-Taastrup (DK). Credit: GXN

This is a 6-step design toolkit for co-designing with young people in your region. Involving young people in a design workshop is a strategic approach to building valuable insights and design principles that can contribute to the creation of future-proof solutions. Co-designing with young people offers them a space to express their needs, explore their ideas, and have them translated into engaging design projects and visuals. The process has been tested and validated with students aged 12–17, but the toolkit is designed for a much broader age group. The toolkit is a comprehensive PDF guide that provides conceptual frameworks, activities, templates and case study examples.

Link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularsociety.eu/think-it-sketch-it-show-it>

Listening to Places

Street event, Kalundborg (DK). Photo: Benjamin Hesselholdt.

Listening to Places is an experiential activity that engages participants as part of site visits and discussions to help them understand and express their sensory experiences and aspirations. The ideas and observations generated from the exercise go beyond the visual to capture essential sensory aspects that can help guide a new idea or vision for a place, and it is essential to integrate these insights into the strategic planning of a regional innovation project.

Link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularsociety.eu/listening-to-places>

The Tender Wheel

Tender wheel

The model is dynamic, which means that each circle represents different levels in the governing elements of this tender. The model is rotatable and it is thus possible to move all the elements of the model

NEB – The Fundamental Values of the New European Bauhaus

- Sustainable
- Inclusive
- Aesthetics

Domea's Selected Principles

- Circularity
- Biodiversity
- Inclusion

Young people's principles for the green area

- Manifesto
- Developed on the basis of their investigation
- Developed on the basis of prototypes

Prototypes

- 13 prototypes for desirable future
- All prototypes are based on the above elements

Credit: AGORA and Domea.dk

The Tender Wheel helps guide the development of a tender programme. It is used to include those who are not usually involved, such as children or other users of the site. There are four layers of the Tender wheel:

The NEB base: Sustainability, Inclusion and Aesthetics.

Selected principles: choose three Principles that you want to focus on for your own site-specific prototypes.

Customised principles: the principles that you develop for your site-specific context, customised to your setting and for your needs.

Prototypes: prototypes of the places, events, and objects that the other layers have inspired and guided toward.

Outdoor Space Mapping

Ziepju street, Riga (LV). Photo: Benjamin Hesselholdt

This tool is designed to include citizens in creating their desired transformation of a place. It is a simple yet effective approach that helps them to visualise their needs and creates a tangible way to integrate their perspectives into the ongoing stages of regional development. The toolkit includes simple cut-out images to place on a large scale print from a satellite mapping service such as Google Maps, allowing for discussions and negotiations with regard to placement of amenities and imagined site use.

Link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularsociety.eu/outdoor-space-mapping>

Co-creation Workshops and Hackathons

Gadehavegaard, Høje-Taastrup (DK). Photo: Benjamin Hesselholdt

Desire recommends a range of hands-on, collaborative co-creation workshops as a methodology to work with long-term transformations that rely on participatory, multi-level, and multi-disciplinary processes. Co-creation workshop is an umbrella term for a range of different interventions, ranging from 20 minutes to several days of activity. The workshops follow the logic that including various perspectives will invariably lead to better and more innovative solutions. A strong element of Learning by Doing underpins the Co-Creation Workshops, and they aim to generate concrete solutions, prototypes or products that can be implemented in practice. The methodology ensures results and designs that could not have been possible without collaboration. It helps build relationships and makes every workshop participant feel heard and seen in the design.

Link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularsociety.eu/co-creation-workshops>

Multispecies Postcards

Photo: NXT

This tool is designed as a simple writing and imagination exercise to help participants see the world from the perspective of another species. A postcard is written to a fellow workshop participant from the viewpoint of a non-human species sharing the local, regional ecosystem. The template is intended to be used in a larger workshop or within a smaller team. Each participant is given a blank postcard with a specific species assigned to them. In silence, everyone writes their postcard. The additional step of actually sending the postcard is recommended. The organiser ensures that everyone receives a postcard written by someone else. Both writing and receiving the postcard gives participants pause to consider the ways in which they share their environment with other living beings, and how those non-human species might be affected by their actions and interventions.

Link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularsociety.eu/species-postcards>

1:1 Mobile Interventions

Kalundborg (DK). Photo: Benjamin Hesselholdt

This tool is a simple instruction to make long-term processes both tangible and visible before they are implemented. It refers to creating physical 'sketches' as temporary installations in the space you are planning to transform. In other words, if you plan to build something in a location, place something there of that same size to get a sense of its impact and scale. The key is to make something tactile and visible through very simple means. The Desire project recommends that you "work with what you got".

Link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/11-mobile-interventions>

The Value Proposition Canvas

Cascina Falchera, Turin (IT). Photo: Marzia Allietta

The Value Proposition Canvas is a template for co-creating a value proposition for citizens, residents, or other site users of the place you are transforming. Originally created as a service design tool to help commercial providers meet their customers needs and pain points, the application of the canvas in a regional development and innovation context helps stakeholders and user communities think through their current and potential relationship with the site under development. At the urban farm Cascina Falchera in the Turin area, Desire lighthouse partners worked with artist Rooy Charlie Lana to reimagine the site as a living lab. They used the Value Proposition Canvas to engage the community and neighbourhood by listening and collecting ideas and proposals from various users. Through this methodology, they identified the need to improve internal procedures, particularly regarding lifelong learning for internal staff.

Link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/value-proposition-canvas>

Stakeholder Mapping

Photo: BLOXHUB

Stakeholder mapping is always an essential first step in any regional or city development. It helps give an overview of the relevant actors and ecosystems, ensuring the inclusion and representation needed for your project to succeed. However, the Desire Lighthouse focused on two innovative approaches that go beyond traditional stakeholder listing and mapping, both of which are provided as templates and guides available from the Danish Design Centre, linked from the Desire website. Ecosystem Mapping focuses on the motivations, resources and capabilities that will become valuable for the overall ecosystem, while Value System Mapping concerns the exchange of value within the new development, and the kinds of value they are exchanging.

Link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularsociety.eu/stakeholder-mapping>

How to be an Irresistible City Maker

Photo: Hanne Kokkegaard, DTU Compute

The 'How to be an Irresistible City Maker' tool is a template for an interactive and engaging design sprint that leads participants through the creation of concrete images of irresistible circular cities of the future. Participants imagine and develop scenarios to reflect on and discuss what needs to be considered when developing thriving and inclusive future cities. The tool helps participants reflect on critical questions such as the role they can play in the creation of that vision, and who else is needed to get on board to help design the irresistible circular city. The tool sparks imagination by creating alternative future scenarios, and gains insights into the roles, actors, and partnerships necessary to achieve that Desired future. It helps highlight what you should continue to do and what you should start doing differently tomorrow.

Link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularsociety.eu/how-to-be-an-irresistible-city-maker>

The Closing Circle Ritual

Photo: Hanne Kokkegaard, DTU Compute

Endings are as important as beginnings. As a project or development process comes to a conclusion, the Closing Circle Ritual allows groups to celebrate what they have achieved together throughout a project or transformation process. It marks a significant milestone, taking the time to look back with appreciation for the group and the work accomplished. The tool is a series of prompts and questions that guide participants through a reflective process. It is a simple act that embeds the learning and takeaways as well as the positive experience of the joint accomplishment.

Link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularsociety.eu/the-closing-circle-ritual>

Our Walk App

Photo: Hanne Kokkegaard, DTU Compute

Our Walk App is a tool for participatory research about a place or a city under transformation. Participants from the local community are encouraged to explore the local neighbourhood and engage in data collection, idea generation and the co-design of their locality. They join the app in a designated user group and are asked to complete one or more photo tasks. They take pictures of places and situations worth capturing or that are meaningful to them, in response to a specific task. To complete the task, they are asked to "annotate" the photo. A 'datascape' – an interactive map representing the data collected – displays all walks and photos taken with their exact geolocation. This aids decision-makers, architects, urban designers and planners to interactively explore the thoughts and responses of residents and so supports the creation of urban spaces where citizens feel seen, heard and listened to.

Link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularsociety.eu/our-walk-app>

EYES

HEARTS

HANDS

URBAN REVOLUTION

Eyes Hearts Hands – Urban Revolution focused on the transformation of cities while considering both the local heritage and the social context. To do this, it worked across seven diverse European cities with different backgrounds, cultures and local conditions. The project bridged the worlds of art, culture, and education with science and technology and contributed to the EU Missions aligned with NEB to tackle major challenges in health, climate, and the environment through closer engagement with citizens and harnessing the power of research and innovation.

The project considered that three things were necessary to make change happen:

Eyes: Aesthetically viable and socially accepted urban transformation

Hearts: Inclusive and socially fair involvement of local communities

Hands: Concrete engagement actions for full sustainability

Eyes Hearts Hands has supported cities with innovative co-design and co-investment practices that bring together local business and education communities as well as entrepreneurs, social enterprises and city residents. The aim was to design and apply solutions to grand challenges such as environmental and climate adaptation, social segregation, and reconversion of existing or heritage infrastructure – and to make cities sustainable and resilient for the long haul.

As part of that initiative, Eyes Hearts Hands examined 300 case studies and selected 30 best practices for dissemination. The case studies were evaluated through the lenses of 5 levels of sustainability (from conventional to regenerative), 3 ambition levels of NEB values, and the level of match or applicability for the seven Lighthouse cities in the project. Case studies were further categorised by the scale at which they are applied: City, Neighbourhood, Street, Building, or System.

A series of methodologies for co-creation were assembled, focusing specifically on the engagement of citizens and residents. Many of these tools are already very familiar to policymakers and make up much of the existing facilitation playbook for local governments. However, each of these can be implemented in a way that supports a NEB approach to ecosystemic regional innovation, and are included in the following pages to ensure that no ideas or strategies that may be useful are overlooked or discarded.

Link: <https://eyesheartshands.eu/>

City

01: Sønderborg – SmartEnCity, Sønderborg, Denmark – A pioneering zero-carbon community project focused on integrating energy-efficient solutions, renewable energy systems, and sustainable urban practices to reduce emissions and create a replicable urban model. <https://smartencity.eu/>

02: Les Contrats des Quartiers Durables, Brussels, Belgium – An urban regeneration initiative fostering public-private partnerships to revitalise neighbourhoods, improve infrastructure, and empower local communities with sustainable living solutions. <https://www.brussels.be/sustainable-neighbourhood-contracts>

03: E-on Waste Heat Recovery, Berlin, Germany – A project transforming industrial waste heat into a resource for urban energy systems, contributing to sustainable city development and reduced carbon emissions. <https://www.eon.com/en/business-customers/success-stories/buerogebaeude-berlin.html>

04: The Rivers of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria – An initiative reconnecting urban landscapes with natural waterways, enhancing biodiversity and creating vibrant public spaces

for recreation and ecological awareness. <https://bigsee.eu/rivers-of-sofia/>

05: Amsterdam Rainproof, Amsterdam, Netherlands – A city-wide programme promoting climate adaptation through innovative designs to manage rainfall and prevent flooding in urban areas. <https://www.rainproof.nl/>

Neighbourhood

06: Replicate, San Sebastián, Spain – A smart city pilot implementing energy-efficient technologies, sustainable mobility systems, and smart infrastructures to enhance urban resilience and quality of life. <https://replicate-project.eu/>

07: Enghave Park, Copenhagen, Denmark – A multi-functional urban park designed to handle extreme rainfall while providing a recreational space that contributes to the city's climate resilience strategy. <https://www.tredjenatur.dk/en/portfolio/enghaveparken-climate-park/>

08: Jardin Joyeux, Lyon, France – A grassroots urban transformation turning asphalted car parks into green spaces, improving ecological balance and fostering community connections. <https://landezine.com/jardin-des-joyeux-by-wagon-landscaping/>

09: Gardens of the Future, Nicosia, Cyprus – A forward-thinking urban project developing shared green spaces to support sustainable food ecosystems and enhance community-driven urban living. <https://gardensofthefuture.com/>

Street

10: Health Street, London, United Kingdom – A street redesign initiative prioritising healthy urban living by creating accessible, active, and community-centred environments. <https://heatherwick.com/studio/news/healthstreet/>

11: Green Shades, Seville, Spain – A project employing innovative shading systems to manage urban microclimates and improve thermal comfort on streets and in public spaces. <https://www.singulargreen.com/en/green-shades/>

12: The 200-Foot Garden, Detroit, United States – A community-led transformation of neglected urban land into productive green spaces, encouraging local engagement and sustainable practices. (in Hes, D. and du Plessis, C. (2015) *Designing for Hope: Pathways to Regenerative Sustainability*, 1st ed. London: Routledge.)

Building

13: Marion Fire Station, Marion, United States – A regenerative architectural project demonstrating sustainable design principles and fostering environmental awareness within the community. <https://www.archdaily.com/1005665/marion-fire-station-no-1-opn-architects>

14: Hitchcock Center for the Environment, Amherst, United States – A cutting-edge environmental education facility showcasing regenerative design and sustainable resource use. <https://hitchcockcenter.org/>

15: COOKfox Studio, New York, United States – An office environment designed with biophilic principles, integrating nature into the workspace to enhance well-being and productivity. <https://cookfox.com/>

16: De Verwondering, Almere, Netherlands – A school designed to promote a deep connection to nature, utilising biophilic design to create inspiring learning environments. <https://verwondering-almere.nl/over-de-verwondering/>

17. Maggie's, Leeds, United Kingdom – A free cancer care drop-in centre housed in a building designed by leading

architects to create an uplifting, sustainable environment. <https://www.maggies.org/our-centres/maggies-yorkshire/>

18: Gleis 21, Vienna, Austria – A co-housing development blending sustainable architecture with a focus on communal living and shared resources. <https://gleis21.wien/>

Systems

19: SolarLeaf – Algae Bio-Reactive Façade – An innovative façade system utilising algae cultivation to generate bioenergy and improve building sustainability. <https://www.arup.com/projects/solarleaf/>

20: Made of Air – Carbon Super Block – A carbon-negative building material designed to sequester atmospheric CO₂ while offering high-performance construction solutions. <https://www.madeofair.com/>

21: CO-mida Vertical Garden – A vertical garden system promoting urban greening and local food production in densely built environments. <https://iaac.net/project/co-mida-en/>

22: Xifré's Rooftop: "Floating" Wild Garden – A rooftop garden project transforming urban spaces into ecological

havens for biodiversity and community use. https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/get-inspired/inspiring-projects-and-ideas/xifres-rooftop-floating-wild-garden_en

23: ERDEN PURE Walls – A sustainable wall system made from natural materials, promoting energy efficiency and ecological design. https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/get-inspired/inspiring-projects-and-ideas/erden-pure-walls_en

24: NORDIC LAM GLULAM – Engineered timber systems offering sustainable, high-performance structural solutions for modern construction. <https://www.nordic.ca/en/products/nordic-lam-glued-laminated-timber-glulam>

25: Bullitt Center, Seattle, United States – A model for net-zero energy buildings featuring advanced systems for electricity generation, water recycling, and energy efficiency. <https://bullittcenter.org/>

26: Vivihouse – A modular construction system focused on affordability, sustainability, and adaptability for urban housing needs. <https://www.vivihouse.cc/>

27: Clayworks – Sustainable interior finishes made from natural materials, enhancing thermal and acoustic performance while being environmentally friendly. <https://clay-works.com/>

28: Bertschi Living Building Science Wing, Seattle, United States – A learning facility designed to meet Living Building Challenge standards, incorporating innovative water and energy systems. <https://www.bertschi.org/about-us/our-campus/living-building-science-wing>

29: The Phenix Sustainable Design Lab – A laboratory showcasing cutting-edge sustainable systems for heating, cooling, and ventilation in buildings. <https://lemay.com/projects/the-phenix/>

30: Fabbrica dell'aria / Air Factory – An air purification system integrated into architectural spaces, improving indoor air quality through innovative design. <https://www.pnat.net/fabbrica-dellaria/>

Photo: EHHUR

Co-creation methodologies

Information Hotline: A communication tool for large projects that provides phone-based access to project information, allowing stakeholders to receive updates, leave comments, and ask questions. While offering an inexpensive and consistent method of information dissemination, it requires broad advertising and a commitment to timely responses.

Community Day: A celebratory gathering designed to foster community engagement through workshops, cultural activities, and informational booths. By creating a welcoming and inclusive environment, Community Days encourage broad participation, promote transparency, and generate valuable feedback from diverse attendees.

Open House: An informal platform where stakeholders can engage with project materials, ask questions, and provide feedback in an accessible public venue. Using visual aids like posters and maps, Open Houses create a non-intimidating environment that encourages community participation and builds trust through direct engagement.

Town Hall: A structured meeting facilitating direct dialogue between project leaders and community members, typically involving presentations and open forums for expressing opinions and concerns. Town Halls promote transparency, address community issues, and build consensus by ensuring all voices are heard.

Community Walkshop: An immersive, hands-on method combining guided tours with interactive workshops, enabling stakeholders to explore neighborhoods, identify challenges, and collaboratively propose solutions. Walkshops are particularly effective for addressing hyperlocal issues by providing participants a tangible sense of place and context.

Public Consultation: A formal process for soliciting community input on proposed plans, policies, or projects through public meetings, written submissions, and surveys. This method ensures projects align with community needs by incorporating diverse perspectives and identifying potential concerns early in the decision-making process.

Buzz Groups: Small, focused discussion groups formed during larger meetings to tackle specific topics or generate solutions. By dividing participants into smaller clusters and then reconvening to share insights, Buzz Groups foster inclusivity, collaboration, and ensure diverse perspectives are heard.

Public Hearing: A formal event similar to Town Halls where stakeholders present views on specific projects, policies, or plans. These hearings typically include a structured agenda with project presentations followed by an open forum, underscoring transparency and allowing community members to directly influence project outcomes.

Public Workshop: Interactive sessions where stakeholders actively engage in hands-on activities to co-create or refine project solutions. Designed to foster creativity and leverage collective knowledge, these workshops are particularly valuable during design or planning phases to encourage innovative thinking and community ownership.

Citizen Advisory Group: A team of community representatives providing ongoing input throughout a project's lifecycle. By selecting members that reflect community diversity, these groups act as a bridge between the project team and wider community, offering feedback and advocating for stakeholder interests.

Online Jam: Digital brainstorming sessions allowing stakeholders to collaborate asynchronously or in real-time using virtual platforms. Particularly effective for large-scale projects or engaging geographically dispersed participants, Online Jams enable idea generation and problem-solving without physical meeting constraints.

Innovation Challenge: Competitive events designed to crowdsource creative solutions to project-related problems. By inviting participants to propose ideas and prototypes with potential incentives, these challenges generate fresh perspectives and engage diverse stakeholders in innovative problem-solving.

Forum Theatre: An interactive method using theatrical performances to explore social issues and encourage collaborative problem-solving. By combining emotional and intellectual engagement, Forum Theatre creates a safe space for stakeholders to express ideas and collectively envision solutions.

Consensus Workshop: Structured sessions guiding diverse stakeholders toward shared agreement on specific issues. Through facilitated brainstorming, discussion, and prioritisation, these workshops synthesise individual ideas into collective decisions, fostering stakeholder ownership and alignment.

World Café: A conversational methodology encouraging small-group discussions where participants rotate between tables with different prompts. By exchanging ideas and building on collective insights, World Café explores complex issues in a participatory and inclusive manner.

Vision Factory: A collaborative method where stakeholders co-create future scenarios and develop strategies to achieve desired outcomes. Participants engage in creative thinking activities, often using visual aids like drawings or models to illustrate potential futures, helping to align stakeholder aspirations and create a shared understanding of project objectives.

Envisioning the Future: A participatory process inviting stakeholders to visualise potential long-term project outcomes through facilitated sessions using storytelling, sketches, or scenario planning tools. This method helps shape project strategies by ensuring they reflect shared values and collective aspirations.

Charrette: An intensive, multi-day workshop bringing together community members, planners, designers, and experts to collaborate on detailed project designs. Through iterative cycles of brainstorming, prototyping, and feedback, Charrettes create highly contextual solutions that reflect collective stakeholder input.

Citizen Jury: A representative group of community members evaluates project proposals or policies by receiving information and participating in facilitated discussions. This method builds legitimacy and trust in decision-making processes by ensuring informed recommendations that reflect diverse community perspectives.

Gamification: A method applying game mechanics like challenges, rewards, and competition to engage stakeholders and motivate participation. By designing activities that incorporate game elements, this approach simplifies complex issues, encourages behavioral change, and increases stakeholder engagement through interactive experiences.

Stakeholder Working Group: A collaborative team representing different stakeholder categories (community members, experts, officials) formed to provide specialised input and ensure diverse perspectives are integrated into project planning and execution. These groups directly influence project decisions through regular meetings and collaborative input.

Living Lab: An experimental environment where stakeholders co-create, test, and refine innovative solutions in real-world settings. By integrating input from citizens, researchers, and industry partners, Living Labs develop and validate ideas through iterative experimentation focused on complex societal challenges.

Community Mapping: A participatory tool where stakeholders create visual representations of local resources, challenges, and opportunities. By generating maps that include physical features, social networks, or service gaps, this method builds local knowledge and provides valuable insights for project planning and advocacy.

VIPP Cards Collection Clustering: A visualisation method where participants write ideas on cards that are then grouped into clusters based on emerging themes or relationships. This approach organises complex perspectives, ensures all voices are represented, and provides a clear, visual method of synthesising collective input.

Appreciative Inquiry Process: A strengths-based approach that identifies and amplifies positive community attributes instead of focusing on deficits. Structured in phases of discovery, dreaming, and design, this method builds optimism, trust, and aligns stakeholders by focusing on existing successes and future possibilities.

Fishbowl: A dialogue technique where a small group discusses an issue in the center of a larger group, with observers able to join by stepping into the "fishbowl". This method allows for focused discussion while maintaining broader audience engagement, exploring complex topics through dynamic and inclusive conversations.

Nominal Group Technique: A structured brainstorming method that prioritises ideas through group consensus. Participants individually generate ideas, which are then shared, discussed, and collectively ranked to identify the most important or feasible options, ensuring all voices are heard and managing group dynamics.

Reflexive Interactive Design: An iterative project development approach that continuously integrates stakeholder feedback to refine solutions. By creating a cycle of design, feedback, and revision, this method ensures solutions remain flexible, relevant, and responsive to evolving stakeholder needs.

Six Thinking Hats: A problem-solving methodology encouraging participants to approach issues from six distinct perspectives (facts, emotions, positives, negatives, creativity, process). By preventing groupthink and ensuring comprehensive exploration, this technique promotes balanced and diverse discussions.

Topsy Turvy (Reverse Brainstorming): A creative problem-solving technique that flips conventional thinking by first brainstorming ways to exacerbate a problem, then systematically transforming these ideas into potential solutions. This approach helps overcome mental blocks and uncover innovative insights.

After Action Review: A reflective process for evaluating completed activities by systematically analysing what worked well, what didn't, and potential improvements. By fostering open discussion and documenting lessons learned, this method promotes continuous learning and accountability.

Design Thinking: A user-centered methodology emphasising empathy, ideation, prototyping, and testing to address complex challenges. By understanding user needs, generating collaborative solutions, and iteratively refining prototypes, Design Thinking promotes innovative, human-centered problem-solving.

NEBOURHOODS

"Making the city sustainable, affordable and attractive for all has long been at the core of what we do. The New European Bauhaus places particular emphasis on the role of culture and creativity and on directly tangible benefits for people." – **Elisabeth Merk**, Chief Planner of the City of Munich

NEBourhoods focuses on the Munich district of Neuperlach (65,000 inhabitants), with a range of activities and interventions for public spaces, attractive living, energy communities and local mobility, youth culture, nutrition, biodiversity and circular economy for that locality. The ambition is to prototype, test, validate and establish models for other European cities and to become an exemplar of the NEB principles.

Neuperlach faces significant social, urban development and construction-related challenges. With residential and office buildings from the 1960s – 1980s in serious need of renovation, neglected open spaces and a high unemployment rate compared with the city as a whole. Its strengths include the social connection of its multi-cultural residents to their district, extensive green spaces and a separate road network for pedestrians and cyclists, as well as vacant office

structures from which something new can be created. The territory therefore presented an ideal starting point for a revitalisation in the spirit of the New European Bauhaus.

The project established a NEBourhoods Pavilion to provide a meeting place for everyone who would like to be actively involved in the development of their district. They also established a 'Library of Things' with a digital tool, allowing residents to borrow useful household items to support a circular sharing economy. Clubs, organisations and groups from the region were invited to use the NEBourhoods Pavilion free of charge for meetings, exhibitions, events and more.

NEBourhoods created a series of NEB Actions to engage in the design and use of public spaces for all generations, the upgrading of residential buildings and circularity in the existing building inventory. These tested innovations targeting greater biodiversity, renewable energy, local transit and nutrition.

Link: <https://www.nebourhoods.de/>

Animal-Aided Design

Animal-Aided Design (AAD) is an innovative urban planning methodology that integrates wildlife considerations into the architectural and urban development process from the very beginning, rather than as an afterthought. The approach begins with a comprehensive species assessment, where planners identify regional wildlife that could potentially thrive in urban environments. In Neuperlach's case, this involved evaluating approximately 400 animal species and determining which ones could successfully adapt to the local urban conditions.

The design approach focuses on developing multifunctional structures that address both human needs and wildlife requirements.

The "NEBourhoods Nesting Stool" is an urban furniture piece that demonstrates how everyday structures can be designed to serve multiple purposes – providing seating and shade for humans while creating nesting spaces and habitats for various wildlife species.

Growing a Tasty Neuperlach

"Growing a Tasty Neuperlach" integrates sustainable nutrition and edible greening through community-driven activities and education. In collaboration with local residents, the project creates hands-on opportunities in public spaces to inspire interest in climate-adapted food systems and greening. Communal planting and cooking bring diverse participants together to learn and build a greener, edible neighbourhood. Partnering with the Munich Sustainability Initiative and the Nutrition Council of Munich, the project connects agriculture, food production, and climate protection while fostering networks among initiatives, councils, and businesses to transform local food chains.

Public Power

Shade and Energy in Public Spaces focuses on combating urban heat islands through shading solutions that also generate solar energy. Heat stress mainly affects vulnerable groups, making public spaces less accessible and enjoyable.

In Neuperlach, the project identified critical areas for shading interventions based on social, environmental, and economic criteria. Collaborating with architecture students from the Technical University of Munich and local residents, the project developed and implemented demonstrators that showcase the social, ecological, and economic benefits of climate-adaptive design, fostering inclusivity and sustainability in urban spaces.

Circular Neuperlach

The Roadmap to Circularity for Commercial Buildings focused on transforming non-residential buildings in Neuperlach into models of sustainable design, usage, and material recycling. By analysing the spaces, uses, and construction materials of these buildings, the project aimed to reduce resource consumption, extend building lifespans, and close material loops. A collaborative methodology engaged stakeholders from the real estate industry, government, urban planning, and civil society, creating entrepreneurial opportunities and connecting participants to relevant networks.

Private Spaces for Public Use

This NEB Action focuses on integrating vacant office buildings and their surrounding privately-owned public spaces (POPS) into vibrant, mixed-use complexes that enhance urban neighbourhoods. The initiative aims to improve ecological sustainability, encourage social interaction, and enhance residents' quality of life. The project developed the "UrbanSpaceCheck," a certification system awarding gold, silver, and bronze ratings to incentivise the positive transformation of POPS across Europe. This approach integrates ecological, social, and economic considerations and leverages student projects at the Technical University of Munich to address the complexities of urban redevelopment.

Redesigning Housing Structures

The *Wohnen Weiterbauen* demonstrator showcases the outcomes of extensive evaluations of various building types, contributing to climate justice through renewable materials and improving housing efficiency to reduce land use and housing pressure. It aims toward energy-efficient upgrades and social benefits by renovating facades and expanding living spaces using prefabricated timber or reused building materials.

The project emphasises *never demolishing but always transforming*. It proposes a model where building facades are upgraded with prefabricated wooden structures that improve thermal efficiency and create additional usable spaces, such as winter gardens. These spaces act as thermal

buffer zones, reducing heating energy needs and enhance social interaction and living quality by creating flexible, multi-use areas. The design integrates ecological, social, and economic sustainability through the use of renewable materials, long-lasting construction, and affordable housing concepts.

As a prototype for renovating post-war housing estates across Germany and Europe, the project leverages digitised workflows to ensure the broad applicability of its findings. The project resulted in an exhibition at KulturBunt Neuperlach, where films, models and drawings suggest a variety of new living environments that can be created for Neuperlach's aging buildings. The ideas are intended to stimulate discussion about a new culture of conversion in Neuperlach.

Link: <https://www.nebourhoods.de/events/wohnen-weiterbauen-ausstellung/>

Mobility NEBourhoods

A sustainable implementation of innovative forms of mobility is essential to reduce environmental pollution and CO2 emissions. At the same time, it presents an opportunity for the design of attractive urban spaces. New transport strategies such as sharing concepts cannot be realised as purely technological solutions, but must be anchored in local communities and actual urban locations. "Mobility NEBourhoods" combines the data-based analysis of the district's Digital Twin with a collaboration among local stakeholders via playful forms of participation.

Energy Communities

The Energy Communities initiative empowers residents to take control of their energy supply by collaboratively producing, consuming, storing, sharing, and marketing solar power at the neighbourhood level. This programme explores the potential of renewable energy plants developed through cooperative processes, focusing on inclusive financing, participation, and organisational structures tailored to the community. Beyond technological and economic optimisation, the project prioritises social innovation, fostering entrepreneurial services such as electric vehicle charging. Local participation leads to democratic, decentralised, and decarbonised energy systems.

ECOLOPES

The ECOLOPES action supports urban biodiversity by transforming building envelopes into habitats for humans, plants, animals, and microorganisms. In response to declining biodiversity in increasingly dense urban areas like Neuperlach, the project develops ecological building envelopes that address the needs of various species. These innovative structures move beyond being mere barriers between interiors and exteriors, creating transitional spaces that foster cross-species coexistence. Through a multidisciplinary approach combining ecology, architecture, landscape design, and computational methods, the project installs mock-ups of future building envelopes to test their functionality. The initiative promotes beneficial interactions between people and nature, enhances urban well-being, and contributes to biodiversity preservation in city environments.

PEARL – Places for Youth Culture

Joint development of temporary and permanent venues for youth culture that supports young people in engaging with their own living space and creates opportunities for them to actively help shape it. PEARL co-creates places where youth culture can be lived both temporarily and permanently. For example, the project cooperates with the Münchner Kammerspiele to establish a future permanent theater laboratory where youth culture can develop ever new forms of expression. NEBourhoods work with young people in film, urban stories and music and empower them to present their ideas through performative interventions in city locations throughout Neuperlach in the hopes of initiating sustainable changes.

BAUHAUS
OF THE
SEAS
SAILS
(BoSS)

Bauhaus of the Seas Sails (BoSS) focuses the NEB principles on coastal areas and bodies of water because they represent a shared space between Europe and the rest of the world. They regulate the climate by capturing heat and carbon, providing an essential source of food, and generating jobs and wealth through tourism. Coastal regions are the areas most at risk from climate-related effects such as sea level rise, ecosystem degradation, biodiversity loss, and weather events. They also host over 40% of the EU population.

Co-Design Template

Bauhaus of the Seas Sails has published a comprehensive co-design template as part of their project, introducing a methodology for conducting co-design that addresses key considerations and reflective questions, particularly with respect to coastal communities and their relationship with the sea.

The template defines four core principles for demonstrator development: sustainable, inclusive, aesthetic, and locally grounded, and outlines how co-design engages with these principles. It provides an overview of stakeholder involvement, establishes a general timeline for the co-design

process, and offers specific guidance for developing locally relevant co-design practices.

The BoSS framework is a model for achieving sustainable transformations at regional levels. Its focus on co-design ensures that innovation with ecological and social priorities are aligned. Policymakers are encouraged to consider the four guiding principles as evaluative criteria and as tools for fostering dialogue, exploring synergies, and addressing systemic challenges in collaboration with diverse stakeholders.

The four principles reflect the NEB values as well as the contextual element of the coastal communities and marine environments that are the focus of the BoSS Lighthouse.

Sustainable

BoSS shifts from exploiting marine resources to fostering interdependence between humans, ecosystems, and the sea. This entails reconciling with the ocean as a shared space for innovation and ecological renewal.

Inclusive

Focusing on the 'blue economy', BoSS advocates engaging citizens, public institutions, and commercial organisations to counteract societal polarisation. It focuses on creating

pathways for marginalised voices and interconnections between communities and ecosystems.

Aesthetic

Cultural and artistic practices foster relationships and connections for redefining aesthetics as a medium for understanding and engaging with ecological interdependence.

Locally grounded

Sustainable societies cannot be standardised. While the three NEB Pillars are universal, BoSS emphasises managing specific predicaments that are locally experienced rather than seeking universal solutions. It requires meeting communities where they are, beginning with local concerns, needs, fears and hopes to develop processes relevant to community interests.

Those four principles inform the evaluation framework, and provide the following sliding scales for activity planning and assessment.

A local shift in relation to the New European Bauhaus grounding principles

BoSS provides comprehensive guidance for the process of co-creation with communities, and the full document is highly recommended for policymakers who wish to explore this methodology, particularly those working in coastal areas. It can be broadly summarised as follows:

Iterative Co-Design

BoSS approaches co-design as a flexible and inclusive process where problem identification and solution development are connected and cyclical. It involves engaging stakeholders at every stage to foster shared ownership, refine ideas, and then adjust approaches based on emerging results, feedback and insights. Problems are not treated as static or pre-defined. Instead, they are explored collaboratively, recognising that defining a challenge and revealing its complexity can be as significant as solving it. Proposed solutions are tested in practice, generating observations and impacts that go on to shape subsequent iterations. This allows for real-time learning and refinement.

Stakeholder Engagement

BoSS places a strong emphasis on involving a wide spectrum of stakeholders, including community representatives, institutions, cultural practitioners, local organisations, and non-human entities, including ecological systems and marine life. In this way, the methodology embodies the principle of Ecosystem Living, integrating diverse human experiences and non-human considerations, challenging anthropocentric paradigms and fostering ecological balance. Particular attention is paid to involving marginalised voices, recognising that diverse perspectives are essential for systemic change.

Creative Practices

BoSS proposes that artistic and cultural methods should be central to fostering dialogue, experimentation, and relational aesthetics. These practices serve to encourage innovative thinking by moving beyond conventional deductive and inductive problem-solving frameworks. Cultural interventions deepen participants' emotional and experiential connections to the sea and its ecosystems.

Problems and their solutions should not just be considered intellectually, but lived and felt. BoSS also prioritises the facilitation of the (non-confrontational) exploration of tensions and opportunities.

Principles as Planning and Evaluation Tools

The four principles – sustainable, inclusive, aesthetic, and locally grounded – are implemented through a series of evaluative tools, including the "sliders" framework above. This allows co-creation participants to map progress, identify tensions, and balance their priorities.

The Sea Forum

BoSS introduces the operational structure of the 'Sea Forum' – a group who ensure local relevance and alignment with the four principles. The group's responsibilities include enrolling participants with particular thought given to diversity and expertise within the group, co-planning activities and developing the project's executive plan, defining "drops" (specific initiatives) and their expected "ripples" (broader impacts) and co-evaluating to assess progress, adapt strategies and iterate in line with the principles.

Ocean Ambassadors

'Ocean Ambassadors' are community representatives who bridge the project's activities with local aspirations. Their roles include promoting long-term community engagement with sea-related initiatives, assisting in evaluating activities and suggesting adjustments, advocating for marginalised perspectives, and building connections between institutions and local groups.

Link: <https://bauhaus-seas.eu/co-design/>

The BoSS Co-design methodology

- 1. Mapping Local Contexts** Activities begin with identifying local assets, challenges, and opportunities. This includes stakeholder mapping, participatory asset mapping, and defining target communities.
- 2. Creative Exploration** Through workshops and artistic interventions, stakeholders co-create bold visions for local demonstrators (pilot projects). Techniques such as storytelling, visualisation, and role-playing help to uncover new possibilities and strengthen relational connections.
- 3. Theory of Change** The BoSS methodology uses a theory of change framework to define desired impacts and measure progress. This involves identifying long-term goals, mapping the pathways by which activities can lead to these goals, and defining indicators to monitor progress and refine strategies.
- 4. Integration of More-Than-Human Perspectives** The BoSS approach represents non-human stakeholders in all planning and decision-making. This requires new tools and facilitation techniques, such as identifying ecological proxies or using creative representation.

- 5. Managing Tensions** Recognising the potential for conflict between the four principles, for instance balancing ecological priorities with local economic interests. BoSS views these tensions as potentially productive. Structured dialogue and adaptive planning are used to navigate these challenges.
- 6. Social Learning** Mutual learning means that participants not only address immediate challenges but also develop the capacity for ongoing transformation. It includes learning from other regions and contexts and building shared understandings and capacities within local communities.
- 7. Evaluation and Adjustment** Co-evaluation is embedded throughout the project lifecycle, allowing for iterative adjustments. Evaluation focuses on both the direct impacts of activities and the transformative learning among participants.

Drops, Ripples and Waves

Drops are focused, localised pilot projects developed at the regional level to engage communities through co-design, incorporating architecture, sustainability, ecology, and culture. Drops address specific environmental and societal challenges within a defined area or community.

Ripples represent the broader effects of the drops as they extend beyond the immediate context of the demonstrator projects. These impacts spread to cities and influence urban planning and policy, and roll out to regions, nations and beyond. Ripples illustrate how localised activities create a legacy of broader transformation by influencing stakeholders, encouraging replication and scaling.

Waves symbolise the long-term and large-scale systemic change resulting from the cumulative effects of drops and ripples. They are the cultural shifts in how communities and policymakers think about sustainability and inclusivity, the solutions shared across countries

Ripple pilot

or continents and the sustained, global movements for environmental and social innovation that can result.

The Drops pilots are described in brief below to give a sense of the diversity and potential impact for replication in other regional contexts. While they particularly focus on coastal areas, the examples in these drops can also provide inspiration for projects in other contexts.

Multispecies Assemblies

This drop builds on the zoöp concept developed by the Nieuwe Instituut, integrating human and non-human interests into decision-making. Each Bauhaus of the Seas Sails-zoöp pilot uses digital distributed ledger technologies (e.g., blockchain) to share governance knowledge and practices, including appointing a "Speaker for the Living" to advocate for non-human life. Multispecies Assemblies focus on climate justice, citizen engagement, and the co-creation of knowledge, using platforms to assess and address climate impacts through citizen science and social innovation.

Regenerative Menu

This initiative develops sustainable food systems that adapt to climate changes by focusing on regenerative aquatic foods. The drop combines gastronomy, architecture, and design, co-creating menus with local chefs, algae producers, and schools to promote ecosystem-friendly diets. It aims to shift eating habits to reflect environmental resilience, encouraging a "sitopia" mindset that understands the ways that food is more than just sustenance, but connects us to our environment and each other, shaping places and climates.

Blue Makerspace

Inspired by Atelier LUMA's work in the Camargue, this drop creates a design research hub for non-extractivist exploration of aquatic materials, including algae, shells, and salt. It promotes sustainable innovations in architecture, textiles, and urban design. The makerspace bridges culture, critical thinking, and entrepreneurship for a circular blue economy.

Ocean Literacy

This drop educates younger generations about ocean sustainability through partnerships with industry, cultural, and educational institutions. Inspired by the Escola Azul and Eco-Schools Network, it translates scientific findings into actionable insights. The initiative develops tools, products, and experiences to engage students and communities, encouraging a culture of responsibility towards the oceans.

Inclusive Digital Storytelling

Drawing from the MEMEX project, this drop uses AI and AR technologies for geolocalised storytelling to promote intercultural dialogue and inclusivity. Focused on displaced communities, it employs participatory storytelling to build empathy and shared cultural understanding. Stories highlight both human and non-human perspectives, fostering community-building and intercultural engagement.

Wellbeing Reefs

This drop seeks to restore degraded natural reefs to counter coastline erosion and habitat loss. Inspired by artist collective Superflex and Alex Jordan's research, it develops toolkits for creating reef systems that support marine and human populations. It trains local stakeholders to monitor and sustain reef regeneration, integrating scientific, historical, and cultural knowledge into design and construction processes.

Blue Seniors

Targeting senior citizens, this drop addresses mobility, safety, and social inclusion in coastal and island environments. It promotes intergenerational collaboration through co-designed tools and workshops that adapt urban spaces to seniors' needs. By teaming seniors with designers and families, it enhances accessibility and encourages intergenerational knowledge sharing.

Future Tidal Architectures

Focusing on coastal and wetland adaptation, this drop engages architects and urban planners to design solutions for rising sea levels and changing water patterns. By reconciling diverse interests and collaborating across regions, it envisions adaptive strategies through co-design competitions and social engagement. It connects heritage preservation with sustainable urban and rural planning.

Living with Water

Part of the Rotterdam-based New Academy curriculum, this drop positions water as central to the city's identity and resilience. In partnership with Studio Makkink & Bey's WaterSchool, it explores water's role as a material, economic driver, and cultural force. It fosters community-based knowledge production, linking education, activism, and design to shape a city-wide vision of water sustainability.

NEB-STAR

The Barcode

NEB-STAR focuses on innovative urban experimentation and participatory solutions to environmental and social challenges, with 16 partners involved. The tools developed in NEB-STAR involve citizens and stakeholders in urban planning processes. Some offer detailed virtual representations of urban areas, enabling stakeholders to model and test scenarios for development. Others combine research and education to embed NEB principles into local development projects, helping professionals and the public understand and contribute to urban transitions.

NEB-STAR encourages the testing of new ideas through tools that allow companies to trial innovative products or services in collaboration with municipalities, and engage students in solving real-world challenges. There are also tools to help planners balance spatial demands and priorities, fostering a "10-minute city" concept where essential services are easily accessible to all residents. The aim of all these tools is to create processes and methods that are adaptable, scalable, and replicable.

Link: <https://nebstar.eu/>

The barcode concept represents a comprehensive urban planning approach that quantifies and interconnects various city elements like housing, work, social facilities, sports, energy, and infrastructure. By demonstrating the interdependent nature of these functions, the barcode reveals that urban growth is not just about adding housing, but requires a holistic consideration of related needs—such as how constructing 10,000 homes necessitates additional space for supporting functions like greenery, workplaces, and infrastructure. This method allows cities like Utrecht to plan balanced, integrated urban expansion that prevents overburdening of existing resources and maintains a proportional development across different urban sectors.

Citizen panel

Citizen panels are a democratic innovation method that involves randomly selected ordinary citizens in meaningful civic engagement by bringing together small groups (typically 15–30 people) to learn about, discuss, and make recommendations on complex issues. By providing participants with expert knowledge and facilitating structured discussions, these panels aim to enhance public participation in decision-making processes, offering a structured approach to involving citizens in deliberations.

Guided Tours

Guided tours are a valuable tool for community development, offering site-specific knowledge, promoting citizen involvement and inspiring smart solutions. They provide insights into an area's history, culture, and physical features, helping a community make informed decisions on land use, infrastructure, and social programmes. Not just for the tourists, guided tours encourage participation, build trust, and create a sense of ownership within communities. They bring people together, promoting interaction and dialogue that strengthens social cohesion and sparks ideas for place-based innovation.

Digital Twin

A digital twin is a virtual representation of a physical object or system that mirrors its behaviour and characteristics using real-world data. It enables users to visualise, simulate, and experiment with changes that can then be applied to the physical counterpart. By integrating data from sources such as 3D models and real-time sensor updates, a digital twin provides a deeper understanding of complex systems like urban neighbourhoods by modelling elements such as energy, transport, and environmental factors. The Stavanger Municipality's "Bymodellen" allows users to explore planned developments, including viewing surroundings from different angles and walking inside virtual buildings, offering a dynamic and detailed perspective.

NEB Impact Model

The NEB-STAR Impact Model is a framework that supports the NEB principles of sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetics. Based on CrAft's Impact Model, the model captures the environmental, social, cultural, economic, financial and governance impacts of project activities. The model's purpose is to avoid siloed decision-making and uses five impact pillars—environmental, social, cultural, economic, and governance performance—spanning 17 impact categories and 46 suggested indicators. By integrating all of the different impact considerations, the model reduces the risks of fragmented approaches.

Co-creation School

The Samskapingskolen (Co-Creation School) is an educational initiative developed by the city of Stavanger to teach co-creation methodologies, focusing on interdisciplinary collaboration to create better and more inclusive solutions. Initially launched in 2018 as an internal training prototype, it teaches co-creation and design methodologies through practical project work. Since 2020, it has been integrated into the University of Stavanger's postgraduate and further education offerings as a 10-credit course, the first of its kind in Norway. In 2023, the course was expanded into a master's programme in transformation and innovation for team leaders, project managers, and department heads who want to lead innovative change processes, focusing on sustainability, inclusive management, and future knowledge to support the green shift.

Utopian Future Workshop

The Utopian Future Workshop is a co-creation method used in NEB-STAR to empower vulnerable and marginalised groups in urban planning. It facilitates socially and spatially equitable decision-making by asking participants to envision and advocate for desirable urban futures, counterbalancing existing power asymmetries. Utopian ideas are tested against reality, with strategies developed and experimental actions initiated. Experts and decision-makers help participants gain the political leverage to implement these ideas. The approach enables inclusive regional innovation by amplifying underrepresented voices and supporting their role in shaping policies.

Social Marketplace

The Social Marketplace method provides a forum where companies and non-profit organisations can meet to establish new social cooperation. The method facilitates collaboration across different sectors in the local community, and connects volunteering, business, and the public sector. As in a traditional market, participants specify what they have to offer or what they are looking for and seek suitable partners. The aim is to create new opportunities and form collaborations. The participants share resources such as knowledge, labour, care, relationships, internships, materials, and equipment. The Marketplace method is a good context for understanding the opportunities and needs in the local environment.

Vis det! (Show it!) Evaluation tool

Show it! is an impact measurement tool based on the Theory of Change. It's designed to link activities with the desired outcomes and the underlying rationale. It uses a qualitative and narrative approach to articulate how specific actions are expected to bring about meaningful change. The tool examines the target group's needs, identifies barriers to success, and makes the assumptions clear. Gathering insights through surveys, interviews, and focus groups, the methodology helps social enterprises develop a strategic plan for future efforts. It ensures that activities are purpose-driven and effectively aligned with their social impact goals.

Walk the Land

Walk the Land is a method developed by the architectural firm Helen & Hard to foster a deeper connection to the context and resources of a site during the early stages of architectural projects. Inspired by Aboriginal practices of relating to land, it involves walking the site to uncover its unique material, cultural, human, and aesthetic potentials. Participants explore the site, using their senses to observe its unique qualities—such as smells, sounds, and atmosphere—forming an extended and personal impression. They translate

those experiences into physical expressions, such as drawings, models, or compositions, as a way to externalise their understanding and inspiration, and the group shares and discusses these expressions, collectively distilling insights to inform the project. These outcomes are then communicated to stakeholders such as clients or municipalities.

Urban Belonging

Urban Belonging is a participatory project that explores how marginalised groups experience their relationship with the city. Partnering with local community organisations, the initiative engaged participants identifying as ethnic minorities, deaf, homeless, physically disabled, mentally vulnerable, international, and/or LGBT+. Participants documented their interactions with the city over three months using tools such as participatory mapmaking and photography, producing over 1,400 photos, 200 maps, and extensive data visualisations. The outputs include a rich catalogue that tells individual and collective stories about Copenhagen, offering insights into what "belonging" means for different identities. The initiative provides valuable perspectives for understanding and addressing inclusion in regional innovation, urban planning and design.

Situated Learning Environment

Situated learning theory is about how knowledge develops through active participation in a community of practice. Learners improve their expertise by engaging with real-world contexts, becoming active participants. Within the NEB-STAR project, TU Delft creates situated learning environments that connect students with societal partners, allowing for meaningful problem-solving, structured collaboration, and engagement in societal debates. In the "Geodesign for Circular Economy in Urban Regions" Master's course, students applied principles of sustainability, collaboration, and aesthetics in line with New European Bauhaus principles. The approach links research and education to create relevant solutions, strengthen societal connections, and amplify the impact of student contributions in regional innovation.

Agile Piloting (Kvikktest)

Kvikktest is a method used by municipalities to invite companies, start-ups, and entrepreneurs to test out innovative solutions to local challenges. The process creates a collaboration between the municipality, businesses, and citizens, focusing on a challenge defined by the municipality, who release a call inviting companies to propose solutions that can be trialled for up to six months. Selected solutions receive financial support to cover expenses, allowing for real-world testing and valuable feedback within a short timeframe.

Smart Art

Smart Art integrates art in urban planning and public engagement. It emphasises the role of art in fostering inclusion, aesthetics, and sustainability, while strengthening the artist economy and cultural industries. One significant project, Sjøkanten, brought together artists, researchers, and planners to incorporate ecological thinking with innovative public engagement methods. It involved workshops, temporary art projects, and active engagement with residents, including children, to expand participation in the urban development process. Sjøkanten introduced the concept of artists-in-residence within municipal planning teams, which is now being tested in NEB-STAR.

Another example is the Broken Column Art Hike, which uses AI technology to enhance public access to Stavanger's cultural history. Visitors can listen to synthetic speech narrating the story behind 23 sculptures across the city, making art more interactive and inclusive. These projects collectively highlight how art and technology can enhance cultural engagement and contribute to urban innovation and inclusion in Stavanger.

Innovation Camp

Innovation Camp focuses on fostering creativity, innovation, and collaborative problem-solving, often as part of the start-up phase for student or youth companies. Students are presented with a real-world problem defined by a private or public sector client. Working in groups, they develop solutions within a set timeframe and present their ideas to a jury, which selects the best solution based on specific criteria. Collaboration with local businesses and industries is a key element of the programme. Clients provide essential background information and guidance, ensuring the solutions are relevant to real-world challenges. Innovation Camp combines experiential learning with practical engagement, enhancing participants' skills in teamwork, creativity, and entrepreneurship.

The CrAft Cookbook

The Creating Actionable Futures (CrAft) project places the transition to climate neutrality at the forefront of urban development. The project conducted experiments in three Sandbox Cities – Amsterdam, Bologna, and Prague – to test and refine collaborative local governance models, and engaged with a broader network of more than 70 Reference Cities, sharing knowledge and insights about climate-neutral transformations.

The resulting methodology is distilled into the CrAft Cookbook – a collection of recipes, ingredients and techniques for climate-centred regional innovation. It contains seven stages of integrated planning and implementation, each with key principles and a series of actions with ingredients and techniques needed to plan and execute local co-creation with partners and stakeholders.

Vision: Redefine the problem, identify what you need, organise the local ecosystem, brainstorm, create a shared, evidence-driven knowledge base, explore legislation and commitments, and summarise in a vision document.

Decide and Commit: Translate the vision, detail roles, responsibilities and capacity, re-align goals, ambitions and strategies, jointly prioritise pathways and actions, form internal and external teams and explore different financial schemes.

Plan: Jointly define milestones, targets and responsibilities, explore the state of the art, rank relevant ongoing and possible

new projects, select preferred financial and partnership models and prepare the monitoring process.

Do: Upskill the team with additional knowledge and capacities, identify the baseline and start the monitoring process, organise access to and sharing of data, kick off implementation and execute implementation with structural support.

Check: Use the NEB Impact Model to balance perspectives, fill gaps with NEB Impact Model Indicators and co-benefits, undertake benchmarking and evaluate progress and identify potential adjustments.

(Re)Act: Decide upon and implement the most suitable improvements, report and learn.

Scale & Replicate: Engage in peer-to-peer sharing and learning, define NEB-inspired business and governance models, and perform a viability assessment.

Link: <https://craft-cities.eu/craft-cookbook/>

CULTUUR&
CAMPUS
PUTSELAAN

Cultuur&Campus Putselaan is an approach to urban innovation and transformation through a central hub to bring a local community together around arts, education and ecological innovation. It differs from the other NEB Lighthouse projects in that it centres around the repurposing of an historic building, the opening of which is the key milestone and culmination of the project.

The Feijenoord district in the south of Rotterdam has a highly diverse population, where the majority are non-western immigrants, including significant Moroccan, Turkish, Surinamese, and Antillean communities. The area faces considerable socio-economic challenges, with high unemployment and low educational attainment, and several neighbourhoods rank among the most disadvantaged in the Netherlands.

Cultuur&Campus provides an interesting case study for regional innovation intended to result in the creation of a new facility, community hub or building project because it brings together a wide range of stakeholders and addresses commonly shared challenges in simple and creative ways that are easily replicable and adaptable to other contexts.

Creative Campus

Putselaan is intended to act as a hub for interdisciplinary collaboration, fostering dialogue and co-creation between local residents, students, educators, researchers, and entrepreneurs, outside of traditional formal education settings.

It exemplifies how culture and education can be central to addressing pressing urban challenges, and that neither of those things need mirror the formal infrastructures usually associated with them. It will instead operate as a living lab, experimenting with innovative approaches to urban development and creating a dynamic space where anyone can contribute to sustainable solutions. Activities are designed to reflect the lived experiences of local residents while addressing broader environmental challenges such as climate change and biodiversity loss. These include ecological innovation projects, co-designed programmes, and public events that bridge cultural and educational objectives.

Local voices

One of the main ways in which Cultuur&Campus has galvanised its community is by conducting 87 street interviews that captured spontaneous and candid insights into the needs and aspirations of the community. Street interviews allowed the project team to meet residents, creating an informal and approachable avenue for dialogue. This direct engagement helped break down barriers between the community and the project organisers, fostering a sense of trust and inclusion from the outset.

The project also leveraged the stories of community "champions" through video portraits. These highlighted individual experiences and aspirations and placed the champion in their own context, personalising the broader goals of Cultuur&Campus, making them relatable and connected to lived experience. The insights captured in this way provided a more accurate and grounded understanding of the community and presented a shared 'bottom-up' vision.

Identify and Support Local Champions

Recognise and empower individuals within the community who can inspire, lead, and mobilise others. Work closely with these champions to foster trust and co-create initiatives that resonate deeply with local values.

Ensure Co-Ownership of Projects

Collaborate with residents as equal partners in the design, planning, and implementation phases. Share decision-making authority to create a sense of ownership and pride in the project's outcomes.

Tailor Activities to Community Needs

Customise programming to address the specific challenges and aspirations of the community. Educational workshops, cultural events, and sustainability initiatives should be relevant and accessible to all.

Build Strong Partnerships Across Sectors

Establish collaborations with local schools, universities, cultural institutions, and businesses. Use these partnerships to create a robust ecosystem for innovation and social impact.

Invest in Community Trust-Building Efforts

Address historical mistrust in institutions by demonstrating transparency, consistency, and accountability. This can take time, but is essential to the success and buy-in of a project like this. Celebrate local narratives through events, public art, and storytelling initiatives to strengthen the connection between the community and its surroundings.

Promote Local Talent and Expertise

The project is a place to create and foster new works and upskill local people, but it also provides a focal point to bring in, celebrate and amplify the contributions of the brilliant people already achieving great things in your neighbourhood. Encourage and build upon a local sense of achievement, pride, agency and capability.

Celebrate Milestones and Progress Publicly

Use events, festivals, and showcases to celebrate achievements and engage the broader public. These moments of visibility help galvanise community support and maintain momentum.

Link: <https://putselaan.nl/>

Link: <https://www.cultuurencampusrotterdam.nl/>

NEB Labs

NEB Labs bring together architects, designers, scientists, policymakers, businesses, and citizens to create multi-disciplinary partnerships that co-design solutions for sustainable and inclusive spaces. The NEB Labs test innovative ideas, methods, and materials to address environmental, social, and economic challenges. Pilot projects may involve creating or renovating public spaces, experimenting with circular construction techniques, or integrating renewable energy into urban environments.

They act as hubs for sharing best practices, tools, and methodologies. Workshops, training programmes, and knowledge-sharing events are hosted to equip participants with skills and insights. The work with policymakers informs and shapes local, regional, and EU-level policies that integrate NEB principles. They sometimes pilot policy frameworks that can be scaled or replicated across the EU.

Labs actively involve local communities in decision-making, ensuring that their outcomes are grounded in real needs and aspirations. Public dialogues and participatory design processes are often central to their activities, and successful initiatives are documented and showcased to inspire others and create pathways for scaling up solutions across Europe.

Examples of NEB Lab Activities:

- Designing carbon-neutral urban spaces that incorporate natural ecosystems, such as urban forests or wetlands.
- Developing sustainable building materials from recycled or biodegradable resources.
- Reimagining underutilised public spaces into vibrant, inclusive hubs for culture, education, and interaction.
- Exploring digital and artistic tools to visualise and promote the NEB principles in urban and rural settings.

The purpose of the NEB Labs is to act as the operational arm of the New European Bauhaus, turning its visionary goals into practical, scalable actions. Each lab operates with its own unique focus, depending on the local context and stakeholders involved. This ensures their activities are relevant to their specific environment.

Nordic Carbon Neutral Bauhaus

The first of the NEB Labs, the **Nordic Carbon Neutral Bauhaus** was established by Nordic authorities as an active collaboration for preparing effective and practical policies for sustainable construction. Regular activities include Nordic stakeholder meetings and the annual Nordic Climate Forum for Construction.

Link: <https://www.nordicbauhaus.eu/>

NEB goes South

NEB goes South (NEBgS) was created by six schools of architecture from different European countries, expanding by a further eight schools in September 2024. The initiative is a pan-European platform for meetings and discussion about sustainable and innovative architectural practices in Southern Europe, addressing contemporary challenges through sustainable design, public engagement, and interdisciplinary research.

Link: <https://www.neb-goes-south.pt/>

The New European Bauhaus of the Mountains

The **New European Bauhaus of the Mountains** seeks to improve the quality of the built environment and citizens' quality of life in rural and mountain areas. The project enables a creative collaboration process between thinkers and facilitators who want to develop innovative beautiful, sustainable and inclusive solutions for complex social problems in the areas of affordable housing, sustainability, circular design, art and democracy, creative industries, design education and digital transformation for the common good. It focuses particularly on South Tyrol, as the province's landscape is dominated by mountains

Link: <https://mountainbauhaus.eu/>

New European Bauhaus on the Danube

The **New European Bauhaus on the Danube (NEBoD)** is a think-and-do tank driving the green transition in the Danube Region by fostering cooperation between public authorities, civil society, and the private and financial sectors to promote sustainable land use and a green economy. The initiative pioneers innovative methods to engage diverse stakeholders, revitalise degraded areas, and advance education for a just and inclusive transformation.

Link: <https://danube-region.eu/nebod/>

NEB Stewardship Lab

The **NEB Stewardship Lab** explores how higher education can play a transformative role in advancing the goals of the New European Bauhaus. By co-developing the NEB Stewardship model through workshops and participatory research activities, the lab provides a framework for integrating sustainability-focused education and practical innovation. This academic-led effort aims to inspire climate stewardship, particularly among students, while offering tools, networks, and proof-of-concept examples to make the NEB vision accessible and actionable.

Link: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/neb-stewardship-lab/>

European Triennial of Modernism (ETOM)

The **European Triennial of Modernism (ETOM)** initiative supports trans-European collaboration focusing on Modernism through a co-creation platform and festival. The ETOM NEB Lab supports transnational cooperation, research, and the sharing of best practices and hosts a recurring European Triennial of Modernism. The ETOM motto "Diverse Modernism | Modern Diversity" highlights Modernism's inclusive and sustainable values, addressing its heritage and relevance to contemporary global challenges.

Link: <https://www.triennale-der-moderne.de/2022/en/european-triennial-of-modernism-etom/>

NEB

COMPASS

NEB Compass

As an evaluation tool, the NEB Compass is a guiding framework for policymakers, project leaders, and regional administrators. In addition to the three core values, the Compass also allows for examining proposals and projects in terms of their participatory, transdisciplinary, and multi-level engagement approaches as essential working principles.

As these kinds of values can be particularly difficult to measure in any quantifiable way, the Compass is particularly useful as a tool for assessing – and therefore allowing project teams to reflect upon – varying levels of ambition. It encourages projects to evolve from baseline practices to transformative actions. It supports rethinking local governance models, experimenting with creative urban planning, and fostering collaboration between public, private, and community sectors. By mapping projects against three distinct and identifiable levels of ambition within

each principle, regional policymakers and stakeholders not only have a framework for contextualising their project, they can easily course-correct and adjust to ensure the kinds of impacts they wish to have.

This flexible approach means it can be applied to a wide range of projects—from urban design and architecture to educational programmes and community engagement activities. The full NEB Compass document, linked below, provides concrete examples, guiding questions, and a framework for self-assessment. It aids in designing initiatives that align with the NEB goals while addressing specific regional priorities. This ensures that the Compass not only inspires innovative solutions but also creates opportunities for scalable, systemic change that reflects local needs and aspirations.

The core elements are summarised in the next pages.

Link: https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/get-involved/use-compass_en

Beautiful

The **Beautiful** value in the NEB Compass is structured around three ambition levels, each representing a progressive approach to embedding beauty and aesthetics into projects.

Ambition I: Activate focuses on enhancing the sensory and emotional experiences of individuals through cultural, social, and natural qualities. It seeks to reawaken appreciation for a place or project by encouraging interactions that improve physical and mental well-being while embracing local heritage and aesthetics. For example, a project may revitalise a neglected landscape or structure by celebrating its unique features and creating positive experiences that highlight its aesthetic and cultural value. Regional policymakers could use this ambition level to activate underused or neglected spaces, encouraging new appreciation and functional use while preserving local identity and history.

Ambition II: Connect is about building connections between people, places, and contexts, creating opportunities for meaningful social interactions and fostering a sense of belonging. It emphasises openness and mutual care by integrating the experiences of diverse groups and making spaces more inclusive. For instance, a project might involve co-design with different community members to create a shared cultural or social experience that unites disparate groups through art, design, or architecture. This ambition can help design projects that bridge divides in communities, such as creating shared spaces or programmes, encouraging collective engagement and enhancing mutual understanding.

Ambition III: Integrate is the highest ambition, focusing on enabling systemic change by embedding aesthetic, cultural, and social values into the long-term identity of a place. Projects at this level aim for deep transformation, encouraging co-creation and sustainable practices that anticipate future shifts. They integrate human and non-human needs, fostering resilience and a holistic sense of beauty that celebrates materials, community, and environmental harmony. The ambition of integration invites projects to adopt long-lasting approaches that restructure

the way cities, regions, or communities live and interact on a day-to-day basis, and encourage permanent transformative urban or rural development.

Sustainable

The **Sustainable** value in the NEB Compass is also structured around three ambition levels. These provide a roadmap for embedding sustainability into regional innovation and project development.

Ambition I: Repurpose focuses on rethinking and repairing services, products, and places to minimise resource use, reduce pollution, and lower carbon footprints. Projects aim to repurpose existing materials and spaces, emphasising durability, adaptability, and recyclability. For example, initiatives might involve reusing architectural materials or upgrading infrastructure to extend its lifespan while reducing environmental impact. This level describes projects that breathe new life into existing resources and infrastructure. It supports adaptive reuse and sustainability while reducing costs and waste.

Ambition II: Close the Loop moves beyond repurposing to transform linear processes into circular systems, minimising waste and aiming for a net zero impact. It encourages collaboration across all actors in a product's lifecycle, from design and production to disposal and reuse. 'Close the Loop' projects embrace industrial symbiosis and systemic circularity, such as using modular designs and sustainable materials to create adaptive solutions. This promotes cross-sector partnerships and efficient resource management, reducing long-term environmental impacts.

Ambition III: Regenerate is the highest ambition, which seeks to restore and enhance natural ecosystems while encouraging behavioural and systemic change. Regenerative projects give back more than they take, focusing on biodiversity, carbon storage, and ecosystem restoration. This level is about the project's broader, positive impact on natural resources, society, and worldviews, addressing long-

term sustainability and resilience. This ambition can drive transformative projects that replenish ecosystems, recover biodiversity, combat climate change, and shift societal norms toward sustainable living. It aligns urban or regional development with ecological stewardship, emphasising deeper systemic challenges.

Together

Under the **Together** theme of the NEB Compass, the three levels of ambition outline approaches to inclusion, representation, and collective social growth. These levels can guide project leaders and policymakers to create equitable and cooperative regional innovations.

Ambition I: To Include prioritises accessibility, equality, and affordability, ensuring that opportunities and services are open to all, particularly disadvantaged and underrepresented groups. Projects with this ambition break down barriers, providing equitable treatment and access regardless of gender, ability, or socioeconomic status. For example, initiatives might address affordable housing and inclusive public spaces for diverse community use. This ambition can be used to design infrastructure and programmes that directly address disparities, prioritising equity.

Ambition II: To Consolidate focuses on overcoming segregation and fostering representation and social stability. Projects with this ambition create mechanisms that reshape community relationships through a lens of societal justice by sharing resources and ensuring structural support through policies, business models, and funding tools. Initiatives could encourage intergenerational cooperation and community-building activities to strengthen ties. This level of ambition provides a framework for bridging social divides, fostering cohesion, and institutionalising inclusive practices to build lasting relationships between communities and sectors.

Ambition III: To Transform is the highest ambition. It seeks systemic change, introducing new ways of living together based on solidarity and shared social values. Projects with this ambition eliminate discrimination and inequality while creating replicable models of inclusion that break down outdated systems. For example, collaborative neighbourhood design could empower residents to co-create shared spaces, transforming social behaviours and encouraging collective action. Transformative initiatives redefine community interaction, making inclusion a foundational principle of regional planning and governance.

It's important to remember that regardless of ambition, societal challenges are never 'solved'. Instead, the intention is to create the kind of society and infrastructure in which they would not be encountered or experienced.

The NEB Compass document includes several examples and case studies of NEB-aligned projects across Europe that demonstrate the application of the Compass to a range of initiatives, from a textile process made from flower waste to a new 30-metre wooden event pavilion in a public space, each initiative demonstrating a different level of ambition across the three main pillars.

DIGITAL LIFE

CONNECTED YET DISCONNECTED

The extent to which, during the pandemic, society shifted towards data-driven systems cannot be overstated. This was not an incremental or even accelerated rate of change but radical and exponential. The unprecedented demand for technological solutions that could bridge physical distances required by remote work, the newly tech-driven requirements for the delivery of formerly analogue components of education, healthcare, food systems and democracy – to maintain a semblance of operational continuity – was just the tip of the iceberg. Substantial capital investments usually channelled to the automotive sector, aviation, commercial real estate, large-scale in-person entertainment events and other domains were severely impacted by lockdowns and other restrictions, and were redirected in bulk towards digital communication tools, cloud computing and, in particular, rapid AI development²⁰. The value of Bitcoin increased by over 800% between the start of 2020 and April 2021²¹, and Venture Capital funding in technology startups doubled during that same period²². These had the effect of

throwing fuel on an already substantial fire. All the signs were of the emergence of an entirely data-driven society as the dominant framework condition.

Prior to 2020, many in Europe were regular and accustomed users of digital tools and technology. But since 2022, we *inhabit* an almost entirely digital world – one defined by data – which not only drives economies and governance but mediates social interactions, facilitates cultural production, and shapes personal identity. This shift has positioned data not merely as a tool for decision-making but the infrastructure upon which modern life is built.

This was the societal equivalent of the music industry's 'Napster moment', distributed across all industries, the public sector, and culture as a whole. The shift highlighted opportunities and vulnerabilities in data-driven systems. It accelerated advancements in medicine, commerce, and remote work infrastructure while exposing serious gaps in data governance, ethical AI use, and digital accessibility.

Data promises emancipatory and democratic power, as well as the power of surveillance, control and concentration of wealth. The primacy of data-driven systems has deepened divides between those who can leverage them and those excluded by digital inequities. Our now total reliance on data systems raises critical questions about fundamentals such as truth, human rights, and ethical governance. It also raises questions about the disconnect between the good work on the ground and the digital systems that we build.

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20 The Recovery will be Digital – McKinsey & Company, 2020. [\[Link\]](#)

21 Investopedia: Bitcoin's Price History. Last accessed 10/2024 [\[Link\]](#)

22 Looking Back: 2022 Venture Capital Trends Review, 2023. Vation. [\[Link\]](#)

JUST Data

Please draw a picture of a man and a woman. The woman is taller than the man.

Message ChatGPT

In one of the JUST Data experiments conducted with stakeholders from the health sector, participants asked ChatGPT to draw a couple, where a woman is taller than the man. No way of rephrasing the question could stop the system from repeatedly drawing a couple where a man was much taller than the woman.

JUST Data promotes Judicious, Unbiased, Safe and Transparent data practice by data scientists, industries, operators, analysts and owners – creating context and understanding beyond measurement and statistics.

Our quality of experience depends upon the qualities encoded within our digital systems. More than 400 million terabytes of data are created every day²³. All that data is processed to train AI systems and used to make decisions about where we can live, whether we can work, which public services can be offered, what healthcare we can receive, and what measures can be taken to improve air quality, reduce local crime or ensure safety on the roads.

.....
23 Volume of worldwide data created, 2024. Statista. [Link]

JUST Data proposes that while data can never be entirely 'unbiased', it is possible to mitigate against the negative effects of data bias by understanding the limitations and context of any data set.

A system trained on a dataset that has inherited limited views might not understand that a woman can be taller than a man.

Perhaps more importantly, data is only ever about the past, so data systems cannot imagine possible futures.

Knowledge about data can be more valuable than the data itself.

Applying JUST data practices to industry, research, and public policy reconnects the values, imagination and good work of the NEB communities with the digital systems we build.

The digiNEB project organised **JUST Industry Data Week** at Linköping Science Park, a European Digital Innovation Hub (EDIH) in the current European Capital of Innovation. In a city of 160,000 residents, Linköping Science Park is home to over 600 businesses, including large organisations like Ericsson, SAAB and Actia Nordic, and innovative SMEs addressing societal challenges through data and technology.

The universal relevance of data across industrial and knowledge domains and the shared concerns about truth, trustworthy systems and ethical governance meant that JUST Data practices proved an ideal platform to bring together a diverse cross-section of domains and areas of expertise, ensuring ongoing collaboration and knowledge exchange between NEB communities, digital, industry and business.

Link: <https://mtflabs.net/just/linkoping-programme/>

International NEB experts meet the local digital ecosystem

JUST Industry Data Week invited international experts from the wider NEB community to meet in Linköping to work with the local digital, technology and industry ecosystem. JUST Industry Data Week featured keynote presentations and global brainstorming on issues like circularity, data sovereignty, inclusion, representation and bias in synthetic data, AI in industry, data sonification in industrial and public sector communication, cognitive cities, JUST living environments, and AI applications for social good. These showcased the integration of NEB principles with cutting-edge digital technologies and underlined the importance of NEB to the digital and industry domains.

Sound for Urban Environments

The week-long experimentation track implemented JUST Data practice across domains. The unifying challenge focused on the technological and cultural aspects of Sound for Urban Environments, exploring how to signal and interact in the era of AI, automation and IoT devices, how this affects personal space and culture, and how to ensure that technologies are implemented for social good.

Deconstructing AI Literacy

A workshop by TU Delft researcher Diana Popa, 'Deconstructing AI literacy' is a role-based approach to defining relevant AI literacy. By engaging the NEB community and industry practitioners in conflicting narratives around what is essential when developing, deploying and using AI systems, the event explored adaptive AI governance frameworks and AI literacy responsibilities.

AI for social good: JUST Living Environments

Data-driven systems and technologies can enhance the quality of life in urban spaces. JUST Living Environments reflects on JUST Data practice as a key component of the hands-on, collaborative methods that allow for prototyping

Ana Kuštrak Korper, PhD student of service design at Linköping University, working with Naveen Venkatesh Sridharan, PhD researcher of ICT for industrial systems at Luleå University of Technology. Photo: Francisca Siza

and experimentation across the built environment, primary industry, transportation, healthcare, and earth observation.

Global brainstorming

The JUST Data event brought in a global community, with online participants interacting through hybrid brainstorming sessions in response to provocations that spark interdisciplinary dialogue. Discussions addressed data ethics, the challenges of training AI systems with diverse datasets, and whether AI can be trained to help envision more equitable and sustainable futures. Global brainstorming sessions provide a platform for international perspectives and emphasise the need for collaboration in addressing shared challenges across regions.

Field trips and hands-on prototyping

Field trips and experimental activities within Linköping allowed for hands-on engagement. Participants collected data (including audio and EMF recordings) from the local environment and began developing prototypes incorporating insights from direct experience with urban soundscapes, focusing on restoring connections between work on the ground and the digital systems we create and use.

Connecting NEB Communities with Digital and Industry

A digiNEB day focused on the application of data for social good, emphasising ethical data practices, participatory design, and ecosystemic approaches to regional innovation. Discussions centred on sustainable urban planning, cognitive cities and international examples of AI and data being used to support informal settlements in India and coastal communities in Portugal.

Testing with local communities

Projects were tested on local citizens in a public showcase event held at the Linköping Concert Hall, bringing the local community, representatives of regional government, industry leaders and academics to experience installations, engage with prototypes and watch performances and presentations of the works created during the week.

Establishing long-term collaborations

The ongoing results of the JUST Industry Data Week include partnerships between international experts and local actors, proposed funding for new research collaborations in industrial data sonification, continuing dialogue between NEB communities, digital, industry and business, and the establishment of new local collaborations, with several supported to scale further.

Link: Playlist – JUST Industry Data Week presentations: <http://bit.ly/JUST-videos>

Environmental sound and performance artist Kat Austen presented one of the most quoted provocations of the Global Brainstorming sessions at the JUST Industry Data Labs in Linköping Science Park.

As part of the JUST Data project, Vinnova funded a white paper about data governance solutions to support JUST data practices.

Link: White Paper on Data Documentation for JUST Data Practices: <https://zenodo.org/records/14228289>

The following pages list some of the tools and methods that can be used to work towards JUST Living environments:

- tools and methods for fair engagement of citizen communities with the digital,
- innovation lab methodologies for developing and testing technologies that embed human values,
- innovative approaches to public funding for collaborative development, and
- ways to examine technological artefacts for their impacts on society.

Waag Futurelab

Waag Futurelab is a pioneering organisation that has been working at the junction between the digital and citizen communities since the 1990s. The Waag Society for Old and New Media was originally founded in 1994 by Marleen Stikker (now director of Waag Futurelab) and Caroline Nevejan (now Chief Science Officer of the City of Amsterdam) as the first public access portal to the internet that engaged citizens in democratic processes.

Over the years Waag has developed a series of tools that make the interaction between technology, society and governance more open, fair and inclusive. It opened the first FabLab in Europe in 2007, launched a Fairphone in 2010 claiming the Right-to-Repair for citizens, and an Open Wetlab in 2013 for experimental learning about biotechnology. In 2020 Strikker published the book "The Internet is broken, but we can fix it" anticipating some of the current technological challenges.

Below is a list of tools that enhance engagement of citizens with their environments and democratic processes.

Co-creation Navigator

<https://ccn.waag.org>

Communing

<https://waag.org/en/project/code-conduct-social-economy/>
<https://waag.org/en/project/platformcoop-incubator/>
<https://waag.org/en/project/atelier/>

Public Stacking

<https://waag.org/nl/article/toolkit-de-public-stack/>

Human values for smarter cities

<https://humanvaluesforsmartercities.nl/>
<https://civicinteractiondesign.com/projects/human-values-for-smarter-cities/>

Co-creation Navigator: an interactive guide through different stages of co-creation, from preparation to execution.

Handbook Public-Civic collaboration

<https://waag.org/nl/article/handboek-publiek-civiele-samenwerking/>
(In Dutch but translation possible)

Urban freeing handbook of T-factor

<https://hub.t-factor.eu/thematic-toolbox/>

Temporary place making guide

https://waag.org/sites/waag/files/2024-08/TemporaryPlacemaking_WaagFuturelab.pdf

Power mapping

<https://waag.org/nl/article/publieke-waarden-het-aanbestedingsproces/>

MTF Labs

A veteran of the data-driven innovation space, MTF Labs was born out of an EU research project community centred around Music Information Retrieval, as Music Tech Fest in 2012, and grew into a global cross-domain knowledge exchange and prototyping community of over 8000 contributors from across industrial and knowledge domains.

24 global labs have enabled community experimentation with the affordances of frontier technologies, challenging notions of ability, the nature of work, and the set up of supporting systems. Week-long labs that unite artists and scientists, academia and industry are listed as a Best Practice for technology transfer and cross-domain knowledge exchange in the EU Knowledge Valorisation platform²⁴.

International experts engage with local knowledge

Invited international experts who participate in hands-on innovation activities engage with the local ecosystem developing a greater understanding of the local culture, regional ambition and technological affordances. This leads to long-term relationships with experts who have a vested interest in the success of the local ecosystem, and establishes an ongoing network of shared knowledge.

Global brainstorming establishes ongoing collaborations

Hybrid online and in-person brainstorming sessions gather expertise from different parts of the world and knowledge domains to incentivise long-term collaborations.

Participants immerse themselves in the local context

Field trips connect the international expertise to the specific lived reality of the regional ecosystem, allowing for applied knowledge rather than theory and abstraction.

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24 <https://bit.ly/mtflabs-valorisation>

*MTF Labs in the Laguna de Aveiro in Portugal: experiments between oceanographers, neuroscientists, artists and the local community.
Photo: Francisca Siza ©MTF Labs*

Prototyping translates thought into practice

Conducting practical experiments and building prototypes allows locals and internationals from different domains to work together and turn ideas into tangible results that cement these partnerships and create momentum for ongoing development and scaling.

Prototypes become part of a collective experience

Final demonstrations and showcases test the impact of the resulting technology prototypes on humans and ecosystems by making them part of the lived experience.

Results are embedded in long-term collaborations

Identifying and supporting the most successful prototypes through funding mechanisms, industry partnerships, and institutional support allows for scale and impact.

Innovation Commons

"The key resource in an innovation commons is not the technology itself, but the distributed, partial and heterogeneous information that surrounds it. Much of this information is experimentally acquired, often tacit and of little value by itself, but of high value when combined with other information that reveals how the technology might be applied, and by whom, to do what, in combination with what, and so on."²⁵

The concept of Innovation Commons presents a useful approach to fostering innovation within regional ecosystems. As a catalyst for creative experimentation and the coalescence of ideas, they function much like the historical example of the Homebrew Computer Club at Stanford, which famously nurtured early personal computing innovations. In today's context, similar environments can be observed in hacker and maker spaces and various collaborative communities, where open-source software development thrives. These spaces balance competition and collaboration, allowing for the collective development of shared resources crucial for innovation.

One significant challenge to this space of commons is the mechanism by which innovation is funded and financed. While often effective in addressing specific challenges or knowledge gaps, public funding does not often foster long-term value creation or sustainable operations. As a result, many innovation-supporting assets, such as tools, methods, and models, fail to be utilised effectively beyond the initial project phase, leading to a cyclical pattern of "reinventing the wheel."

Swedish innovation agency Vinnova has funded a preliminary study into funding, governance and development models for Innovation Commons approaches.

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²⁵ Allen & Potts, 2016. How innovation commons contribute to discovering and developing new technologies. International Journal of the Commons, Vol. 10, No. 2 (2016), pp. 1035-1054.

The proposed actions are:

- 1. Transition** from traditional project financing **to more dynamic investment models** that act as enablers for long-term collective action.
- 2. Promote** not only initial knowledge enhancement but also **long-term strategic learning** to capture the uniqueness of each commons' experimental design of rules required to achieve desired outcomes.
- 3. Explore and develop technical platforms** for active management and continuous development of commons in innovation ecosystems.
- 4. Explore and develop monitoring and evaluation methods** by identifying the factors that determine if and when commons create value, the effects of use, behavioural changes and shifts within the ecosystem.

Link: https://digitalwellarena.se/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/policypaper_commons_eng.pdf

The study provides a proposal for structured experiments by financiers:

Link: https://digitalwellarena.se/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/financing_commons_eng.pdf

A legal memorandum is provided on how to view the commons in relation to Swedish state aid rules. Different models for describing, organising and analysing the commons have been compiled. Swedish documents can be accessed here:

Link: <https://digitalwellarena.se/en/innovation-commons-en-forstudie/>

The Tetrad

The Tetrad is an insightful and analytical co-creation activity based on Marshall and Eric McLuhan's book *The Laws of Media* (1992). While some may be put off by the apparently academic nature of the source material, the exercise invites participants, ideally from diverse departments or stakeholder groups, to examine proposed approaches through a framework that helps to analyse the effects of any system based on four aspects: Enhancement, Obsolescence, Retrieval, and Reversal.

This kind of analysis, applied to various technologies and initiatives, can reveal hidden effects and long-term implications, aiding policymakers in crafting measures that are more resilient and in tune with societal needs.

For instance, let's examine the introduction of the smartphone:

Enhancement (What does it improve?): Smartphones enhance communication by making it instant and multimedia, allowing users to connect through voice, text, and video from virtually anywhere. It enhances understanding of the world through instant access to information wherever you are.

Obsolescence (What does it render obsolete?): The smartphone renders traditional landlines and even earlier forms of mobile phones less necessary, along with media such as standalone cameras, radios and newspapers.

Retrieval (What does it retrieve that was previously obsolesced?): Smartphones retrieve the personal touch in communication that was lost with the advent of email and texting by reintroducing video calls and social media connections.

Reversal (What does it become when pushed to its limits?): The prevalence of smartphones can lead to information overload, a lack of privacy, the loss of in-person social interaction, over-reliance on external information sources, and addiction to social media and gaming.

PODCAST: **NEB Concepts**

The digiNEB project has produced a 'modular' podcast series that features conversations about sustainability, innovation, and human-centred design with leading architects, educators, and project leaders from the NEB community.

NEB Concepts allows listeners to explore themes by topic tags such as climate adaptation, technology integration, and interdisciplinary collaboration – or continue with the wide-ranging thoughts of a single interviewee. Each short episode provides a collection of ideas and practices, projects and reflections, highlighting the twin transitions and the transformative potential of the New European Bauhaus for a more inclusive and sustainable future.

Link: <https://digineb.eu/podcasts>

FURTHER READING

New European Bauhaus: Inspiring projects and ideas

https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/inspiring-projects-and-ideas_en

Innovation for place-based transformations

<https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC135826>

Mission-oriented innovation – a handbook from Vinnova

<https://www.vinnova.se/en/publikationer/mission-oriented-innovation---a-handbook-from-vinnova/>

A practical guide to the New European Bauhaus self-assessment method and tool

<https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC139118>

The Square: Putting place-based innovation policy for sustainability at the centre of policy making

<https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC131244>

Designing for the Common Good

<https://www.archdaily.com/tag/archdaily-topic-2024-designing-for-the-common-good>

Humanity's Biggest Problems Require a Whole New Media Mode

<https://www.wired.com/story/media-climate-change-film/>

Handbook for Sustainable Urban Development Strategies

<https://urban.jrc.ec.europa.eu/strategies/handbook-sud/>

Partnerships for Regional Innovation Playbook

<https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC129327>

Why Sustainable Development requires societal innovation and cannot be achieved without this

<https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/12/3/1270>

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